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Refugee Economic Integration: Prospects or Challenges?

Supervisor

Chiar.mo Enzo Valentini

PhD Candidate

Dott. Supriya Krishna Pilli

Coordinator

Chiar.mo Luca De Benedictis

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Table of Contents

Abstract	5
Chapter 1	7
1.1. Introduction	7
1.2. Literature review	8
I. Concept and history of refugee migration	8
II. Labor market integration of refugees: obstacles and key factors	9
III. Policy considerations for effective refugee integration	12
IV. EU key challenges	14
V. Case studies of refugee integration by countries	15
1.3. Lack of data and research gap	19
1.4. Methodology preview	20
1.5. Data and descriptive statistics	21
I. Natives, refugees, and other migrants	23
II. Migrants' main reason for initial migration	25
III. Refugees from five main origin areas	28
Chapter 2	31
Do refugees differ in their labor market outcomes compared to natives?	31
2.1. Employment likelihood of refugees compared to natives	31
2.2. Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to natives	33
2.3. Occupation likelihood of refugees compared to natives	34
2.4. Heterogeneities between refugees and natives based on gender, education, and locality	35
2.5. Visual representations of employment and language proficiency outcomes of migrant groups	38
2.6. Conditional and unconditional employment gaps of migrant groups	40
Chapter 3	42
How do refugees fare in the EU labor market among migrant groups?	42
3.1. Employment likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups	43
3.2. Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups	45
3.3. Occupation likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups	49
3.4. Heterogeneities between refugees and other migrant groups based on gender, education, and language skills	52
Chapter 4	60
Do refugee labor market outcomes differ based on their origin areas?	60
4.1. Employment likelihood among refugee groups	60
4.2. Unemployment and income distribution likelihood among refugee groups	62
4.3. Occupation likelihood among refugee groups	65
4.4. Heterogeneities among refugee groups based on gender, education, and language skills	68

Chapter 5	75
Conclusion	75
Appendix	77
Labor market outcomes of refugees across the five main EU regions	77
1. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Nordic region	77
2. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Anglo-Saxon region	78
3. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Eastern European region	79
4. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Mediterranean region	80
5. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Continental Western European region	82
6. Concluding remarks	83

List of Figures

1 Refugee versus other migrant employment outcomes	39
2 Refugee versus other migrant language outcomes	40
3 Conditional and unconditional employment gaps of migrant groups	41

List of Tables

1 Outcome variables of interest	21
2 Cohort sizes of migrant groups classified by their main reason for initial migration to EU destination countries	22
3 Cohort sizes of refugees based on their origin area	23
4 Descriptive statistics: Natives, refugees, and other migrants	25
5 Descriptive statistics: Migrants' main reason for initial migration	26
6 Descriptive statistics: Refugees from five main origin areas	29
7 Employment likelihood of refugees compared to natives	32
8 Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to natives	33
9 Occupational likelihood of refugees compared to natives	35
10 Heterogeneities between refugees and natives based on gender, education, and locality	38
11 Employment likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups	44
12 Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups	47
13 Occupation likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups	51
14 Heterogeneities between refugees and other migrant groups based on gender, education, and language skills	58
15 Employment likelihood among refugee groups	62
16 Unemployment and income distribution likelihood among refugee groups	63
17 Occupation likelihood among refugee groups	67
18 Heterogeneities among refugee groups based on gender, education, and language skills	74
19 Labor market outcomes of refugees across the five main EU regions	84

Abstract

This doctoral thesis studies the labor market outcomes of refugees i.e., individuals who initially entered EU destination countries to seek humanitarian protection. This study explores three main aspects: the comparison of refugees' labor market outcomes with those of natives, the labor market gaps between refugees and other migrants entering EU destination countries from the same origin areas and entry cohorts, and the differences in labor market outcomes among refugee groups based on the origin area they come from. Using probit regression models for empirical analysis and linear regression models for graphical representations, this research accounts for various socio-demographic characteristics, including gender, age, education, language proficiency, household composition, parental education, and urbanization degree. Additionally, it incorporates fixed effects for the destination country and origin area, and the destination country and entry cohort, to control for unobservable heterogeneities. A further dimension of this study investigates whether entering EU destination countries during an economic recession has a lasting impact on refugees' labor market outcomes. This is done by incorporating GDP growth rates at the arrival period of the individuals and incorporating fixed effects of the destination country and survey year.

The findings of this study reveal that refugees consistently experience worse labor market outcomes than natives and other migrant groups. They are significantly less likely to be employed and more likely to be unemployed, even when they have socio-demographic characteristics similar to natives and other migrants. Refugees are overrepresented in elementary and medium-skilled occupations and underrepresented in high-skilled occupations. Compared to other migrant groups, refugees face larger employment and unemployment gaps despite entering EU destination countries from the same origin areas and arrival cohorts. These differences persist even though refugees often have better education and language-related characteristics that should theoretically enhance their labor market outcomes.

Gender gaps further worsen these challenges. Refugee women are significantly disadvantaged in the labor market, with lower employment rates and higher unemployment rates compared to native women. However, compared to refugee men, they are less likely to be unemployed and more likely to hold high-skilled jobs and be in the top-income decile. Individuals' education and language skills play a crucial role in shaping labor market outcomes. However, refugees with tertiary education experience large employment and occupational gaps relative to similarly educated natives and other migrants. On the other hand, refugees without tertiary education are more likely to be concentrated in elementary jobs. However, advanced language proficiency in the host country significantly improves employment outcomes and reduces gaps in unemployment, high-skilled employment, and income distribution outcomes for refugees.

The timing of refugees' arrival and the economic conditions of a country at entry also shape long-term labor market outcomes. Refugees who arrived within the last ten years face larger employment and unemployment gaps compared to refugees with extended residences in EU destination countries. Furthermore, entering EU countries during a recession significantly reduces employment outcomes, and increases the likelihood of working in elementary jobs, and being in the bottom-income decile. These recession effects are particularly pronounced among older migrant cohorts.

Labor market disadvantages are not uniform across all refugee groups, with refugees from North Africa and the Middle East facing the most significant barriers to employment. These groups also experience the highest unemployment rates and the lowest likelihood of holding high-skilled jobs. Refugees from North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, and Asia are disproportionately employed in elementary occupations. Refugee women from North Africa and the Middle East have particularly low employment rates. At the same time, refugee women from Latin America, Africa, and

the Middle East exhibit higher unemployment rates.¹ Tertiary education helps mitigate employment and occupational disadvantages for refugees from African and Middle Eastern regions.² Furthermore, North African and Middle Eastern refugees without advanced language proficiency are significantly disadvantaged in labor market integration, highlighting the importance of language acquisition in improving economic outcomes.

Keywords: refugees, labor market outcomes, EU destination countries

¹Africa is referred to its entirety, i.e., including both North African and Other African regions.

²Africa is referred to its entirety, i.e., including both North African and Other African regions.

Chapter 1

1.1. Introduction

The global landscape has witnessed a sudden surge in forced migration, with millions seeking refuge outside their homelands due to conflict, persecution, natural disasters, and other humanitarian crises. Developed nations, including EU countries, have become primary destinations for displaced individuals and their families. Ever since the 2015 European refugee crisis, the integration of refugees has become a central debate in Europe's political and economic spheres. Moreover, the rising refugee inflows into Europe have highlighted the critical need to integrate refugees into its societies and labor markets effectively. Though the word 'Refugee' in many EU countries remains highly politicized, Europe has been engaging itself in continuous efforts to establish a unified asylum framework for effective refugee integration.

On the other hand, refugees face challenges in integrating into destination societies, given the forced nature of their displacement. Not just the violence they endure in their home country but also the uncertain and dangerous migration paths they take to reach a destination country compound these challenges. A study by [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#) highlights that while some economic integration obstacles are inherent due to the forced nature of refugee displacement, the governments of the destination countries, too, play a crucial role in determining the future socio-economic integration of refugees.

Prior research argues that governments may hinder refugee integration by implementing suboptimal asylum policies. These policies are influenced by a complex trade-off in decision-making. Efforts to reduce refugee inflows through restrictive border policies may also negatively affect the refugee populations in the destination country and, in turn, impact their long-term socio-economic integration. Short-term political considerations may lead to policies that minimize immediate costs rather than maximizing long-term benefits. This approach could result in potential long-term adverse effects and the under-investment of effective refugee integration. For example, dispersing asylum seekers to remote deprived areas could offer immediate savings in budget but should be weighed against the future negative impact on refugee labor market integration. Overcoming short-sightedness while designing asylum policies is an ongoing challenge for governments of the EU destination countries.

Refugees, compared to natives and other migrants, stand out as a unique demographic group that started gaining attention in developed nations. Research and policies now focus on analyzing refugee socio-economic situations in destination countries, understanding how refugees integrate into societies and economies, and the challenges refugees face in destination countries. Understanding the refugee experiences in destination societies and their distinct characteristics has become increasingly important in creating effective refugee policies.

Refugees in the destination countries' labor markets often encounter unique challenges compared to natives because of the forced nature of displacement and traumatic experiences in their migration journey. Additionally, refugees differ from natives in their characteristics and often face additional problems like language barriers, differences in educational backgrounds, and the recognition of qualifications they acquired in their home countries. Also, unlike other migrant groups, refugees bear the burden of violence, trauma, the forced nature of displacement, and the sudden interruption of their professional trajectories in their home countries that could impact their integration into the destination countries' labor market. Their situations, therefore, differ from those of economic migrants who choose to migrate voluntarily to destination countries, a process known as "self-selection" in migration. This self-selection process varies between refugees and those primarily migrating for economic reasons, commonly known as "economic migrants." Economic migrants, such as work migrants, decide to move based on factors related to potential economic gains from migration. While economic

factors could also be an influencing contributor for refugees while leaving their homes when escaping conflict or oppression, factors related to potential discrimination and security in their home country are likely more significant in the self-selection process for refugees (Borjas, 1987; Chiswick, 1999). Therefore, refugee migration is often linked to the concept of "forced marriage," while other migrants are related to the concept of a "chosen match." Also, refugees are a complex group of non-economic migrants compared to other non-economic migrant groups, such as study and family migrants in the field of migration research.

Both economic and non-economic migrants choose a destination country based on their interest in migration, while refugees do not have a meaningful choice in the matter of migration. Refugees additionally face challenges associated with not being accepted by the destination society, employment difficulties, unstable residential status, and the imminent threat of repatriation that contribute to the prolonged mental health challenges (Bogic et al., 2012; Kone et al., 2019). Therefore, understanding the labor market dynamics of refugees in EU destination countries is essential for their effective socio-economic integration. Recognizing these distinctions is crucial for developing policies that address the specific needs of refugees and contribute to their successful integration in destination countries.

Additionally, refugee migration decisions are primarily driven by push factors rather than pull factors (Hatton, 2009). As a result, refugees may be less responsive to the destination country's economic conditions. This potentially increases the refugee's likelihood of arriving during economic downturns that could hinder their long-term labor market outcomes in the destination country. Apart from the potential differences in the arrival time of refugees to destination countries, the negative impacts of migrating to a destination country during a recession could be more profound and persistent for refugees. Therefore, refugees could typically start with a significantly large labor market disadvantage.

Furthermore, in the European context, the ongoing refugee crisis since 2015 highlights the need to study how EU societies are receiving and integrating refugees. Europe's unique cultural and political situation could lead to diverse approaches to the socio-economic integration of refugee sub-groups and, in turn, their labor market outcomes. Therefore, policymakers and researchers could gain valuable insights into effective integration strategies for refugees by comparing refugee experiences with natives, other migrant groups, and refugee sub-groups. This helps identify challenges, patterns, and potential best practices in refugee integration. Therefore, this doctoral thesis aims to contribute to the existing body of literature on the labor market outcomes of refugees by shedding light on the multifaceted dynamics of refugees in EU destination countries compared to natives, other migrants, and refugee sub-groups. This research will focus on four key labor market outcomes, i.e., employment, unemployment, occupation, and income distribution indicators, to enhance the understanding of refugees' unique challenges and contributions within the European labor market. By doing so, this research aspires to inform evidence-based policies that foster a more supportive and inclusive environment for refugees in the EU labor market and, in turn, potential economic gains to the EU destination countries through the effective use of the existing refugee capital.

1.2. Literature review

I. Concept and history of refugee migration

Globally and within the European context, forced migration has been a complex and evolving phenomenon characterized by significant shifts in refugee patterns. Nevertheless, modern refugee legislation roots back to the aftermath of World War II, driven by decolonization, and the Cold War, driven by geopolitical issues. The 1951 Refugee Convention, which defines the legal status of a refugee, was

initially drafted in response to World War II and the Cold War, focusing on refugees only from Europe. However, the subsequent adoption of the 1967 Protocol was expanded to remove the geographic and time limitations to address refugees seeking international protection worldwide. According to the 1951 GCR (Global Compact on Refugee) convention:

”A refugee is someone who has been forced to flee his or her country because of persecution, war, or violence. A refugee has a well-founded fear of persecution for reasons of race, religion, nationality, political opinion, or membership in a particular social group.”

While World War II triggered mass population movements, including the displacement of Holocaust survivors and the expulsion of millions of ethnic Germans from Eastern Europe, several other historical events have significantly contributed to forced migration. These include the Chilean diaspora of the 1970s and 1980s, the collapse of Eastern European regimes and the dissolution of former Yugoslavia in the 1990s, the armed conflict in Afghanistan in the early 2000s, the Arab Spring in the 2010s, the 2015 Syrian refugee crisis, and the ongoing mass displacement caused by the Russia-Ukraine war since 2022.

Europe has long been the main destination for refugees fleeing conflict, with the number of arrivals steadily increasing in recent years. While war remains a primary driver of displacement, the growing impact of climate change and natural disasters has further contributed to this trend. As these environmental challenges intensify, the number of individuals seeking refuge in Europe is expected to rise even further.

The 2015 refugee crisis, triggered by the Syrian war, marked a particularly sharp increase in asylum applications, with Greece and Italy emerging as major entry points for those seeking protection in EU countries. According to the UNHCR Global Trends Report (2021), the world faces an unprecedented displacement crisis, with over 89.3 million people forcibly displaced due to violence, conflict, persecution, and human rights violations. More than 7 million individuals in Europe have been displaced across borders, reflecting a 3 percent increase compared to the previous year. Furthermore, as of September 2022, the Russia-Ukraine war had displaced over 7.4 million refugees, and in the same year, the EU received 881,220 first-time asylum applications.

For some individuals, seeking refuge in a host country is a temporary solution as they intend to return home once the conflict or disaster subsides. However, for many others, prolonged instability in their country of origin leads to permanent resettlement in destination countries. As a result, Europe has repeatedly found itself at the center of political and policy debates, raising critical questions regarding the effective economic integration of refugees within EU destination countries.

II. Labor market integration of refugees: obstacles and key factors

Refugees, distinct from other migrant groups, represent a unique category of migrants who are primarily compelled to leave their home countries due to conflict and imminent threats. Consequently, their migration is predominantly influenced by the push factors of their home country rather than the pull factors of the destination country. This peculiarity results in substantial variability in the socio-economic conditions of refugees within the destination country (Chin and Cortes, 2015). While EU destination countries are consistently putting efforts to integrate refugees into their societies, effective integration into their labor markets appears to have obstacles stemming from political situations and less effective integration policies. During the 2015 Syrian refugee crisis, Europe witnessed the rise of barriers and fences at its borders, indicative of a growing resistance to refugees within Europe. Some political parties have voiced concerns, stating that refugees are a threat to the European economy and

societies (Europe, 2020; Guardian, 2015; Quartz, 2015). Within this shifting landscape, reports have emerged regarding grey areas within the EU labor market, as revealed by administrative data and public surveys.

Beyond labor market barriers, religious discrimination and gender inequality continue to surface as significant challenges in European societies. Recent policies such as the [EU-Turkey-Deal \(2022\)](#) and the [UK-Rawanda-Deal \(2022\)](#) aimed at deterring those seeking refuge in EU member states serve as notable examples that restrict refugees' freedom to choose their country of asylum. Such hostile measures contradict the principles outlined in the 1951 GCR Convention and its 1967 Protocol on non-refoulement. The resistance towards refugees at the EU borders has reverberations inside its countries, particularly in terms of the challenges surrounding the effective integration of refugees into its labor markets.

Despite political resistance, a substantial body of scholarly literature supports the potential economic benefits member states could gain through the effective socio-economic integration of refugees. The prevailing monetary losses are increasingly attributed to the ineffective and inequitable integration policies that have evolved in recent years. In light of the unprecedented surge in refugee flows experienced by Europe since 2015, the effective integration of refugees into the labor market has emerged as a critical area of future research. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that refugees face distinct disadvantages compared to other migrant cohorts, including disruptions in education and work in their home countries, trauma from displacement, and lack of qualification recognition and language barrier in the destination country.

Future refugee inflows into Europe are unavoidable as conflicts and natural disasters primarily drive refugee migration. Therefore, this underscores the pressing need for effective socio-economic integration of refugees. However, the EU continues to struggle with structural and policy-related barriers, leading to economic inefficiencies and missed opportunities for refugees and host economies.

One of the primary barriers to refugee integration is the **physiological distress and trauma** resulting from conflict, persecution, and violence, followed by their interim sojourns in refugee camps by the time they arrive in their destination countries (Burnett and Peel, 2001; Porter and Haslam, 2005).

Refugees frequently experience elevated mental health issues, including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, and mood disorders. While PTSD is often linked to war-related trauma, post-migration stressors such as social exclusion, legal uncertainties, and perceived discrimination further exacerbate mental health challenges (Bogic et al., 2012). Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach, incorporating both mental health support and economic empowerment initiatives to facilitate successful refugee integration.

Employment ban is another significant barrier that hinders refugee integration into EU labor markets. Many European countries impose employment restrictions on refugees while their asylum claims are under review, with bans lasting between 3 to 12 months and, in some cases, indefinitely. Over an eight-year period, these bans have resulted in significant economic losses of 37.6 billion EUR to the EU economy. Even after the bans are lifted, additional restrictions on sectors, job types, and contract durations continue to limit employment opportunities for refugees, thereby hindering their full integration into the EU labor market (Fasani et al., 2021).

Much like economic migrants, refugees also engage in a self-selection process when choosing their destination countries, aligning their decisions with their existing human capital (Aksoy and Poutvaara, 2021). Consequently, a pertinent question arises: Why do refugees consistently underperform in labor market outcomes compared with their counterparts, i.e., other migrants and natives? A study by Brell

et al. (2020) delves into refugee and economic migrant integration using the micro-data of many developed countries. Their findings underscore significant disparities in the integration outcomes of refugees, primarily attributable to the initial labor market disadvantages that refugees encounter. The duration of initial employment bans imposed upon the entry of refugee cohorts emerges mainly as a key factor influencing their future labor market integration. These bans lead to the underutilization of refugee human capital resulting in foregone tax revenues and social security contributions (Fasani et al., 2021). Conversely, facilitating the early integration of refugees into the labor market holds the potential to yield fiscal dividends for destination countries. Such early access generates tax revenues and recovers the initial expenditures incurred in processing the refugee asylum claims, ultimately contributing positively to the destination country's public finances (Aiyar et al., 2016).

Additionally, geographical **dispersal policies** have adverse effects on refugee integration. For instance, the NASS dispersal policy in the UK isolates refugees in areas far from urban job markets. This geographical separation of refugees significantly impacts their economic integration prospects, resulting in elevated unemployment rates, and even among those refugees who secure employment earn below-average wages (Fasani et al., 2022; Phillimore and Goodson, 2006). These dispersal policies imposed on asylum seekers, along with the employment bans by restricting their labor market access, have been criticized by research scholars due to the enduring economic losses faced by EU member states. However, there is a potential opportunity to harness the talents and abilities of refugees to rejuvenate deprived areas in EU destination countries.

Another disadvantage that refugees face is the **prolonged asylum procedure and the absence of a unified asylum framework** for interpreting the 1951 GCR among member states, contributing to significant uncertainty in determining refugee status for individuals seeking protection. The prolonged asylum procedures in European countries negatively impact refugees' future economic integration and increase the public expenditure incurred by the destination countries throughout the asylum process. As evidenced by Hainmueller et al. (2016) in their study, with each passing year of the waiting period for asylum claim resolution, the employment rate among refugees decreases by 5 percentage points. Despite these longstanding adverse effects, the absence of a common asylum framework among EU member states has created uncertainty when determining the refugee status of an asylum seeker. Also, the categorization of the status of the asylum seekers within the destination country, especially whether they are granted "temporary protection" or "permanent refugee status," carries importance in influencing the subsequent process of labor market integration of refugees. Specifically, obtaining a temporary protection status yields substantial positive employment probabilities among asylum migrants (Auer, 2018).

Another critical factor is **social networks**, which play a pivotal role in shaping refugees' access to information, resources, and employment opportunities. These networks can be categorized into:

1. Destination country social networks – These networks provide job market access, housing support, and essential services, helping refugees integrate more effectively.
2. Country of origin social networks – These networks serve as emotional, financial, and logistical support sources, particularly in the early resettlement stages.

The impact of destination country social networks is further shaped by housing access, language proficiency, and the duration of stay. Early engagement with co-national and religious groups improves access to employment and stabilizes integration. While social networks alone may not directly determine employment, the absence of such networks can significantly hinder labor market outcomes.

Moreover, factors such as pre-migration qualifications and employment history play important roles

in shaping the labor market outcomes of refugees. Among all, **high-quality language training** has been found to expedite employment access and improve job quality. To enhance labor market outcomes for refugees, [Cheung and Phillimore \(2014\)](#) propose the concept of "support housing." This approach involves providing refugees with housing options close to their existing social networks, such as family and friends. As opposed to "dispersal housing," this approach has been found to yield more favorable labor market outcomes. Additionally, cohabitation with a partner has been associated with increased access to employment opportunities. In summary, the interplay between social networks, housing access, and language proficiency, among other factors, significantly influences the labor market outcomes of refugees.

Furthermore, the refugees' **country of birth** emerges as a key determinant in influencing their employment outcomes. For instance, refugees from former Yugoslavia exhibit higher employment rates than refugees from other regions. Similarly, refugees from Iran tend to achieve higher employment rates than their counterparts from Iraq and Afghanistan ([Bevelander and Pendakur, 2014](#)). Additionally, the most pronounced employment gaps are identified among refugees from North Africa and the Middle East when contrasted with refugees from other origin areas ([Dustmann et al., 2017](#)).

Additionally, refugees with backgrounds directly impacted by war experiences exhibit significantly higher rates of mental disorders and health issues when compared to refugees not affected by war regions. Also, specific demographic factors aggravate mental health issues, i.e., female refugees, older refugees, and unemployed refugees report higher levels of stress and mental health issues. Male refugees and young refugees who do not reside with their families or partners tend to exhibit higher rates of substance use ([Bogic et al., 2012](#)).

Human capital is another critical determinant that profoundly affects the economic integration of migrants in a destination country ([Chiswick and Miller, 2001](#)). Refugees, however, often underperform in the labor market due to the failure of the recognition of their qualifications and work experience that they bring from their home country to the destination country ([Ager and Strang, 2008](#)). The impact of refugees' foreign human capital, that is, their education and work experience acquired in their home country, is characterized by limited effect on the destination country's employment rates and overall labor market participation. Additionally, it exerts a minimal positive impact on refugee earnings. Therefore, it is crucial to address the skills recognition challenge to enhance the labor market outcomes of refugees. This can be achieved through strategies such as credential recognition and investment in developing the refugee human capital in the destination country. Such measures can potentially yield benefits not only in the short term but also in the long term, ultimately fostering more favorable labor market outcomes for refugees ([Aydemir, 2011](#)). Another study by [Friedberg \(2000\)](#) finds that the destination country's human capital plays a significant role in shaping refugees' employment and income outcomes. Factors such as education, work experience acquired in a destination country, and proficiency in the destination country's language strongly affect labor market integration. Language proficiency plays a crucial role in the employment prospects and earnings potential among non-white ethnic minorities ([Dustmann and Fabbri, 2003a](#)). The implementation of early integration mechanisms, such as language and vocational training ([Aksoy and Poutvaara, 2021](#)), along with job search assistance programs ([Battisti et al., 2019b](#)), play a crucial role in facilitating the labor market integration of refugees. Such initiatives contribute to fostering greater inclusivity of refugees within European societies.

III. Policy considerations for effective refugee integration

In conclusion, ineffective policies have hindered refugee labor market integration in the EU, leading to significant economic losses. Though Europe works as a union of member states and adopts the free movement of people policy, it has encountered difficulties in achieving robust labor market integra-

tion of refugees. This difficulty arises partly from an imbalance between the surplus of human capital that refugees bring to certain EU countries lacking corresponding employment opportunities in the relevant sectors and other EU countries facing unfulfilled job vacancies owing to human capital shortages. The absence of a unified asylum framework among member states also burdens EU destination countries substantially. A visible difference appears in the volume of asylum applications across EU member states (Hatton, 2015).

While refugee labor market outcomes are influenced by a mix of complex factors, including their initial flight from their home country due to conflict and persecution coupled with pre and post-migration trauma, the exposure to rigid asylum policies is further worsened by social isolation and prolonged waiting times for asylum status outcomes. Additionally, refugees typically have lower educational qualifications and exhibit limited language proficiency in the destination country. They also often face significant unemployment challenges in the labor market. Furthermore, a common pattern emerges among those who secure employment: they tend to occupy low-skilled positions and earn wages that are below the average.

Nevertheless, it is crucial to recognize that refugee wage and occupational characteristics are not permanent but can evolve with time, particularly with the attainment of the human capital of the destination country. Therefore, effective policies can play a crucial role in this transformation. For instance, initiatives that provide childcare support and financial assistance, such as loans for education and training, can facilitate refugees' access to high-skilled employment opportunities in destination countries. Moreover, gradually reducing social support for refugees who engage in education and training programs can encourage refugees to transition into more favorable occupational positions, thereby enhancing their earnings potential within the destination country's labor market. Furthermore, ensuring access to affordable housing in neighborhoods offering improved economic prospects can prove highly advantageous for refugees, contributing to their overall integration and success in the labor market.

Upon the arrival of refugees, implementing proactive programs such as skill audits and directly engaging employers and trainers from the outset of integration strategies can yield substantial benefits. In particular, validating and recognizing the skills refugees bring from their origin countries and aligning them with the destination country's requirements can empower refugees to pursue high-skilled and more stable employment opportunities in destination countries (Phillimore and Goodson, 2006). This transformation has the potential to benefit refugees and contribute positively to the destination country by effectively using the unique skills and experiences from the very beginning that refugees bring from their country of origin.

Studies conducted by Dustmann et al. (2017) suggest that, in contrast to dispersal policies, the concentration of refugee networks within a specific region can significantly enhance their labor market integration. Early access to ethnic networks during the initial stages of labor market integration has yielded more favorable employment outcomes among refugees (Ruiz and Vargas-Silva, 2017). While refugees often embark on their migration journey with the intent of returning to their home country once the conflict abates, the prolonged and destabilizing nature of these conflicts frequently culminates in their permanent settlement in the destination country. Consequently, refugees exhibit the highest rates of naturalization compared to other migrant cohorts in EU destination countries. However, the lack of effective refugee policies and insufficient coordination among EU member states causes high unemployment rates among refugees. Even when refugees secure employment, they often struggle to attain wage and occupational parity with other migrants and native workers. A substantial proportion of refugees earn incomes below the average earnings of their fellow migrant groups. Paradoxically, refugees tend to excel in the long run in terms of language proficiency in the destination country more than their counterparts. Nonetheless, they frequently occupy low-skilled

positions within the destination country with suboptimal wage conditions.

According to [Adda et al. \(2021\)](#), the policies initially imposed on migrants upon their arrival and during their residency critically shape their investment in human capital and subsequent labor market outcomes. Therefore, effective refugee policies are key to effective refugee integration in destination countries. Also, the methods individuals employ to find a job impact both the duration of their employment and earnings. Specifically, individuals with lower qualifications and skills tend to utilize the Public Employment Service (PES) as their primary job search method, often acquiring temporary and part-time positions ([Weber and Mahringer, 2008](#)). Research conducted by [Addison and Portugal \(2002\)](#) further reinforces this observation. Their findings suggest that reliance on the Public Employment Service leads individuals to less lucrative and more unstable paths in their job searches. On the contrary, directly contacting employers and utilizing social networks tend to yield better job opportunities. In the context of asylum migrants, there is a pronounced reliance on public employment agencies as the primary means of job search compared to other migrant groups and native workers ([Kone et al., 2019](#)). This reliance on the Public Employment Service often translates into lower recognition of an individual's human capital, resulting in lower wages and a higher prevalence of temporary employment.

In summary, implementing a cost-neutral policy strategy, achieved via legislative measures that remove employment restrictions within the labor market holds the potential to yield dual benefits. Specifically, this approach is anticipated to result in economic advantages to EU countries and simultaneously facilitate the successful integration of refugees into the labor market ([Fasani et al., 2021](#)). Prompt access to networks and prompt access to labor markets mutually serve as avenues of benefit, encompassing both the provision of support from the destination society to refugees and the refugees' capacity to contribute optimally to the destination economy ([Ruiz and Vargas-Silva, 2017](#)). Necessary adjustments to the current policies are crucial to mitigate the lengthy waiting period within the asylum procedure, generating uncertainty and demoralizing refugees, thereby hindering their effective integration into the labor market. Such collective policy modifications would limit public expenditures linked to welfare benefits for refugees and boost government revenue through the tax contributions of employed refugees.

A marginal cost-benefit analysis reveals that a mere reduction of 66 days, equivalent to 10 percent of the waiting period for the refugee asylum claim, could yield substantial gains, amounting to 5.6 million dollars within a single year to the host country ([Hainmueller et al., 2016](#)). Future policy considerations should also prioritize addressing mental health challenges among refugees, as well as tackling issues related to language proficiency and the recognition of their qualifications and prior work experience from the refugee's home country. Thereby, enhanced economic integration of refugees would foster greater acceptance within destination societies, reducing the likelihood of backlash and discrimination.

IV. EU key challenges

A triad of formidable challenges surrounds the current European landscape, each having profound implications for the EU region:

1. Ageing population — One of the main challenges of Europe is its aging population. The demographic shift towards an older population poses complex economic and social difficulties.
2. Emigration issues — The migration landscape in EU member states divides individuals into two primary categories: intra-EU migrants and non-EU migrants. However, Europe faces the complexities of emigration as its citizens seek opportunities outside their homelands. The dynamics of this outward

migration have multifaceted consequences.

3. Inefficiency in the effective use of refugee human capital — Another pressing issue centers on the underutilization of refugee human capital.

Refugees with valuable skills and expertise should be regarded as a positive resource that could ease the strains of the aging population in EU destination countries. The strategic integration of refugees has the potential to yield lasting contributions to the public finances in the long run in the EU destination countries (Åslund et al., 2017; Phillimore and Goodson, 2006). Moreover, the early and effective integration of refugees could mitigate fiscal burdens, offering a practical remedy to the aging population and declining fertility rates that currently afflict Europe (Aiyar et al., 2016; Commission, 2018). Hence, considering its aging population and fertility challenges, Europe would require an increased influx of migrants and citizens in the foreseeable future, where effective use of refugees would be a valuable asset to EU destination countries.

V. Case studies of refugee integration by countries

The pull factors, such as the promise of enhanced employment opportunities and higher earnings in developed countries, can act as a compelling incentive for refugees, similar to the motivations of economic migrants. While refugees constitute a relatively smaller subset of the overall migrant population, they tend to gravitate toward particular destinations, including but not limited to Germany, the United Kingdom, Sweden, and France. As of the 2014 EU-level data, most refugees comprised men, with their numbers exceeding that of female refugees (Dumont et al., 2016; Hatton, 2015).

In Sweden, a study conducted by Lundborg (2013) on the labor market outcomes of refugees considering the period of migration and the country of origin of refugees revealed significant variations in the employment outcomes of different refugee groups. Even after residing in Sweden for many years, refugees originating from countries like Iran, Iraq, and certain regions of Africa were found to face extended periods of unemployment and initial difficulties in entering the labor market. In contrast, refugees from Latin America and Eastern Europe tended to experience shorter periods of unemployment.

Additionally, the refugee employment rates in Sweden do not converge with native workers even after many years. Overall, the employment gap between refugees and native-born individuals was substantial, with refugees initially facing employment rates at 70 percent compared to natives. The gap gradually closed, and the employment rate reached around 90 percent in a decade. However, the gap showed no signs of convergence even after the prolonged residence of refugees in Sweden thereafter. On the other hand, the initial unemployment rate among refugees upon arrival is pronounced but tends to shrink over time. However, the gap persists and does not entirely close.

Furthermore, refugees originating from Islamic nations had particularly challenging labor market outcomes, especially during their first 20 years in Sweden. Despite these challenges, the unemployment gap between refugee women and native women was relatively smaller compared to the gap between refugee men and native men. However, labor market participation among refugee women remained low in Sweden. The findings underscored the need for targeted policies and interventions to address these disparities and enhance the economic integration of refugees in the Swedish labor market. According to their study, the country of birth and the reason for migration significantly impacted employment probabilities and earnings differentials.

Another research by Åslund et al. (2017) within the Swedish labor market that focused on refugee cohorts reveals that non-Western refugees do not attain parity with natives concerning employment

rates and wage earnings. Refugees predominantly tend to secure employment in the service industry. A study by [Edin et al. \(2004\)](#) reveals that a significant transformation in refugee reception policies occurred in Sweden between 1984 and 1994 when the country implemented a reform aimed at dispersing refugees and assigning them to regions with lower concentrations of migrants. Their research reveals that refugee cohorts who entered Sweden during this period experienced a substantial decline in earnings by 25 percent and a simultaneous increase in the unemployment rate by 6 percent, even after residing for eight years in Sweden. Sweden and Denmark, among other European countries, have stopped implementing such dispersal policies.

Another study by [Bevelander and Pendakur \(2014\)](#) on the comparative analysis of labor market outcomes among refugees and family migrants in Canada, and Sweden finds that both these non-economic migrant groups' wage earnings are higher in Canada compared to Sweden. Their study further revealed variations in labor market participation rates, employment outcomes, and earnings among refugee groups. In their research, refugees originating from Former Yugoslavia had the highest participation rates, followed by refugees from Iran, while those from Iraq and Afghanistan faced relatively lower employment rates. Additionally, the gaps in employment rates were more pronounced in Canada than in Sweden, based on the migrant category and country of birth. The reason for migration substantially affected labor market outcomes in Canada and Sweden, particularly affecting women more than men. Earnings differentials were also evident between the two countries, with earnings generally lower in Sweden than in Canada. The country of birth of refugees played a significant role in shaping earnings profiles in both countries.

Notably, Sweden implemented a comprehensive 18-month settlement training program for both the non-economic migrant groups. This program comprised language and skills training, credential recognition and assessment, and housing assistance. In contrast, Canada provided settlement assistance, language training, income support, and housing assistance to refugees, while family migrants in Canada received language training assistance only. The research findings by [Bevelander and Pendakur \(2014\)](#) indicated that such assistance programs contributed to better labor market outcomes among refugees than among family migrants in Canada despite refugees facing physiological and social disadvantages. In contrast, having a graduate degree yielded higher returns in Sweden, reflecting the importance of skills equivalency assessment measures implemented by Sweden to benefit refugees.

In Switzerland, language training emerges as a crucial factor influencing the successful labor market integration of refugees ([Auer, 2018](#)). Their research on the Swiss labor market contrasts with the prevailing approach of randomly assigning refugees to cantons where their mother tongue is spoken. Instead, they explore the outcomes of a contrasting strategy that allows refugees to choose their preferred canton. Remarkably, this alternative approach results in a 15 percent increase in refugees' employment probabilities within two years of registering as job seekers. Further, the shift towards extensive language training courses bears significant benefits for refugees in Switzerland. Refugees who participated in language training programs and obtained certificates accredited by Swiss institutes exhibited employment probabilities on par with refugees who shared the same mother tongue as the canton they resided in. Furthermore, the absence of established ethnic networks hinders refugees' labor market outcomes.

Another study in Switzerland on individuals who applied for asylum between 1994 and 2004 by [Hainmueller et al. \(2016\)](#) finds that the average waiting period for asylum decision outcome is 665 days. Their study emphasizes that securing employment several years before the resolution of an asylum claim significantly enhances employment outcomes by 48 percentage points. On the contrary, the detrimental effects stemming from prolonged waiting times for asylum claim resolution are two-fold: refugee skill wastage and psychological discouragement.

In the UK, a study conducted by [Ruiz and Vargas-Silva \(2018\)](#) finds that seeking asylum is associated with some of the poorest labor market outcomes linked to lower employment rates, weekly earnings, and hours worked per week. Another study in the UK by [Ruiz and Vargas-Silva \(2017\)](#) finds that the administration of the asylum process bears lasting economic implications for refugee labor market outcomes. Extended asylum procedures substantially impact the future economic integration of refugees. In the UK, refugees are prohibited from engaging in employment for the entire duration of their asylum claim processing, a policy that not only deteriorates the existing skills that refugees bring from their home country but also worsens their mental health, resulting in refugees' reliance on social welfare programs, which, in turn, leads to higher levels of unemployment within the refugee population.

Remarkably, refugees in the UK exhibit a greater inclination towards self-employment compared to other migrants and native-born individuals. They own small and medium-sized businesses contributing to entrepreneurial characteristics ([Kone et al., 2019](#)). However, gender differences appear in the UK labor market. The employment gap between male and female refugees is more pronounced than between male refugees and native-born male individuals ([Ruiz and Vargas-Silva, 2018](#)). Consequently, female refugees face more labor market disadvantage compared to male refugees and other female migrants ([Ruiz and Vargas-Silva, 2017](#)). A study conducted by [Dustmann et al. \(2017\)](#) finds that though refugees tend to lag behind economic migrants in labor market integration in the EU destination countries, the most substantial gaps between refugees and economic migrants are observed in the United Kingdom and Ireland.

A study conducted by [De Vroome and Van Tubergen \(2010\)](#) on refugees arriving from different origin countries to the Netherlands finds that education obtained in the destination country positively influences the labor market integration of refugees. However, this favorable effect is often offset by the challenge of unrecognized educational qualifications acquired in the refugees' country of origin. Additionally, proficiency in the language of the destination country and social capital, particularly connections with native individuals within the destination country, significantly contribute to enhancing refugees' employment and occupational outcomes.

In the Norwegian context, a study by [Sarvimäki \(2017\)](#) focusing on refugees of the 1990-2013 cohort finds that refugees from Afghanistan, Iraq, and Somalia have higher unemployment rates, lower wages, and higher dependence on social benefits. And though refugees, compared to other migrants, tend to narrow the gap in labor market outcomes over time, they often fall short of attaining employment and wage rates on par with native-born individuals. A longitudinal study conducted on the employment and wage patterns by [Bratsberg et al. \(2014\)](#) on refugees and other migrants coming from both developed and developing countries to Norway reveals that refugees and other migrants originating from developing countries exhibit higher rates of unemployment and higher dependence on the social security assistance.

In the United States, a study conducted by [Connor \(2010\)](#) finds despite similar employment rates between refugees and economic migrants, refugees typically occupy low-skilled jobs, subsequently resulting in lower wages. Also, compared to their occupational status in their country of origin, refugees tend to accept low-skilled jobs as a means of economic survival. Another research conducted by [Cortes \(2004\)](#), utilizing synthetic panel data, finds that refugees and economic migrants in the United States reveal intriguing insights. Despite refugees and economic migrants initially having similar levels of language skills, refugees experienced lower wages and worked fewer hours during the early years of their settlement. However, after 10 years of stay in the United States, both refugees and economic migrants showed improvements in overall labor market performance. Still, refugees demonstrated more substantial economic gains through increased wages and work hours than economic migrants. Furthermore, refugees have reported superior language skills by 11 percent

compared to economic migrants.

Different destination countries have adopted varying policies that impact refugees' mental health and employment outcomes. For instance, Germany's policy of granting residence permits exclusively to refugees undergoing post-traumatic stress treatment may inadvertently lead to lower employment rates in refugees with mental health disorders. Many refugees in Germany struggle to obtain work permits and find themselves inclined to low-skilled jobs that do not align with their actual skills. Additionally, inadequate accommodation leads to most refugees experiencing high unemployment rates and unrecovered prolonged mental health issues. In contrast, Italy's policy of granting residence permits to refugees who are already employed or have family members who are employed in the country has resulted in higher employment rates and fewer reports of mental health disorders among refugees.

A study conducted by [Bogic et al. \(2012\)](#), focusing on former Yugoslavian refugees resettled in Italy, the UK, and Germany sheds light on the mental health challenges faced by refugees, particularly those arriving from war-affected countries. The research reveals that refugees with backgrounds directly impacted by war experiences exhibit significantly higher rates of mental disorders and health issues when compared to refugees not affected by war regions. Consequently, anxiety disorders are also prevalent among this group of refugees coming from war-affected areas.

Another study conducted on multiple European countries by [Fasani et al. \(2021\)](#) finds that a distinct dichotomy emerged in the EU's approach to labor market access for refugees during the 2015 European refugee crisis. While Norway, Sweden, Portugal, and Greece demonstrated a progressive stance by permitting immediate labor market entry for refugees. Conversely, other European countries imposed employment bans ranging from 2-12 months, while Ireland and Lithuania opted for a more restrictive approach, imposing indefinite bans on refugee employment. Also, Norway, the Netherlands, the UK, and Ireland continue actively enforcing dispersal policies that allocate refugees to regions typically situated away from urban centers.

Other studies conducted by [Åslund et al. \(2017\)](#); [Becker and Ferrara \(2019\)](#); [Bevelander \(2020\)](#); [Brell et al. \(2020\)](#) on refugee economic outcomes in developed countries find that, despite struggling with an initial labor market disadvantage, the refugee employment rates gradually improve over the period of their residency in the destination country. However, the gap does not entirely close when compared to other migrants, even after many years of residency in destination countries. Similarly, the refugee unemployment gap gradually declines over the period of their stay in the destination country. However, this gap still does not entirely close even after many years of their residence. Those refugees who secure employment typically work fewer hours, occupy low-skilled jobs, and earn comparatively lower wages than other migrant groups. Even after controlling socio-demographic characteristics such as age, gender, education, country of origin, and the region of residence within the destination country, this employment gap persists.

In summary, integrating refugees into the labor market represents a crucial focal point within the policy discourse of migrant integration in Europe. While integration is a complex two-way process involving active engagement and contributions from both the refugee population and the receiving countries, the destination countries' capacity to host more refugees does not necessarily correlate with their ability to integrate refugees into their labor markets successfully. Successful labor market integration assessment depends on various metrics such as refugee employment, unemployment, income, and occupational outcomes. Depending upon the migrant's classification as an economic or non-economic migrant and the specific policies embraced by the destination countries, coupled with the individual's human capital and language proficiency acquired in the destination country, can either serve as an asset or a constraint in the labor market integration outcomes. For economic and

non-economic migrants, employment is a cornerstone in the integration process (Ager and Strang, 2008). However, the socio-economic integration trajectories of non-economic refugees significantly diverge from those of economic migrants. Like refugees, family migrants also struggle with elevated unemployment rates, positioning them among the migrant groups that face substantial employment challenges. However, in the EU, asylum migrants face higher rates of unemployment compared to all the other migrant groups and native-born individuals. The involuntary yet imperative migration undertaken by refugees in response to threats within their home countries introduces a profound dimension of psychological distress and trauma, a factor that sets them apart. This psychological burden could be relieved by allowing refugees a recovery period upon their arrival in the destination country rather than imposing policies that hinder their labor market integration in EU destination countries.

1.3. Lack of data and research gap

Studies on the socio-economic integration of refugees is a relatively recent development in EU labor market research. A significant portion of previous research focused on migrant demographics in its entirety. Other studies relied on proxy data to categorize migrant types (refugee, study, family, and work) based on their country of origin. This was due to the unavailability of information on the individual's main reason for migration. However, this approach is less ideal when addressing the complex issue of refugees' economic integration compared to other migrant groups. Despite a growing body of literature on refugee studies, significant research gaps remain. There is still a limited exploration of how refugees are faring in the EU labor market. As a result, the effective use of refugee human capital remains a long-standing concern, and addressing this issue strategically could help tackle the EU's demographic challenge.

Prior research on refugees in Europe has broadly focused on comparing their economic outcomes to those of other migrants. However, the second topic of this PhD thesis is novel as it explores the labor market outcomes of refugees, work, family, study, and other reason migrants who arrived from the same origin areas and entry cohorts to the same EU destination countries.

Several studies, including Lundborg (2013); Ruiz and Vargas-Silva (2017); Sarvimäki (2017), have analyzed refugee labor market integration within individual countries such as the UK, Sweden, and Norway. However, there remains a lack of research at the EU level on refugee economic integration. While Brell et al. (2020); Fasani et al. (2021) utilized the 2008 and 2014 EU-LFS survey data to compare refugee labor market outcomes with those of natives and other migrants at the EU level, no research has examined refugee labor market trajectories following the 2015 European migration crisis. This gap primarily stems from the unavailability of EU-level data.

To address this research gap, this thesis uses the newly available data from the 2021 EU-LFS survey wave (released in December 2022) alongside the 2014 survey wave. This dataset enables an analysis of the recent evolution of refugee integration in the EU labor market. Additionally, the third topic of this thesis explores a largely underexamined area: the comparative analysis of refugee sub-groups based on their region of origin.

This empirical analysis of this thesis integrates micro and macro-level factors influencing refugee labor market integration. These include gender, age, education, language proficiency of the destination country, locality, parents' education, household composition, economic conditions at arrival, and broader labor market conditions during the survey year. Unlike most prior research, which primarily applied linear regression models, this thesis applies probit regression models to estimate average marginal effects. Further, linear regression models are used for graphical representations, and logit regression models serve as robustness checks. The analysis of employment outcomes incorporates a step-wise probit regression approach to introduce fixed effects and control variables systematically.

This research aims to provide new insights that address existing gaps in the literature, offering valuable evidence for policymakers on the evolving dynamics of refugee integration in the EU labor market. However, it does not analyze the labor market integration of refugees who arrived in the EU countries because of the Ukraine-Russia war, as this research project predates these developments.

1.4. Methodology preview

This doctoral thesis is structured around three broad topics, each aimed at empirically analyzing the economic integration of refugees in the EU labor market.

The first topic examines how refugees fare in the EU labor market compared to natives. In this analysis, natives are the reference category for assessing refugees' economic outcomes.

The second topic compares refugee labor market outcomes with those of other migrant groups, specifically those who migrated for work, study, family, and other reasons. Work migrants are used as the reference category in this comparison.

The third topic compares the differences in labor market outcomes among refugee groups based on their region of origin. Here, refugees from Other Europe serve as the reference category.

To estimate the likelihood of economic outcomes, this study applies probit regression models to calculate average marginal effects and linear regression models for graphical representations. Like [Ruiz and Vargas-Silva \(2017\)](#), who used probit models to analyze employment and unemployment likelihood among refugees and other migrants in the UK labor market, this research applies probit models to study five key labor market outcomes: employment, unemployment, occupational level, and income distribution (lowest and highest categories).

Probit models analyze employment, unemployment, and income distribution likelihood, and ordered probit models examine occupational likelihood. Logit regression models are applied to conduct robustness checks on the probit regression coefficients. Additionally, the empirical analysis incorporates step-wise probit regression modeling to assess employment likelihood. This method systematically introduces fixed effects and control variables into the model where necessary. This approach aligns with [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#), who introduced variables and fixed effects step-wise in their research. However, it diverges in the methodological application, as [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#) applied linear probability models to analyze the 2008 and 2014 EU-LFS survey data. In contrast, this research applies probit models to analyze the 2014 and 2021 EU-LFS survey data.

The definitions of employment, unemployment, occupational level, and income distribution categories are outlined in [Table 1](#) below:

Table 1: Outcome variables of interest

Outcome variable	Definition
Employment	assigned a value of "1" if an individual is currently engaged in employment and "0" otherwise. The International Labor Organization (ILO) defines employment status as individuals in both wage employment and self-employment.
Unemployment	assigned a value of "1" if an individual is currently unemployed and "0" otherwise. This classification applies to individuals who are part of the labor force and actively seeking employment, following the criteria established by the ILO.
Occupation (High-skilled jobs)	assigned a value of "1" if an individual is employed in a high-skilled occupation and "0" otherwise. This includes individuals working as managers, professionals, technicians, and associate professionals, as classified under the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO).
Occupation (Medium-skilled jobs)	assigned a value of "1" if an individual is employed in a medium-skilled occupation and "0" otherwise. This classification includes clerical, service, and sales workers; skilled agricultural, forestry, and fishery workers; craft and trade workers; and machine and plant operators, based on ISCO standards.
Occupation (Low-skilled jobs)	assigned a value of "1" if an individual is engaged in routine elementary jobs and "0" otherwise. This classification follows the criteria set by ISCO
Lowest income decile	assigned a value of "1" if an individual falls within the lowest income decile and "0" otherwise.
Highest income decile	assigned a value of "1" if an individual falls within the highest income decile and "0" otherwise.

1.5. Data and descriptive statistics

This PhD thesis is based on EU-LFS data, a large cross-sectional survey dataset covering all individuals living in private households, including natives and migrants. The dataset includes a specific question on the "main reason for initial migration," which allows for differentiating migrant groups in EU destination countries. For the empirical analysis, data from the 2014 and 2021 survey waves are used, which include a comprehensive set of questions on the socio-economic conditions of individuals living in the EU countries. The analysis is based on the newly structured scientific use files of the EU-LFS 2014 and 2021 datasets. The 2014 dataset does not include information on Germany, Denmark, Ireland, and the Netherlands, as the survey was not conducted in these countries that year. Additionally, due to Brexit in 2020, UK data is unavailable in the 2021 survey, and therefore, the UK is not included in the empirical analysis.

This research focuses on individuals aged between 20 and 64 active in the EU labor market, meaning they were either employed or actively seeking employment during the 2014 and 2021 surveys. Therefore, individuals with missing data on primary activity, individuals engaged in education or training

in the four weeks before the survey, and individuals serving in the armed forces are excluded from the analysis.

Additionally, some EU destination countries have small aggregated refugee sample sizes which could affect the reliability of results. Therefore, to ensure statistical robustness, countries with fewer than 30 refugee observations are excluded from the analysis.³ The final sample consists of 598,973 natives, 7,347 refugees, and 99,477 other migrants. Migrants residing in EU destination countries are classified based on their region of origin as defined by EUROSTAT. Since EUROSTAT does not provide country-level origin data, only broad origin areas are available. The seven origin areas used in this research are Europe, Other Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, North America and Oceania, and Latin America.

Table 2 provides the aggregated sample sizes of the 2014 and 2021 survey years based on the main reason for initial migration of individuals to the EU destination countries.

Table 2: Cohort sizes of migrant groups classified by their main reason for initial migration to EU destination countries

Destination country	Work	Family	Study	Refugee	Other	Total migrant count
AT Austria	2,266	4,245	365	948	294	8,118
BE Belgium	1,741	3,667	314	652	555	6,929
CH Switzerland	1,885	2,410	202	199	523	5,219
CY Cyprus	1,940	1,259	57	108	170	3,534
DE Germany	1,646	4,435	431	1,228	1,177	8,917
DK Denmark	163	375	95	206	166	1,005
EL Greece	1,901	1,165	31	107	168	3,372
ES Spain	4,461	5,020	348	156	955	10,940
FI Finland	291	889	149	136	128	1,593
FR France	1,297	4,386	641	528	368	7,220
HR Croatia	160	690	60	271	61	1,242
IE Ireland	598	1,129	157	37	131	2,052
IT Italy	10,246	9,585	355	133	324	20,643
LU Luxembourg	3,515	2,611	96	128	415	6,765
NL Netherlands	959	3,191	545	1,010	816	6,521
NO Norway	962	1,447	203	606	293	3,511
PT Portugal	446	2,234	106	179	321	3,286
SE Sweden	340	1,525	153	642	207	2,867
SI Slovenia	1,231	1,096	127	73	563	3,090
Total	36,048	51,359	4,435	7,347	7,635	106,824
Percentage	(33.75 %)	(48.08 %)	(4.15 %)	(6.88 %)	(7.15 %)	(100%)

Table 3 presents the aggregated sample sizes of refugees residing in EU destination countries from the 2014 and 2021 survey waves. The data is categorized into five main origin areas: Other Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America.⁴

³Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia, Malta, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia are not included in the analysis because of smaller refugee sample sizes.

⁴Other Europe refers to all European countries not part of the EU-28 in the 2014 survey wave and the EU-27 in the 2021 survey wave, as per the EU-LFS classification. This includes EFTA countries, EU candidate countries, and other European non-EU states.

Table 3: Cohort sizes of refugees based on their origin area

Origin area	Count	Percentage
Other Europe	1,889	29.83%
North Africa and the Middle East	2,226	35.15%
Other Africa	1,085	17.13%
Asia	819	12.93%
Latin America	316	4.99%
Total	6,335	100%

Tables 4, 5 and 6 provide an overview of the descriptive statistics of all individuals who are active in the European labor market between the age groups 20 to 64.⁵

I. Natives, refugees, and other migrants

Table 4 presents descriptive statistics for natives, refugees, and other migrants based on EU-LFS data from the 2014 and 2021 survey waves.⁶

There are **shifts in refugee origin areas** from the 2014 to 2021 survey wave. In the 2014 survey wave, the main origin areas of refugees are Other Europe (28.93 percent), North Africa and the Middle East (23.55 percent), Other Africa (16.01 percent), and Asia (10.69 percent). By the 2021 survey wave, there are notable shifts in refugee origin distribution, i.e., North Africa and the Middle East (38.42 percent), Other Europe (19.91 percent), Asia (13.75 percent), and Other Africa (13.52 percent). These changes indicate a growing share of refugees from North Africa and the Middle East region, while the refugee share from Other Europe region has declined.

The **gender distribution in the EU labor market** among natives remained relatively balanced and stable between the 2014 and 2021 survey waves. Among other migrants, there is a slightly higher representation of women in the EU labor market, with 52.7 percent women in 2014 and 53 percent women in 2021. Among refugees, men are consistently overrepresented, with 56.94 percent men in 2014 and 60.63 percent men in 2021. This suggests that male refugees are more prevalent in the EU labor market than female refugees. While the gender composition of natives and other migrants remained stable, Table 4 highlights substantial shifts in the gender composition among refugees over time.

Between the 2014 and 2021 survey waves, there are notable **changes in the mean age** in the EU labor market. The average age of natives increased from 43.6 to 44.42 years. The average age of refugees decreased from 45.06 to 42.09 years, indicating that recent refugee waves are younger and predominantly male. The average age of other migrants increased from 41.82 to 43.26 years, following a similar trend to natives. These changes reflect demographic shifts among all three groups over time.

⁵In the descriptive tables, the employed rate is the mean percentage of individuals employed and the unemployment rate is the mean percentage of individuals actively seeking employment during the survey years.

⁶Natives are individuals born in the respective EU destination countries. Refugees are individuals who initially migrated to EU destination countries to seek asylum, other migrants are individuals who initially migrated to EU destination countries for reasons other than seeking asylum.

In the **employment and unemployment trends**, employment rates show a mixed trend across groups. While natives' employment increased from 69.19 percent (2014) to 77.55 percent (2021). Other migrants' employment increased from 63.95 percent (2014) to 69.35 percent (2021). Refugee employment declined from 60.71 percent (2014) to 57.46 percent (2021), indicating increasing challenges in labor market integration of refugees. Unemployment rates decreased for all groups: natives from 9.72 percent (2014) to 5.19 percent (2021), refugees from 14.08 percent (2014) to 10.98 percent (2021), and other migrants from 14.16 percent (2014) to 8.39 percent (2021). Despite this decline, refugees consistently experience higher unemployment rates than natives and other migrants.

In the **occupational segmentation**, refugees are underrepresented in high-skilled jobs, only 14.07 percent of refugees hold high-skilled occupations in 2021 compared to 24.22 percent of other migrants and 35.95 percent of natives. This implies there are barriers to occupational mobility for refugees compared to other groups.

Education plays a crucial role in employment outcomes. At the **low education level**, natives reduced from 30.51 percent (2014) to 20.80 percent (2021), refugees increased from 31.92 percent (2014) to 44.19 percent (2021), other migrants reduced from 36.44 percent (2014) to 32.26 percent (2021).

At the **tertiary education level**, natives increased from 28.99 percent (2014) to 34.13 percent (2021), refugees reduced from 30.13 percent (2014) to 23.16 percent (2021), and other migrants increased from 26.44 percent (2014) to 31.04 percent (2021). These trends indicate that while natives and other migrants have improved in educational attainment, refugees, mainly those from recent waves, are more likely to have lower secondary or even lower education levels.

In the **urbanization trends**, refugees are more likely to reside in cities compared to natives and other migrants. This may reflect settlement patterns influenced by access to services, community networks, and labor market opportunities.

Overall, Table 4 highlights major shifts between 2014 and 2021 in refugee demographics. While natives and other migrants experience improvements in employment and education levels, refugees face declining employment rates and lower educational attainment, indicating potential barriers to economic integration.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics: Natives, refugees, and other migrants

	Natives		Refugees		Other migrants	
	2014	2021	2014	2021	2014	2021
Total Observations	277,342	321,631	1,792	5,555	40,890	58,587
Male (%)	50.05	50.43	56.94	60.63	47.30	47.00
Female (%)	49.95	49.57	43.06	39.37	52.70	53.00
Mean age	43.60	44.42	45.06	42.09	41.82	43.26
Employed mean rate (%)	69.19	77.55	60.71	57.46	63.95	69.35
Occupation level:						
Missing (%)	82.52	23.29	82.66	42.99	79.65	31.15
High-skill (%)	4.27	35.95	2.18	14.07	3.27	24.22
Medium-skill (%)	10.15	35.80	9.80	31.63	11.36	32.71
Elementary (%)	3.06	4.96	5.36	11.31	5.73	11.92
Lowest income decile (%)	2.71	-	2.78	-	6.09	-
Highest income decile (%)	3.77	-	1.22	-	2.14	-
Unemployed mean rate (%)	9.72	5.19	14.08	10.98	14.16	8.39
Education :						
Missing (%)	0.18	0.10	0.76	0.68	0.37	0.50
Low (%)	30.51	20.80	31.92	44.19	36.44	32.26
Medium (%)	40.32	44.96	37.19	31.97	36.75	36.20
High (%)	28.99	34.13	30.13	23.16	26.44	31.04
Degree of urbanization:						
Cities (%)	37.26	37.92	51.72	56.77	48.33	52.06
Towns/Suburbs (%)	32.57	36.94	30.42	33.93	32.21	34.98
Rural areas (%)	30.16	25.14	17.86	9.30	19.46	12.95
Region of origin:						
Missing (%)	-	-	5.79	3.76	1.00	0.85
Europe (%)	-	-	9.4	5.17	34.00	33.23
Other Europe (%)	-	-	28.93	19.91	17.11	21.67
N.Africa/M.East (%)	-	-	23.55	38.42	18.00	16.71
Other Africa (%)	-	-	16.01	13.52	7.88	6.10
Asia (%)	-	-	10.69	13.75	7.48	8.41
N.America/Oceania (%)	-	-	0.15	0.14	1.27	1.43
Latin America (%)	-	-	5.46	5.33	13.24	11.59

Note: The table displays the descriptive statistics of the 2014 and 2021 ad-hoc modules of the EU-LFS data. Module weights are applied to conduct the descriptive analysis. The sample consists of individuals aged between 20 and 64 who were not primarily engaged in education in the last four weeks at the time of the survey or in military service. The sample includes migrants residing in the EU destination countries regardless of the duration of their residency. Refugees are individuals who have migrated to one of the EU destination countries with the primary objective of seeking "international protection" or "asylum." "Other migrants" are non-natives who initially migrated to EU destination countries for reasons other than seeking refuge. Based on their level of qualification, the educational attainment of all individuals is divided into three categories: high is having at least a tertiary degree, medium is having an upper secondary qualification, and low is having a lower secondary qualification or even less

II. Migrants' main reason for initial migration

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics of the EU-LFS pooled sample data from the 2014 and 2021 survey waves, categorized by migrants' main reason for initial migration to EU destination countries. Migrants primarily enter EU countries for work, study, family, refugee, and other reasons.⁷ These migrant groups come from seven main regions: Europe, Other Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, North America and Oceania, and Latin America. Some key findings from Table 5 are discussed below:

In the **migration patterns by region**, among the different migrant groups, a large share of European migrants enter EU destination countries for work (40.75 percent), family (29.48 percent), and other reasons (37.34 percent). A large share of North African and Middle Eastern migrants primarily migrate as refugees (35.42 percent) and for study reasons (23.95 percent).

In the **gender distribution by migration reason**, migration patterns vary by gender, i.e., men primarily migrate for work (60.37 percent), study (51.41 percent), and refugee (59.9 percent) reasons.

⁷Family migrants are those who initially entered EU countries to reunite with their families living in EU destination countries. Other reason migrants are those who initially entered EU destination countries for holidays or vacation motives.

Comparatively, women are largely represented in family migration (62.17 percent).

In the **age and living preferences**, study migrants have the lowest average age (39.56 years), while other reason migrants have the highest average age (45.05 years). Most migrants live in cities rather than towns, suburbs, or rural areas. Study migrants (71.14 percent) are the most likely to reside in cities. And most migrants prefer couple households over single-adult and two-adult households.

In the **labor market outcomes**, study migrants (79.76 percent) and work migrants (75.15 percent) have the highest employment rates. Refugees have the lowest employment rate (58.12 percent), indicating potential challenges in the labor market integration of refugees in EU countries. In unemployment, refugees have the highest unemployment rate (11.61 percent) compared to other migrant groups. Regarding occupational characteristics, only 11.67 percent of refugees hold high-skilled jobs (managerial, technical, or associate positions), while 42.73 percent of study migrants occupy high-skilled jobs.

Education and language proficiency are crucial for migrants' successful integration into the destination countries' labor market. In the low education level, 41.71 percent of refugees report having low education, whereas only 6.32 percent of study migrants report having low education. In the high education levels, 75.49 percent of study migrants report having high education, compared to only 24.57 percent of refugees, and 24.47 percent of work migrants report having high education.

In the language proficiency of migrant groups, only a small percentage of refugees report having advanced language skills (39.93 percent), and a high percentage of study migrants report having advanced language skills (74.27 percent). On the contrary, a high percentage of refugees report having basic language skills (20.93 percent), while a low percentage of study migrants report having basic language skills (5.75 percent).

Parent's education can significantly impact migrant characteristics and labor market success. A large share of refugees (41.16 percent), family (47.49 percent), and work (56.77 percent) migrants report having parents with low education. In contrast, 43.77 percent of study migrants report their parents having high education.

Overall, refugees exhibit the poorest employment, unemployment, and occupational outcomes, alongside lower education levels and language proficiency compared to the average overall outcomes of other migrant groups. These challenges suggest that additional support may be needed to enhance refugee integration in the EU labor market.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics: Migrants' main reason for initial migration

	Work	Family	Study	Refugee	Other
Total Observations	36,048	51,359	4,435	7,347	7,635
Male (%)	60.37	37.83	51.41	59.9	49.71
Female (%)	39.63	62.17	48.59	40.1	50.29
Mean age	43.3	42.33	39.56	42.69	45.05
Employed rate (%)	75.15	60.89	79.76	58.12	68.33
Occupation level:					
Missing (%)	45.67	53.26	39.06	51.01	45.02
High-skill (%)	13.14	15.23	42.73	11.67	19.49
Medium-skill (%)	28.17	23.07	15.88	27.22	27.45
Elementary (%)	13.03	8.44	2.33	10.11	8.04

Table 5 continued from previous page

Unemployed rate (%)	11.53	10.35	8.92	11.61	8.86
Education:					
Missing (%)	0.41	0.46	0.14	0.7	0.79
Low (%)	39.73	33.92	6.32	41.71	27.56
Medium (%)	35.39	38.55	18.05	33.02	39.16
High (%)	24.47	27.08	75.49	24.57	32.50
Parents education level:					
Missing (%)	14.42	18.03	14.31	28.31	30.54
Low (%)	56.77	47.49	24.24	41.16	32.42
Medium (%)	15.27	18.16	17.69	14.76	17.43
High (%)	13.55	16.31	43.77	15.77	19.61
Language skills:					
Missing (%)	4.76	7.51	6.11	13.77	17.48
Advanced (%)	51.41	63.38	74.27	39.93	56.96
Intermediate (%)	28.23	17.25	13.87	25.36	15.87
Basic (%)	15.60	11.86	5.75	20.93	9.69
Living in:					
Cities (%)	50.60	48.71	71.14	55.75	49.75
Towns/suburbs (%)	34.08	35.1	21.21	33.22	34.58
Rural areas (%)	15.32	16.19	7.66	11.03	15.67
Household composition:					
Missing (%)	6.67	5.93	4.63	4.57	8.49
Single adult with or without children (%)	21.68	14.41	27.30	29.16	20.39
Couple with or without children (%)	42.22	45.91	47.78	37.90	44.63
Two adults with or without children (%)	29.43	33.75	20.28	28.37	26.50
Origin area:					
Missing (%)	0.47	1.1	1.5	4.17	1.07
Europe (%)	40.75	29.48	22.46	5.36	37.34
Other Europe (%)	17.07	22.8	11.71	21.73	19.13
Latin America (%)	14.36	10.65	13.13	6.02	12.89
North Africa/Middle East (%)	11.9	19.92	23.95	35.42	16.7
Asia (%)	9.26	7.46	11.47	13.13	4.72
Other Africa (%)	5.44	6.83	14.39	14.02	6.64
North America/Oceania (%)	0.74	1.75	1.37	0.14	1.51

Note: The table presents the descriptive statistics of the pooled sample data of the 2014 and 2021 ad-hoc modules of the EU-LFS. Module weights are applied to conduct the descriptive analysis. The sample consists of individuals aged between 20 and 64 who were not primarily engaged in education in the last four weeks during the survey or in military service. Migrants who have been living in the EU destination countries with any period of residency are included. The table provides descriptive statistics of migrants who initially migrated to EU destination countries for work, study, family, refugee, and other reasons. Refugees are individuals who have migrated to one of the EU destination countries with the primary objective of seeking "international protection" or "asylum." All individuals' educational attainment is divided into three categories: high is having at least a tertiary degree, medium is having an upper secondary qualification, and low is having a lower secondary qualification or even less.

III. Refugees from five main origin areas

Table 6 presents the descriptive statistics of the pooled sample data from the 2014 and 2021 survey waves, categorized by the five main origin areas of refugees.⁸ These origin areas include Other Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America. Some key findings from Table 6 are presented below:

In the **gender distribution and age characteristics**, the ratio of male refugees in EU destination countries is higher than female refugees from certain origin areas, i.e., from Asia 68 percent are men, from North Africa and the Middle East 65 percent are men, and from Other Europe 54.6 percent are men. However, for Latin America, the gender balance slightly favors female refugees, who make up 52 percent of the refugee population in EU destination countries.

In age distribution, refugees from Other Europe have the highest mean age, 45.94, while refugees from Other Africa have the lowest mean age, 40.63.

In the **living preferences and household composition**, refugees predominantly choose to live in cities rather than in towns, suburbs, or rural areas. Among all refugee groups, 64 percent of refugees from Other Africa report living in cities, the highest among all groups. While urban living is common among all refugee groups in EU destination countries, household composition varies substantially. Refugees from Other Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, and Asia are more likely to live in couple households. Refugees from Other Africa are more likely to live in single-adult households. Refugees from Latin America report a higher tendency to live in two-adult households.

Labor market characteristics are critical in shaping the economic integration of refugees in EU destination countries. Employment and unemployment rates vary substantially across refugee groups. The highest employment rate is among Latin American refugees (70.94 percent). The lowest employment rate is among North African and Middle Eastern refugees (48.64 percent). The highest unemployment rate is among Other African refugees (14.62 percent). The lowest unemployment rate is among Other European refugees (8.71 percent).

In the **occupational characteristics**, although refugees generally report lower representation in high-skilled jobs, notable variations exist. 16.06 percent of Latin American refugees hold high-skilled jobs (managerial, technical, or associate roles), the highest percentage among all refugee groups. In contrast, 15.56 percent of Other African refugees are concentrated in elementary occupations, the highest among all refugee groups.

Education and language skills play a crucial role in successful integration in the EU labor market. Asian refugees have the highest ratio of low education (58.44 percent). Latin American refugees have the lowest ratio of low education (17.94 percent). On the contrary, 46.3 percent of Latin American refugees report having at least a tertiary education, the highest ratio among all refugee groups.

Similarly, notable differences exist in language proficiency. Latin American refugees (84.05 percent) report the highest percentage of having advanced language proficiency, while Asian refugees (23.18 percent) report the lowest percentage of having advanced language proficiency. On the contrary, Asian refugees (28.18 percent) and North African and Middle Eastern refugees (27.05 percent) report the highest percentage of having only basic language skills.

Parent's education can play a key role in shaping refugee labor market outcomes. A high ratio of Latin American refugees (34.99 percent) report parents having at least a tertiary education, while a

⁸Europe, North America and Oceania are excluded from the analysis to allow for a comparative assessment of refugees arriving in EU destination countries from the five main refugee origin areas.

high ratio of refugees from Other Africa (50.07 percent) report lower parental education levels.

In conclusion, although refugees seek asylum in EU destination countries for a common reason, i.e., fear of war and persecution in their home countries, they exhibit unique characteristics based on their origin areas. Key differences exist in employment rates, educational attainment, language proficiency, living conditions, and family background. Understanding which socio-demographic factors contribute to improving refugee labor market outcomes is essential for designing targeted policies that support the specific refugee groups facing the most significant challenges. Addressing these disparities can enhance economic integration efforts and ensure more equitable opportunities for all refugee groups in EU destination countries.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics: Refugees from five main origin areas

	O.Europe	N.Africa/M.East	O.Africa	Asia	L.America
Total Observations	1,889	2,226	1,085	819	316
Male (%)	54.60	65.29	55.68	67.90	47.84
Female (%)	45.40	34.71	44.32	32.10	52.16
Mean age	45.94	41.44	40.63	41.22	41.1
Employed rate (%)	61.65	48.64	59.23	61.47	70.94
Occupation level:					
Missing (%)	50.77	56.56	47.60	44.81	41.91
High-skill (%)	12.44	10.76	8.50	10.85	16.06
Medium-skill (%)	26.87	25.38	28.34	29.96	30.92
Elementary (%)	9.92	7.30	15.56	14.38	11.11
Unemployed rate (%)	8.71	13.8	14.62	9.32	13.55
Education:					
Missing (%)	0.31	0.65	0.89	0.88	1.65
Low (%)	33.28	45.49	49.35	58.44	17.94
Medium (%)	43.30	28.53	32.41	25.23	34.12
High (%)	23.12	25.33	17.35	15.45	46.30
Parents education:					
Missing (%)	24.10	35.71	24.33	33.15	7.20
Low (%)	44.47	38.12	50.07	47.69	35.27
Medium (%)	19.15	11.18	10.92	9.24	22.53
High (%)	12.28	14.99	14.68	9.92	34.99
Language skills:					
Missing (%)	13.34	19.79	5.08	16.06	0.59
Advanced (%)	47.34	29.04	43.80	23.18	84.05
Intermediate (%)	24.44	24.12	28.14	32.57	11.05
Basic (%)	14.88	27.05	22.99	28.18	4.31
Living in:					
Cities (%)	47.91	57.71	64.47	60.89	56.65
Towns/suburbs (%)	37.58	32.34	28.26	31.58	30.74
Rural areas (%)	14.51	9.95	7.27	7.53	12.61

Table 6 continued from previous page

Household composition:					
Missing (%)	4.60	0.61	3.02	4.66	3.45
Single adult with or without children (%)	17.81	30.92	45.89	27.86	17.46
Couple with or without children (%)	40.36	42.25	32.20	38.29	28.47
Two adults with or without children (%)	37.22	26.22	18.89	29.19	50.62

Note: The table provides the descriptive statistics of refugees from five main origin areas for the pooled sample data of EU-LFS survey waves of the 2014 and 2021 ad-hoc modules. Module weights are applied to analyze the descriptive statistics. The sample consists of individuals between the age groups 20 and 64 whose main activity is not education in the last four weeks during the survey or military service. Refugees who have been living in the EU destination countries with any period of residency are included. Refugees who migrated to EU destination countries to seek "international protection" or "asylum" from five main origin areas, i.e., Other Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America, are analyzed. Education level is divided into three categories: high is having at least a tertiary degree, medium is having an upper secondary qualification, and low is having a lower secondary qualification or even less.

Chapter 2

Do refugees differ in their labor market outcomes compared to natives?

While EU countries have been continuously making efforts towards the effective integration of refugees, it is important to assess whether the gaps still persist between refugees and natives. If such gaps remain, to what extent do they differ between the two groups? Therefore, this chapter examines the labor market outcomes of refugees compared to natives. Studies by [Brell et al. \(2020\)](#); [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#) analyzed the labor market outcomes of refugees of the 2008 and 2014 EU Labor Force Survey waves. Their findings highlighted substantial labor market differences between refugees and natives in EU destination countries. Building on their research, this chapter utilizes data from the 2014 and 2021 survey waves of the EU-LFS to provide an updated assessment of the labor market situation of refugees relative to natives, thereby, this analysis presents a novel contribution to the existing literature.

The probit regression model used to analyze the labor market outcomes between refugees and natives is

$$y_{is} = \beta m.type_{is} + \gamma(D.Country * S.Year)_i + \phi X_{is} + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

" y_{is} " represents the dichotomous outcome of interest of an individual " i " who was interviewed in the survey year " s ." " $m.type$ " is the migrant type that distinguishes if an individual is either a refugee or other migrant, and native is the reference category.⁹ " $D.Country$ " and " $S.Year$ " are the destination country and survey year fixed effects that capture any economic and non-economic conditions in the EU destination countries during the survey year. " X_{is} " is a vector of an individual's socio-demographic characteristics, i.e., gender, age, education, urbanization degree, household composition, and parents' education. " ϵ_i " captures the heteroskedastic robust standard error.

2.1. Employment likelihood of refugees compared to natives

Table 7 presents the coefficients estimated from the probit regression model of equation (1), which analyzes the likelihood of employment while incorporating various controls and fixed effects through a step-wise approach. The results reveal significant employment gaps between refugees and natives across all specifications.

In column (1), when conditioning solely on destination country and survey year effects, refugees who migrated to EU destination countries to seek asylum are 25.3 percentage points less likely to be employed than natives. After accounting for gender and age in column (2), this baseline gap widens to -28.7 percentage points, and when education is included in column (3), it narrows to -22.6 percentage points. The reduction of the employment gap to -22.6 percentage points indicates that **while refugees face a notable initial employment disadvantage, they have relatively favorable characteristics that positively correlate with employment likelihood**, particularly when compared to other migrants.

A study by [Kone et al. \(2019\)](#) on the UK labor market analyzed employment outcomes by controlling for individual's location within London versus the rest of the UK. Their findings revealed that the employment gap between refugees and UK-born individuals is smaller in London than in other

⁹Other migrants are individuals who migrated to an EU destination country for any other reason than seeking refuge.

regions, although the overall gap remains modest. Similarly, column (4) examines the role of urbanization degree in employment outcomes.¹⁰ After controlling for urbanization degree in column (4), the refugee-native employment gap decreases to -22 percentage points. The positive impact of urbanization is more pronounced for refugees than for other migrants, suggesting that access to urban labor markets, i.e. **access to employment opportunities in cities, is particularly advantageous for refugees in EU destination countries.**

Family characteristics also play a pivotal role in an individual’s employment outcomes. Therefore, columns (5) and (6) analyze the effects of household composition and parents’ educational backgrounds of individuals living in EU destination countries. A study conducted by [Cheung and Phillimore \(2014\)](#) on refugees in the UK labor market found that living with a partner significantly increased the odds of permanent employment among refugees. Following a similar approach, when household composition is induced in column (5), the employment gap for refugees marginally increases to -22.2 percentage points, with no effect on other migrants. This slight increase suggests that refugees in single-adult households may lack emotional and social support compared to those living in couple or two-adult households. **Targeted support, such as childcare assistance and specialized integration programs for single refugee households, could mitigate the employment challenges in refugees to a certain extent.**

Parents’ education is another key factor that could influence an individual’s employment outcome. Although this area remains understudied in refugee labor market integration, it plays a crucial role in shaping the labor market outcomes in developed countries, given the cultural and complex network barriers refugees face in EU destination countries. Including parents’ education in column (6) reduces the refugee-native employment gap to -19.2 percentage points, and the other migrant-native gap closes slightly and reaches -6.4 percentage points. This indicates that **higher parental education significantly enhances the likelihood of refugees’ employment in EU destination countries.** Refugees from educated families may better navigate employment challenges and adapt to labor market demands in EU countries.

Discussion and policy implications

Policies targeting refugees with disadvantaged educational family backgrounds and refugees with low education could help bridge the employment gaps. Initiatives such as labor market integration programs, enhanced educational opportunities, qualification recognition programs, mentorship programs, and anti-discrimination measures could significantly improve refugee employment outcomes, particularly for youth and adults from low-educational backgrounds.

Table 7: Employment likelihood of refugees compared to natives

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Native (omitted group)						
Refugee	-0.253*** (0.009)	-0.287*** (0.008)	-0.226*** (0.008)	-0.220*** (0.008)	-0.222*** (0.009)	-0.192*** (0.010)
Other migrant	-0.085*** (0.002)	-0.104*** (0.002)	-0.079*** (0.002)	-0.076*** (0.002)	-0.076*** (0.002)	-0.064*** (0.003)
Observations	705,797	705,797	704,571	704,571	678,631	630,819
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age		X	X	X	X	X

¹⁰Urbanization degree is if an individual is living in a city, town/suburban area, or rural area in an EU destination country.

Table 7 continued from previous page

Education	X	X	X	X
Urbanization degree		X	X	X
Household composition			X	X
Parents' education				X

Note: The table reports the employment coefficients of refugees compared to natives (omitted category) and other migrants estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. The sample estimates the refugees, natives, and other migrants aged between 20 and 64. All specifications include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. The probit model induces gender, age category, education, urbanization degree, household composition, and parent's education through step-wise regression. In the age category, 20-24 is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in education, low education is the excluded category; in urbanization degree, cities is the excluded category; in household composition, single adult with or without children is the excluded category; in parents' education, low education is the excluded category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. *** indicates the estimates are statistically different from natives at a 1% significance level. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

2.2. Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to natives

Table 8 presents the coefficients estimated from the probit regression model of equation (1) for the likelihood of unemployment, top and bottom-income deciles of refugees compared to natives (reference group). The results in the table show that across all the specifications, there are significant unemployment and income distribution gaps between refugees and natives.

At baseline results, in column (1), refugees are 10.8 percentage points more likely to be unemployed than natives. This gap closes to 8.3 percentage points after inducing the socio-demographic characteristics into the model. Overall, the gap between natives and refugees is significantly large for unemployment, while this gap is small between natives and other migrants. Though refugees start initially with a significant large unemployment disadvantage in EU destination countries, **refugees are less likely to be unemployed and are better selected for their socio-demographic characteristics compared to other migrants.**

Columns (3) to (6) present the income decile outcomes.¹¹ A longitudinal study conducted by [Brell et al. \(2020\)](#) on the income differences between refugees, other migrants, and natives found that refugees have consistently low earnings compared to natives and other migrants. This refugee income gap prevails even after several years of migration to high-income countries. In the table below, from the baseline results in columns (3) and (5), refugees are 5.5 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile and 7.2 percentage points more likely to be in the bottom-income decile than natives. After controlling for refugee characteristics in columns (4) and (6), refugees are 6 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile and 10.8 percentage points more likely to be in the bottom-income decile.

Discussion and policy implications

While refugee characteristics correlate better with employment and unemployment likelihood, their characteristics are weakly correlated with earnings. This could be because of refugees' limited attachment to the labor market, coupled with the background of violence and trauma that refugees face in their home countries, which could be suppressing factors for better earnings. Addressing refugee income gaps requires a multi-faceted policy approach that goes beyond short-term labor market access. Ensuring that refugees can translate their skills into meaningful employment and overcome structural disadvantages is crucial for long-term economic integration in EU destination countries.

Table 8: Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to natives

¹¹EU-LFS does not provide information on the exact earnings of individuals but only discloses information on individual's income decile. Information on income decile is only available for the 2014 ad-hoc module. And, in the 2014 module, information on the income decile is unavailable for France, Norway, and Sweden.

	Unemployment		Top-income decile		Bottom-income decile	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Native (omitted category)						
Refugee	0.108*** (0.007)	0.083*** (0.007)	-0.055*** (0.015)	-0.060*** (0.018)	0.072*** (0.018)	0.108*** (0.022)
Other migrant	0.043*** (0.002)	0.037*** (0.002)	-0.052*** (0.003)	-0.042*** (0.003)	0.089*** (0.004)	0.080*** (0.004)
Observations	705,797	630,819	138,607	129,644	138,607	129,644
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Individual Controls		X		X		X

Note: The table reports the unemployment and income decile coefficients of refugees compared to natives (omitted category) and other migrants estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. The sample includes refugees, natives, and other migrants aged between 20 and 64. The baseline estimations include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. Individual controls include gender, age category, education, urbanization degree, household composition, and parents' education. In the age category, 20-24 is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in education, low education is the excluded category; in urbanization degree, cities are excluded category; in household composition, single adult with or without children is the excluded category; in parents' education, low education is the excluded category. Income decile likelihood is only analyzed for the 2014 survey wave, as the information on the 2021 survey wave is unavailable. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. *** indicates the estimates are statistically different from natives at a 1% significance level. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

2.3. Occupation likelihood of refugees compared to natives

The coefficients in table 9 show the occupational likelihood of refugees compared to natives estimated through equation (1). The EU Labor Force Survey covers various occupational categories, which can be classified into 1. High-skilled jobs, 2. Medium-skilled jobs, and 3. Elementary jobs.¹²

Columns (1) and (2) report the likelihood of refugees and other migrants employed in high-skilled jobs. The baseline results in column (1) indicate that refugees are 24.2 percentage points less likely than natives to hold high-skilled positions. However, after accounting for individual characteristics in column (2), this gap narrows to -16.9 percentage points. In contrast, column (1) shows that other migrants are 14.7 percentage points less likely than natives to be in high-skilled jobs. When individual characteristics are included in column (2), this gap reduces to -12.3 percentage points for other migrants. These findings suggest that refugees have characteristics more associated with high-skilled employment than other migrants. Nevertheless, the significant unexplained initial gap in high-skilled occupations places them at a disadvantage in the EU labor market.

Columns (3) and (4) examine the likelihood of refugees and other migrants employed in medium-skilled jobs without and with individual controls. Compared to natives, refugees are 7.9 percentage points more likely to occupy medium-skilled positions, while other migrants are 6.9 percentage points more likely to do so. However, once individual characteristics are accounted for in column (4), the positive effect weakens, with the likelihood decreasing to 6.1 percentage points for refugees and 5.2 percentage points for other migrants.

Columns (5) and (6) analyze the likelihood of refugees and other migrants being employed in elementary jobs relative to natives. Refugees are 16.3 percentage points more likely to take up elementary occupations in EU countries than natives, whereas other migrants are 7.8 percentage points more likely to do so. After controlling for socio-demographic characteristics, the likelihood decreases to 10.8 percentage points for refugees and 7.1 percentage points for other migrants. The higher likelihood of refugees being in elementary jobs, compared to other migrants, reflects the substantial initial disadvantage they face in the EU labor market.

¹²High-skilled jobs = belonging to one of the three major ISCO-08 groups: Group 1: managers, Group 2: professionals, Group 3: technicians and associate professionals; Medium-skilled jobs = belonging to one of the five major ISCO-08 groups: Group 4: clerical support workers, Group 5: service and sales workers, Group 6: skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers, Group 7: craft and related trade workers, Group 8: plant and machine operators, and assemblers; Elementary jobs = belonging to the last ISCO-08 group: Group 9: elementary occupations.

Discussion and policy implications

Refugees face systematic disadvantages in the EU labor market, with lower access to high-skilled jobs and a higher likelihood of working in elementary occupations compared to natives and other migrants. Despite possessing stronger socio-demographic characteristics that should theoretically improve their occupational outcomes, they continue to face an unexplained labor market gap. These findings align with [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#), who identified persistent occupational disadvantages for refugees in EU countries. Targeted policy measures, such as skills recognition programs, employer incentives for refugee hiring, and expanded access to vocational training could help bridge these gaps and improve refugee employment outcomes in high-skilled occupations.

Table 9: Occupational likelihood of refugees compared to natives

	High-skill		Medium-skill		Elementary-level	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Native (omitted category)						
Refugee	-0.242*** (0.007)	-0.169*** (0.010)	0.079*** (0.001)	0.061*** (0.001)	0.163*** (0.008)	0.108*** (0.008)
Other migrant	-0.147*** (0.003)	-0.123*** (0.003)	0.069*** (0.001)	0.052*** (0.001)	0.078*** (0.002)	0.071*** (0.002)
Observations	346,444	308,955	346,444	308,955	346,444	308,955
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Individual Controls		X		X		X

Note: The table reports the coefficients of the refugees compared to natives (omitted category) and other migrants residing in the EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of the ordered probit regression model. The dependent variable 'occupation level' with high, medium, and low-skilled occupations are analyzed. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. The sample estimates the refugees, natives, and other migrants aged between 20 and 64. The baseline estimations include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. Individual controls include gender, age category, education, urbanization degree, household composition, and parents' education. In the age category, 20-24 is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in education, low education is the excluded category; in urbanization degree, cities are the excluded category; in household composition, single adult with or without children is the excluded category; in parents' education, low education is the excluded category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. *** indicates the estimates are statistically different from natives at a 1% significance level. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

2.4. Heterogeneities between refugees and natives based on gender, education, and locality

Table 10 presents the coefficients estimated through equation (1) separately for men and women in Panel A, for non-tertiary and tertiary education in Panel B, and for not living and living in cities in Panel C.

Gender differences in labor market outcomes of refugees compared to natives

In Panel A, the employment gap between refugee-native women is -20.5 percentage points, and between refugee-native men is -17.2 percentage points. The unemployment gap between refugee-native women is 6.4 percentage points, which is comparatively less than the gap between refugee-native men, 9.4 percentage points.

At the occupation level, while the high-skill occupation gap between refugee-native women is -15.5 percentage points, the gap between refugee-native men is almost the same, -14.4 percentage points. The low-skilled occupation gap between refugee-native women is 15.6 percentage points, which is substantially greater than the gap between refugee-native men, 9.1 percentage points.

In the top-income decile, refugee women are not significantly different from native women, but the gap between refugee-native men is quite large -11.4 percentage points. Among those in the bottom-income decile, the gap between refugee-native women is 14.3 percentage points, which is substantially greater than the gap between refugee-native men, 8.3 percentage points.

Discussion and policy implications

Refugee women face a larger employment and occupational gap than refugee men when compared to their native peers. **Among employed refugee women, substantial gaps are particularly found in low-skilled jobs and the bottom-income decile.** In contrast, the gender gap between other migrants and natives is relatively small across employment, unemployment, occupation, and income distribution. However, refugee women perform better in the top-income decile, showing no significant difference from native women—an outcome not observed for other migrant women. Targeted policies promoting gender-sensitive labor market integration, such as skills training, childcare support, and mentorship programs, could help address these differences and improve labor market outcomes for refugee women.

Education differences in labor market outcomes of refugees compared to natives

The refugee-native employment gap with non-tertiary education is -21.1 percentage points, and the gap with tertiary education is -23.5 percentage points. The refugee-native unemployment gap with non-tertiary education is 7.4 percentage points, and the gap with tertiary education is 12.5 percentage points.

At the occupation level, the refugee-native high-skilled occupation gap with non-tertiary education is -10.6 percentage points, and with tertiary education is -31.3 percentage points. The refugee-native low-skilled occupation gap with non-tertiary education is 17.3 percentage points, and with tertiary education is 9.2 percentage points.

In the top-income decile, the refugee-native gap with non-tertiary education is -4 percentage points, however, there is no statistical difference in the refugee-native gap among those having tertiary education. Among those in the bottom-income decile, the refugee-native gap with non-tertiary education is 12.4 percentage points, and with tertiary education is 10.2 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level).

Discussion and policy implications

Overall, the labor market gap for refugees relative to natives is larger for those with tertiary education than for those with non-tertiary education in employment, unemployment, and high-skilled occupation outcomes. However, the refugee-native gap with tertiary education does not statistically differ in the top-income decile, and those in the bottom-income decile are also not too statistically different (significant at a 10% confidence level) from natives. The insignificant income gap between refugee-native is because refugees before the 2014 wave were predominantly from Other European region where the qualification recognition could have been easier; however, the significant large gaps in employment, unemployment, and occupation outcomes could be because the recent refugee waves are predominantly from outside Europe i.e. from African and Middle Eastern regions who are culturally distinct from European region coupled with challenges in qualification recognition.

The recognition of refugee qualifications and education is a recurring topic in refugee studies, and **refugees often struggle with qualification recognition that they bring from their home countries** to EU destination countries (specifically those from outside the European region). On the other hand, the comparative labor market gaps between other migrants and natives are lower in employment, unemployment, and occupation outcomes compared to refugees with similar characteristics. However, similar to refugees, the labor market gap between tertiary-educated other migrant-native is large compared to non-tertiary-educated other migrant-native. A study conducted by [Frattini and Solmone \(2022a\)](#) underscores the challenges of migrants on qualification recognition in EU destination countries. They find that migrants with tertiary education from their home countries cannot get

their qualifications recognized appropriately in EU countries. This mismatch of qualifications leads to labor market difficulties among migrants compared to their native peers with similar educational backgrounds.

Therefore, the lack of qualification recognition among migrants, specifically refugees, leads to underemployment and low-skilled jobs. This qualification and skill recognition barrier exists for both migrants and refugees of those from non-European countries. Although the EU has been continuously making efforts to recognize the qualifications and skills that refugees and other migrants bring from their home countries, **the process is often uneven and slow**. Additionally, refugees, compared to other migrants, are usually penalized in the labor market because of not having proficient host country language skills, discrimination, and improper access to professional networks, along with the initial challenges they face in EU destination countries.

Therefore, **stronger EU policies that foster qualification recognition** along with **mentorship programs to access jobs that match the tertiary education of refugees** and **targeted language training programs** to access high-skilled sectors would encourage refugees with tertiary education in their labor market outcomes, rather than wasting their education and skills that they bring from their home countries.

Locality differences in labor market outcomes of refugees compared to natives

The refugee-native employment gap is smaller for those living in cities (-17.7 percentage points) than those not living in cities (-19.8 percentage points). Likewise, the refugee-native unemployment gap is smaller for those living in cities (6.8 percentage points) than for those not living in cities (10 percentage points).

However, the refugee-native gap in high-skilled occupations is larger for those living in cities (-17.3 percentage points) than those not living in cities (-12.4 percentage points). Similarly, the refugee-native gap in low-skilled occupation is larger for those living in cities (12.2 percentage points) than for those not living in cities (10.2 percentage points).

Among the earnings distribution, the refugee-native gap in the top-income decile is -8 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) for those living in cities, however, for those not living in cities, the gap is -4.4 percentage points. The refugee-native bottom-income decile gap is 15.3 percentage points for those living in cities, however, for those not living in cities, the gap is 6.7 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level).

On the other hand, other migrants have better employment, unemployment, and occupation outcomes than their refugee peers who live and do not live in cities. Previous studies confirm that **refugees living in cities have better employment and unemployment outcomes** compared to those not living in cities. The results in the table align with the literature.

Discussion and policy implications

Cities, compared to other areas, generally have easy access to language training, networks, and job opportunities and, therefore, better employment opportunities. However, the large gaps in high-skilled jobs in cities often could occur because of the high competition in urban areas where refugees could face challenges in acquiring high-skilled jobs, leading to refugee over-representation in low-skilled jobs compared to non-urban settings. Overall, refugees face difficulties in employment, unemployment, and occupation outcomes compared to other migrants. The differences arise because of the main motive of initial migration of individuals coupled with refugee challenges in accessing networks because of initial dispersal policies implemented by many EU destination countries, as well as

other barriers refugees face, such as skills and qualifications recognition.

Table 10: Heterogeneities between refugees and natives based on gender, education, and locality

	Employment		Unemployment		High-skilled job		Low-skilled job		Top-income decile		Bottom-income decile	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Panel A - Gender differences												
Gender:	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women
Native (omitted category)												
Refugee	-0.172*** (0.013)	-0.205*** (0.014)	0.094*** (0.010)	0.064*** (0.010)	-0.144*** (0.016)	-0.155*** (0.022)	0.091*** (0.012)	0.156*** (0.019)	-0.114*** (0.011)	-0.005 (0.030)	0.083*** (0.025)	0.143*** (0.038)
Other migrant	-0.041*** (0.004)	-0.085*** (0.004)	0.043*** (0.003)	0.031*** (0.002)	-0.094*** (0.004)	-0.109*** (0.005)	0.068*** (0.004)	0.116*** (0.004)	-0.064*** (0.004)	-0.020*** (0.004)	0.042*** (0.004)	0.124*** (0.007)
Observations	307,214	323,605	307,214	323,605	159,084	149,865	159,079	149,865	66,027	63,617	66,027	63,617
Panel B - Education differences												
Tertiary Education:	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Native (omitted category)												
Refugee	-0.211*** (0.011)	-0.235*** (0.019)	0.074*** (0.008)	0.125*** (0.015)	-0.106*** (0.013)	-0.313*** (0.023)	0.173*** (0.015)	0.092*** (0.017)	-0.040*** (0.005)	-0.103 (0.056)	0.124*** (0.026)	0.102* (0.043)
Other migrant	-0.057*** (0.003)	-0.113*** (0.005)	0.033*** (0.002)	0.051*** (0.003)	-0.094*** (0.004)	-0.139*** (0.006)	0.125*** (0.004)	0.056*** (0.003)	-0.031*** (0.002)	-0.062*** (0.009)	0.091*** (0.005)	0.082*** (0.009)
Observations	431,316	199,503	431,316	199,503	193,193	115,757	193,187	115,757	87,038	42,606	87,038	42,606
Panel C - Regional differences												
Living in cities:	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Native (omitted category)												
Refugee	-0.198*** (0.015)	-0.177*** (0.013)	0.100*** (0.012)	0.068*** (0.009)	-0.124*** (0.019)	-0.173*** (0.018)	0.102*** (0.014)	0.122*** (0.014)	-0.044*** (0.011)	-0.080* (0.036)	0.067* (0.027)	0.153*** (0.033)
Other migrant	-0.073*** (0.003)	-0.053*** (0.004)	0.036*** (0.002)	0.038*** (0.003)	-0.095*** (0.005)	-0.108*** (0.005)	0.088*** (0.004)	0.089*** (0.004)	-0.031*** (0.004)	-0.056*** (0.005)	0.062*** (0.005)	0.102*** (0.007)
Observations	408,114	222,705	408,114	222,705	195,214	113,739	195,205	113,739	85,333	44,311	85,333	44,311
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Individual Controls	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Note: The table reports the employment, unemployment, occupation, and income decile coefficients of refugees compared to natives (omitted category) and other migrants residing in EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. Panel A reports the gender differences, Panel B reports the tertiary and non-tertiary education differences, and Panel C reports the differences between those not living in cities and living in cities. The sample estimates the refugees, natives, and other migrants aged between 20 and 64. All specifications include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the destination country and survey year fixed effects, and individual controls include gender, age category, education, urbanization degree, household composition, and parents' education. In the age category, 20-24 is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in education, low education is the excluded category; in urbanization degree, cities are the excluded category; in household composition, single adult with or without children is the excluded category; in parents education, low education is the excluded category. The information on income decile is only available for the 2014 survey wave. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. *** and ** and * indicate the estimates are statistically different from natives at a 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

2.5. Visual representations of employment and language proficiency outcomes of migrant groups

Figure 1 highlights the differences in the employment rates between the 2021 and 2014 survey waves of individuals residing in EU destination countries for less than 10 years, between 11 and 19 years, and more than 20 years. Each data point corresponds to an EU destination country.

The findings of the employment rates of the 2014 survey wave in Figure 1 align with the findings of [Brell et al. \(2020\)](#). Refugees residing in EU destination countries for the last 10 years show significantly low employment rates compared to other migrant peers. However, Switzerland stands as an expectation, seeming to have favorable employment rates for newly arrived refugees in the 2014 survey wave. A similar analysis applied to the 2021 survey wave shows that while refugees' employment rates are significantly low compared to other migrants, Italy and Spain stand as exceptions, with favorable employment rates for newly arrived refugees. These favorable conditions could be related to effective integration policies and immediate access to labor markets for refugees in these countries.

On the contrary, employment rates for refugees who migrated to EU destination countries 11 to 19 years ago closely resemble those of other migrants for the 2014 and 2021 survey waves. The disparities in employment rates substantially decline for refugees who migrated to EU destination countries before 20 years.

Overall, compared to the 2014 wave, the 2021 survey wave has smaller gaps in employment rates, projecting the overall improvement of refugee employment rates across all the migration durations. This suggests improvements in the economic integration of refugees and structural adjustments in EU destination countries over time, such as economic stability, employment, and social inclusion. Nevertheless, from both the 2014 and 2021 survey waves, it could be observed that refugees consistently underperform in employment rates compared to other migrants, which persists even after several years of their migration to EU destination countries.

Figure 1. Refugee versus other migrant employment outcomes

Note: The graphical representations of Figure 1 are derived from the 2014 and 2021 ad-hoc modules of the EU-LFS data. Figure 1 compares the employment rates of refugees to other migrants across EU destination countries of the 2014 and 2021 survey waves. Module weights are used in the analysis. Refugees are individuals who initially arrived in EU destination countries to seek “international protection” or “asylum.” Other migrants are individuals other than non-natives who initially arrived in EU destination countries for reasons other than seeking asylum. Individuals whose main activity is education or training in the last four weeks before the survey was conducted and individuals in military service are excluded and the analysis is limited to individuals aged between 20 and 64. Each data point in the figure corresponds to a European country. The deviation below the 45° line in Figure 1 signifies the extent to which refugees experience lower employment rates than other migrants. These comparisons are disaggregated for the migrants residing in EU destination countries for up to 10 years, between 11 and 19 years, and more than 20 years.

Figure 2 highlights the language proficiency differences between refugees and other migrants in European countries. Language plays a crucial role in shaping migrants’ labor market outcomes, and migrants rationally choose a destination country based on the ease of becoming proficient in the destination country’s language skill (Chiswick and Miller, 2015a). The EU-LFS data provides language proficiency of migrants where respondents self-evaluate their competence in the destination country’s language skills as 1. “beginner or less,” 2. “intermediate,” 3. “advanced,” 4. “mother tongue.”

Figure 2 represents the migrants residing in EU destination countries who have responded either having mother tongue or advanced level language skills of those living in EU destination countries for less than 10 years, between 11 to 19 years, and more than 20 years. Each data point corresponds to an EU destination country. In Figure 2, the language outcomes of the 2014 survey wave align with the findings of Brell et al. (2020). A similar analysis is applied to the 2021 survey wave, and the findings show that refugees exhibit significantly lower language skills than other migrants during their first 10 years of migration in almost all the EU destination countries. The gap closes slightly for refugees who migrated 11 to 19 years ago, and refugees who reported to have migrated more than 20 years ago have language proficiency comparable to other migrants, however, still lag slightly behind compared to their other migrant peers.

Overall, refugees show improved language proficiency outcomes in the 2021 survey wave compared to the 2014 survey wave across all durations of migration periods. Despite the overall progress, refugees still exhibit language proficiency issues, specifically during the first 10 years of their migration to EU countries, suggesting that early refugee integration remains a challenge in EU destination countries, and efforts are still to be made to achieve effective refugee integration.

Figure 2. Refugee versus other migrant language outcomes

Note: The graphical representations of Figure 2 are derived from the 2014 and 2021 ad-hoc modules of the EU-LFS data. Figure 2 illustrates the language proficiency rates of refugees compared to other migrants across European countries for the 2014 and 2021 survey waves. Module weights are used in the analysis. Refugees are individuals who initially arrived in EU destination countries to seek “international protection” or “asylum.” Other migrants are individuals other than non-natives who initially arrived in EU destination countries for reasons other than seeking asylum. Individuals whose main activity is education or training in the last four weeks before the survey was conducted and individuals in military service are excluded and the analysis is limited to individuals aged between 20 and 64. Each data point in the figure corresponds to a European country. The deviation below the 45° line signifies the extent to which refugees have poorer language skills than other migrants. These comparisons are disaggregated for the migrants residing in EU destination countries for up to 10 years, between 11 and 19 years, and more than 20 years.

2.6. Conditional and unconditional employment gaps of migrant groups

Figure 3 explores the gaps in employment rates between refugees and other migrants unconditionally (naive estimates) and conditionally (based on socio-demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and education). This analysis is conducted on the 2014 and 2021 EU-LFS survey waves. A similar analysis was conducted by [Brell et al. \(2020\)](#) on the 2008 and 2014 EU-LFS survey waves.

Figure 3 illustrates the conditional and unconditional employment outcomes of refugees and other migrants compared to natives (reference category). The aggregated data is the pooled sample of the 2014 and 2021 survey waves of EU-LFS estimated through a linear probability model. The naive series includes the destination country and survey year fixed effects, and the conditional series includes the destination country and survey year fixed effects along with gender, age groups, and education of individuals. From Figure 3, accounting for the socio-demographic factors has a slight effect on the naive estimates, albeit the qualitative representation remains predominantly unaltered. Compared to other migrant characteristics, refugees have characteristics that are positively correlated to employment (as previously observed in Table 7), and therefore, the graph moves slightly upwards after inducing gender, age, and education. In addition, refugees, compared to other migrants, have a significant initial employment gap. While there is convergence over time, it takes more than 19 years for the employment gap to close, however, the gap persists even after many years.

Figure 3. Conditional and unconditional employment gaps of migrant groups

Note: The graphical representations of Figure 3 are derived from the 2014 and 2021 ad-hoc modules of the EU-LFS. Module weights are used in the analysis. Refugees are individuals who responded to seeking "international protection" or "asylum" as their main reason for initial migration. Other migrants are individuals other than non-natives residing in EU destination countries who migrated for reasons other than seeking asylum. The sample includes individuals aged between 20 and 64, excluding those primarily engaged in education or training activities in the last four weeks before the survey and individuals in military service. The graphical representation illustrates employment gaps among refugees and other migrants relative to natives as a function of years since migration. The employment gaps are derived using a linear probability model. The naive estimates include survey year and destination country fixed effects, and the conditional series include gender, age groups, and education.

Chapter 3

How do refugees fare in the EU labor market among migrant groups?

The 2015 refugee crisis, characterized by a sudden surge in asylum applications in developed countries, raised intense debates over how to manage and integrate refugees effectively. A key issue in this discourse centered on the ability of Western countries to absorb and integrate refugees into their labor markets. Fernández-Huertas Moraga and Rapoport (2015) highlighted inefficiencies in the European Union's asylum policies, advocating for Tradable Refugee-Admission Quotas and a matching mechanism as tools to achieve equitable refugee distribution and improved integration.¹³ Similarly, Dustmann et al. (2017) emphasized that while the EU has made efforts to harmonize refugee integration policies, significant differences exist in the implementation of asylum policies across member states. Hatton (2017) stressed the importance of balancing policies that regulate refugee inflows with those designed to ensure effective integration through coordinated policies at the EU level. Despite its importance, the integration of refugees into EU labor markets remains underexplored compared to the extensive research on broader migration topics, including the migrant economic and labor market effects in developed countries (Borjas, 1999; Kerr and Kerr, 2011). The Syrian refugee crisis further highlighted this gap, as the latest evolution of migrants at the EU-level data necessary to analyze migrant integration, particularly by their initial migration motives, was unavailable until December 2022. While migrants arrive in EU countries for various reasons, such as work, family, study, seeking asylum, and other reasons (such as holiday or vacation motives), an important question concerns the labor market outcomes of refugees compared to other migrant groups.

Fasani et al. (2022) studied the labor market outcomes of refugees on the 2008 and 2014 waves of the EU Labor Force Survey data, comparing refugees to economic and non-economic migrants. Building on this work, this chapter uses the 2014 and 2021 EU-LFS waves to analyze the labor market outcomes of refugees compared to migrants who arrived for work, family, study, and other reasons. This approach offers a novel contribution by providing a more recent understanding of refugee integration relative to other individual migrant groups in the EU labor market.

The probit regression model used to analyze the labor market outcomes of migrant groups is

$$y_{idseo} = \beta \text{migreas}_{idseo} * \text{recession} + \gamma(D.\text{Country} * S.\text{Year})_i + \phi X_{idseo} + \rho(E.\text{Cohort})_i + \delta(O.\text{Area})_i + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

y_{idseo} represents the dichotomous outcome of interest of an individual "i" who resides in an EU destination country "d" and was interviewed in the survey year "s" from the entry cohort "e" and of the origin area "o." "migreas" is the individual's main reason for initial migration to an EU destination country, i.e., migrated for work, study, family, refugee, or other reasons. "recession" is an indicator variable that specifies if an EU destination country was affected by an economic downturn during the entry cohort of an individual.¹⁴ "D.Country" and "S.Year" fixed effects capture any business cycle fluctuations common to all the five migrant groups in the respective destination countries during the

¹³Tradable Refugee-Admission Quota is a system that allows countries better equipped and more willing to accept refugees to trade admission quotas. A matching mechanism is aligning refugees' preferences with the needs and capacities of EU countries.

¹⁴Recession indicator of the EU destination countries is taken from the World Bank data. Recession=1 if an EU destination country has a negative GDP per capita growth rate during the entry cohort of an individual, and recession=0 if an EU destination country has a positive GDP per capita growth rate during the entry cohort of an individual. In the case of a five-year entry cohort band, if an EU destination country had a negative GDP growth rate for more than 2 years, then the recession indicator is 1, else 0.

survey year. X_{idseo} is a vector of an individual's socio-demographic characteristics, i.e., gender, age, education, and language skills. "E.Cohort" is the entry cohort that captures all unobservable factors common to individuals from the same arrival year to an EU destination country.¹⁵ "O.Area" is the origin area that captures the common characteristics of the migrants arriving from the same origin area. " ϵ_i " captures the heteroskedastic robust standard error. In equation (2), individuals initially migrated for work reasons are considered the reference category.

3.1. Employment likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups

Table 11 presents the coefficients of employment likelihood for family, study, refugee, and other reason migrants compared to work migrants (reference group). The coefficients are derived from a probit regression model based on equation (2), which evaluates employment likelihood using various controls and fixed effects in a step-wise approach. Refugee, family, study, and other reason migrants are defined as individuals who initially migrated to EU countries for non-economic reasons, contrasting with work migrants who moved primarily for economic opportunities. This analysis follows a similar step-wise regression framework to that of [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#), who examined refugee employment outcomes using a linear probability model.

In column (1), controlling for destination country and survey year effects, refugees show a significant employment gap of -23.6 percentage points compared to work migrants. Family migrants exhibit a gap of -16.4 percentage points, while other reason migrants show a -10.7 percentage points employment gap. Although study migrants also migrated for non-economic reasons, their baseline employment outcomes are not significantly different from work migrants. **Refugees, however, exhibit the largest initial employment gap among all the migrant groups.**

When controlling for gender and age in column (2), the refugee employment gap decreases to -22.9 percentage points. Controlling for education in column (3) reduces the gap to -21.7 percentage points, and incorporating language skills in column (4) shrinks the refugee employment gap further to -20.7 percentage points. The overall employment gap by column (4) suggests that despite the large initial gap, **refugees tend to have better education and language-related characteristics for employment likelihood** than other non-economic migrant groups.

In column (5), accounting for migrants' origin areas, the refugee employment gap substantially shrinks to -17.3 percentage points. This indicates that **refugees predominantly come from origin areas weakly associated with EU labor market outcomes**. In column (6), controlling for the entry cohort (years since arrival) slightly increases the gap, suggesting that **refugees are overrepresented in recent cohorts**. The literature on migrants shows that longer residence in destination countries positively correlates with higher employment likelihood, which could mean that the recent refugee cohorts could improve their employment likelihood over time.

Column (7) incorporates two-way fixed effects to capture the unobservable characteristics and account for shared initial shocks affecting migrants from the same region and entry cohort arriving in the same EU destination country. Including these two-way effects reduces the employment gap of all groups. However, among all the non-economic migrant groups, this gap shrinks more for refugees and reaches -16.5 percentage points. This suggests that though refugees are from the same entry cohort, come from the same origin area, and enter the same EU destination countries as other non-economic migrant groups, **seeking asylum protection has pronounced adverse effects on the employment likelihood in European countries.**

¹⁵Entry cohort or year of arrival of an individual is represented by a single-year or a 5-year band.

Finally, the "full sample" column presents the effect of recession on employment likelihood. Previous studies of Åslund and Rooth (2007); Barsbai et al. (2023); Fasani et al. (2022) have highlighted the impact of arriving during economic shocks. The table results below show that migrants entering EU countries during a recession period significantly experience a -2.3 percentage point reduction in employment likelihood compared to those arriving in stable economic periods. Refugees, driven by push factors such as violence and war, are more likely to migrate during recessions, resulting in long-term scarring effects. Consequently, their employment gap is large (-17.9 percentage points) compared to other non-economic migrants. In the "less than 10-year sample" column, migrants who arrived during a recession do not exhibit significantly different outcomes from those who arrived during stable economic periods. However, recently arrived migrants (i.e., those who arrived in the last 10 years) generally face larger employment gaps than the full sample of migrants, with the only exception being study migrants. While the significant long-term scarring effects of the recession on employment outcomes are observed in the migrants from the "full sample," migrants who entered EU countries "within the last ten years" are prone to larger employment gaps compared to the "full sample" of migrants, with the only exception being study migrants.

Discussion and policy implications

Special policy attention is required for migrants, particularly refugees, entering EU countries during periods of economic recession. Despite possessing employment-related characteristics that typically correlate with positive labor market outcomes, refugees from the same origin areas and entry cohorts as other migrants continue to face significant employment gaps. This disparity is often linked to discrimination associated with refugee status.

To address these challenges, **employer incentive schemes could be implemented to encourage hiring refugees.** Such initiatives would reduce employment gaps and enhance refugees' economic integration and motivation in the destination country's labor market.

Table 11: Employment likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Work (omitted group)					
Family	-0.164*** (0.005)	-0.123*** (0.005)	-0.129*** (0.005)	-0.148*** (0.005)	-0.139*** (0.005)
Study	0.016 (0.010)	0.027** (0.010)	-0.039*** (0.011)	-0.068*** (0.012)	-0.052*** (0.012)
Refugee	-0.236*** (0.010)	-0.229*** (0.010)	-0.217*** (0.009)	-0.207*** (0.010)	-0.173*** (0.010)
Other reason	-0.107*** (0.009)	-0.078*** (0.009)	-0.094*** (0.009)	-0.115*** (0.010)	-0.108*** (0.010)
Observations	106,824	106,824	106,064	101,253	99,314
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age		X	X	X	X
Education			X	X	X
Language skills				X	X
Origin area					X

	(6)	(7)	(Full sample)	(<10 years sample)
Work (omitted group)				
Family	-0.150*** (0.005)	-0.147*** (0.005)	-0.141*** (0.005)	-0.221*** (0.009)
Study	-0.059*** (0.012)	-0.056*** (0.012)	-0.049*** (0.012)	-0.047* (0.020)
Refugee	-0.176*** (0.010)	-0.165*** (0.010)	-0.179*** (0.010)	-0.239*** (0.017)
Other reason	-0.113*** (0.010)	-0.112*** (0.009)	-0.107*** (0.010)	-0.157*** (0.018)
Observations	97,090	97,072	91,064	29,171
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age	X	X	X	X
Education	X	X	X	X
Language skills	X	X	X	X
Origin area	X	X	X	X
Entry cohort	X			
Entry cohort*Origin area		X		
Entry cohort*Destination country		X		
Recession effect*Reason for migration			X	X
			-0.023*** (0.005)	0.006 (0.006)

Note: The table reports the employment coefficients of family, study, refugee, and other reason migrants compared to work migrants estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. All migrants aged between 20 and 64 are included in the analysis. All specifications include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. The probit model induces gender, age category, education, language skills, origin area, and entry cohort effects of migrants through step-wise regression. Additionally, two-way fixed effects are captured by inducing interaction dummies for the entry cohort-origin area and entry cohort-destination country, and the recession effects of the EU destination countries are captured. In the age category, 20-24 is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in education, low education is the excluded category; in language, advanced language proficiency is the excluded category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates are statistically different from that of the work migrants at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels of significance. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

3.2. Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups

Table 12 presents the unemployment, top and bottom income decile coefficients estimated from equation (2) for family, study, refugee, and other reason migrants with work migrants serving as the reference group.

Unemployment

Panel A reports the unemployment likelihood coefficients for both the "full sample" and the "less than 10-year sample."

The baseline estimates in column (1) indicate that refugees are 5.4 percentage points more likely to be unemployed than work migrants. However, no significant unemployment effect is observed for the other migrant groups. After controlling for socio-demographic characteristics in column (2), the unemployment likelihood for refugees decreases to 3.2 percentage points. Among other migrant groups, family migrants' unemployment likelihood increases to 2.1 percentage points.

Introducing recession effects in column (3) shows no significant difference in unemployment likelihood between migrants who arrived during a recession and non-recession periods.

In the "less than 10-year sample," the baseline estimates in column (4) reveal that refugees are 7.8 percentage points more likely to be unemployed than work migrants. Family migrants are also 3.2 percentage points more likely to be unemployed. After introducing migrant characteristics in column (5), the unemployment likelihood for refugees decreases to 4 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level). For family migrants, the unemployment likelihood increases to 3.7 percentage points.

Controlling for recession effects in column (6) shows that recession periods do not significantly impact unemployment likelihood among recent migrant groups.

Discussion and Policy implications

Refugees who arrived within the last ten years face larger unemployment gaps than those who have resided in EU countries for more than ten years. Among non-economic migrant groups, both refugees and family migrants show significant unemployment effects, but refugees generally possess stronger socio-demographic characteristics than family migrants. This makes refugees relatively less likely to be unemployed than family migrants in EU countries. Study migrants and other reason migrants do not differ significantly from economic work migrants in unemployment outcomes in EU countries.

The higher likelihood of unemployment for refugees, particularly those who arrived within the last decade, suggests that labor market integration challenges are more pronounced for recent arrivals. Family migrants face considerable unemployment risks, potentially due to factors such as family responsibilities, lower initial human capital, and limited labor market attachment. Study migrants show no significant unemployment disadvantage compared to work migrants, possibly due to higher educational attainment or targeted migration policies. **The insignificance of recession effects suggests that economic cycles do not disproportionately impact migrant unemployment, highlighting the need for structural labor market interventions.**

Income distribution

The coefficients in Panels B and C present the estimates for the highest and lowest income deciles for the "full sample" and "less than 10-year sample" of migrant groups in EU countries.¹⁶

In the UK labor market, [Ruiz and Vargas-Silva \(2018\)](#) investigated the differences in wage earnings between refugees compared to work, study, and family migrants. The study found that refugees have weaker earning profiles compared to all other migrant groups in the UK. Similarly, [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#) analyzed the income disparities between refugees compared to economic and non-economic migrants, reporting that refugees are less likely to be in the high-income decile. The study also highlighted that the earnings gap is more significant between refugees and economic migrants than with non-economic migrants.

Top-income decile

Panel B presents the coefficients for refugee, study, family, and other reason migrants relative to work migrants in the likelihood of being in the top income decile.

Unlike the large initial gaps observed in refugees' employment and unemployment likelihood, the baseline estimates reveal that refugees are not statistically different from work migrants in the likelihood of being in the high-income distribution, both in the "full sample" and the "less than 10-year sample." On the other hand, in the "full sample" estimates, study migrants are 6 percentage points more likely than work migrants to be in the top-income decile. In the "less than 10-year sample," family migrants are 3.9 percentage points, and other reason migrants are 3.1 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence interval) less likely to be in the top-income decile than work migrants.

In the "full sample" estimates, after controlling for individual characteristics and fixed effects, while study migrants are not statistically different from work migrants, the likelihood of refugees being in the top-income decile is -2.5 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level); and other reason migrants are 2.9 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile. However, in the "less than 10-year sample," refugees are not statistically different from work migrants in the likelihood of being in the top-income decile; but family migrants are 3.1 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level), and other reason migrants are 4 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile than work migrants. Study migrants are not statistically

¹⁶EU-LFS do not report income data for the 2021 survey wave. Therefore, the income decile analysis is conducted only on the available data from the 2014 survey wave.

different from work migrants.

Overall, from column (2), it could be observed that refugee characteristics are weakly correlated to being in the top-income decile even after residing for many years (in the full sample) in the EU destination countries. These findings align with [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#), who reported that **refugee characteristics are not strongly correlated with high earnings**. Refugees are generally significantly less likely to be in the top-income decile than economic migrants (work migrants) due to limited attachment to the destination countries' labor market.

Entering Europe during a recession has no significant effect on the likelihood of being in the top-income decile for the migrant groups in both the "full sample" and the "less than 10-year sample."

Bottom-income decile

Panel C presents the coefficients for non-economic migrant groups compared to economic migrants (work migrants) in the likelihood of being in the bottom-income decile.

Refugee, study, and other reason migrants are not statistically different from work migrants in the likelihood of being in the bottom-income decile (both at baseline and after inducing controls and fixed effects). However, family migrants are significantly more likely to be in the bottom-income decile in both the "full sample" and the "less than 10-year sample." The effect of being in the bottom-income decile is more pronounced among family migrants in the "less than 10-year sample" than the "full sample."

In the "full sample" estimates, recession effects are statistically significant, increasing the likelihood of all migrant groups being in the bottom-income decile by 2.3 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) compared to those who arrived when there was no recession. However, among the recent migrant cohorts, the recession effect is not statistically significant.

Discussion and policy implications

The findings reveal that refugees face substantial barriers to reaching the top-income decile, even after prolonged residence in EU destination countries. The earnings gap between refugees and economic migrants (work migrants) suggests limited refugee integration into high-paying jobs, given the weak refugee characteristics coupled with labor market segmentation, skill underutilization, and discrimination.

The increased likelihood of family migrants being in the bottom-income decile indicates potential challenges related to family reunification policies, childcare responsibilities, and limited economic mobility. Recession effects exacerbate the economic vulnerability of all migrant groups, highlighting the importance of macroeconomic stability in ensuring equitable labor market outcomes.

Table 12: Unemployment and income distribution likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups

Panel A - Unemployment						
	Full sample			<10 years sample		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Work (omitted category)						
Family	0.009** (0.003)	0.021*** (0.004)	0.013*** (0.004)	0.032*** (0.006)	0.037*** (0.007)	0.036*** (0.007)
Study	0.002 (0.008)	0.008 (0.008)	0.007 (0.009)	0.009 (0.013)	0.018 (0.015)	0.020 (0.015)
Refugee	0.054*** (0.007)	0.032*** (0.007)	0.036*** (0.008)	0.078*** (0.012)	0.040** (0.013)	0.051*** (0.013)
Other reason	-0.002 (0.006)	0.007 (0.007)	0.006 (0.007)	0.015 (0.012)	0.015 (0.013)	0.016 (0.014)
Observations	106,824	96,130	91,064	31,674	28,890	29,171
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Origin area		X			X	
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X	
Origin area			X			X
Recession effect*Reason for migration			X			X
			0.004 (0.003)			-0.002 (0.004)

Panel B - Top-income decile						
	Full sample			<10 years sample		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Work (omitted category)						
Family	-0.004 (0.005)	-0.008 (0.006)	0.003 (0.005)	-0.039*** (0.009)	-0.031** (0.011)	-0.021* (0.009)
Study	0.061** (0.019)	0.011 (0.011)	0.019 (0.011)	0.007 (0.025)	-0.015 (0.019)	-0.015 (0.015)
Refugee	-0.016 (0.014)	-0.025** (0.009)	-0.011 (0.014)	-0.027 (0.031)	-0.024 (0.024)	0.004 (0.036)
Other reason	-0.013 (0.008)	-0.029*** (0.007)	-0.021*** (0.006)	-0.031** (0.010)	-0.040*** (0.011)	-0.028** (0.010)
Observations	19,056	16,536	18,526	6,921	5,395	6,721
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Origin area		X			X	
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X	
Origin area			X			X
Recession effect*Reason for migration			X			X
			-0.001 (0.005)			0.011 (0.006)

Panel C - Bottom-income decile						
	Full sample			<10 years sample		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Work (omitted category)						
Family	0.022** (0.009)	0.031*** (0.009)	0.012 (0.009)	0.087*** (0.016)	0.071*** (0.016)	0.073*** (0.016)
Study	-0.035 (0.024)	0.019 (0.026)	0.009 (0.027)	-0.034 (0.040)	0.043 (0.048)	0.039 (0.050)
Refugee	0.027 (0.022)	0.043 (0.023)	0.029 (0.022)	0.026 (0.042)	0.040 (0.046)	0.029 (0.042)
Other reason	0.000 (0.018)	0.012 (0.018)	0.008 (0.019)	0.017 (0.029)	0.041 (0.031)	0.037 (0.030)
Observations	19,056	18,332	18,526	6,931	6,682	6,729
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Origin area		X			X	
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X	
Origin area			X			X
Recession effect *Reason for migration			X			X
			0.023** (0.008)			0.009 (0.009)

Note: The table reports the coefficients of migrant groups residing in the EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model of the dependent variable 'unemployment,' 'top-income decile,' and 'bottom-income decile.' Sampling weights are used in the analysis. The sample comprises refugees and other migrants aged between 20 and 64. All specifications include destination country-survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. Controls include gender, age category, education, and language proficiency. In education, lower secondary education is the excluded category; in language, advanced language proficiency is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in the age category, 20-24 years is the excluded category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates are statistically different from work migrants at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels of significance. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

3.3. Occupation likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups

Table 13 presents the occupational likelihood coefficients estimated from equation (2) for individuals who entered EU countries for family, study, refugee, and other reasons, and work migrants as the reference group. Panel A reports estimates for the "full sample", while Panel B focuses on migrants who arrived "within the last ten years."

High-skilled occupation

In the "full sample" estimates, refugees are 5.4 percentage points less likely to be employed in high-skilled jobs. However, after accounting for individual characteristics and fixed effects, this gap narrows to -4 percentage points. Among other migrant groups, study migrants have the strongest positive association with high-skilled employment, surpassing even work migrants (the reference group) at both baseline and after controlling for individual characteristics and fixed effects. Family (4.1 percentage points more likely) and other reason (6.1 percentage points more likely) migrants initially show a high likelihood of high-skilled employment compared to work migrants. However, once individual characteristics and fixed effects are accounted for, the positive effect disappears, making them statistically similar to work migrants.

In the "recent cohort" estimates, refugees are 12.3 percentage points less likely to hold high-skilled jobs. However, after inducing controls and fixed effects, they are no longer statistically different from work migrants. Similar to the "full sample," study migrants in the "recent cohorts" also exhibit a strong positive association with high-skilled employment, even exceeding the reference group. While family and other reason migrants initially do not differ significantly from work migrants in high-skilled employment, once controls and fixed effects are applied, family migrants are found to be 4 percentage points less likely to hold high-skilled jobs, while other reason migrants remain statistically similar to work migrants.

Medium-skilled occupation

In the "full sample," refugees are initially not statistically different from work migrants in securing medium-skilled jobs. However, after accounting for socio-demographic characteristics and fixed effects, they become 5.9 percentage points more likely to be employed in medium-skilled occupations. Among other migrant groups, study migrants are the least likely to hold medium-skilled jobs, both at baseline and after applying controls and fixed effects. Family (0.8 percentage points) and other reason (1.4 percentage points) migrants are initially less likely than work migrants to hold medium-skilled jobs. However, after accounting for individual characteristics and fixed effects, family migrants become statistically similar to work migrants, while other reason migrants become 3.8 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to hold medium-skilled jobs.

In the "recent cohort" estimates, refugee, family, and other reason migrants are not statistically different from work migrants in their likelihood of holding medium-skilled jobs. However, study migrants continue to be the least likely group to work in medium-skilled occupations, both at baseline and after controlling for individual characteristics and fixed effects.

Elementary occupation

In the "full sample" estimates, refugees are 5.4 percentage points more likely than work migrants to hold elementary jobs. However, after introducing individual controls and fixed effects, they are no longer statistically different from work migrants in this occupational category. Among other migrant groups, study migrants are the least likely to take up elementary jobs, both at baseline and after applying controls and fixed effects.

At baseline, family migrants are 3.3 percentage points less likely to work in elementary jobs. However, after adjusting for individual characteristics and fixed effects, they become statistically similar to work migrants. Other reason migrants, on the other hand, are initially 4.7 percentage points less likely than work migrants to work in elementary jobs. After controlling for individual characteristics and fixed effects, they are 2.6 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely than work migrants to work in elementary jobs.

In the "recent cohort" estimates, refugees are initially 12.6 percentage points more likely than work migrants to hold elementary jobs. However, once individual controls and fixed effects are introduced, they are no longer statistically different from work migrants. Study migrants remain the least likely to take up elementary jobs. Family and other reason migrants are initially similar to work migrants in this category; however, after accounting for socio-demographic characteristics and fixed effects, family migrants become 2.3 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to work in elementary jobs, while other reason migrants remain statistically similar to work migrants.

Effects of recession

In the "full sample" estimates, arriving in EU countries during a recession has a notable impact on elementary occupations. Migrants who arrived in the EU countries during a recession are 1.3 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to work in elementary jobs than those who arrived during non-recession periods. Furthermore, while the recession impact remains significant in elementary occupations in the "full sample," this effect is not observed in the "recent cohort" estimates.

Discussion and policy implications

The findings highlight that occupational likelihood, beyond just employment rates, plays a critical role in understanding the types of jobs refugees take up in EU countries. Furthermore, in 2015, over half of asylum seekers came from non-European countries such as Afghanistan, Iraq, and Syria. Table 13 underscores the initial disadvantaged position of refugees in the labor market. Previous studies have shown that refugees are more likely to be employed in low-wage elementary occupations, often due to lower education levels, limited skills transferability, and weaker proficiency in the host country's language. For instance, [Backman et al. \(2021\)](#) found that education is crucial for improving the occupational pathways of refugees in Sweden and advocated

for integrating education into refugee settlement policies to provide direct access to national education systems. A comparative study by [Poutvaara and Wech \(2016\)](#) found that refugee labor market integration is faster in the United States than in Europe. This underscores the **need for European countries to develop more effective welfare programs that grant refugees direct access to education and language training alongside recognizing their existing skills**. Such measures could reduce dependency on welfare benefits and mitigate risks of social exclusion and radicalization.

While Europe has the potential to improve refugee labor market integration, it lags behind the United States due to ineffective policies ([Poutvaara and Wech, 2016](#)). The poor occupational quality among refugees relative to other migrant groups is largely attributed to the integration barriers they face. These challenges not only limit employment opportunities for refugees but also contribute to persistent labor shortages in several EU countries. As evidenced in [Table 13](#), refugees face a greater disadvantage in the labor market compared to other migrant groups. A targeted policy intervention is, therefore, necessary to effectively utilize refugee human capital and address structural barriers that hinder their employment in better-quality jobs.

Table 13: Occupation likelihood of refugees compared to other migrant groups

Panel (A)									
Full sample									
	High-skill			Medium-skill			Elementary-level		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Work (omitted category)									
Family	0.041*** (0.005)	-0.005 (0.007)	0.010 (0.006)	-0.008*** (0.001)	0.012 (0.008)	0.013 (0.008)	-0.033*** (0.004)	0.003 (0.006)	-0.013* (0.006)
Study	0.383*** (0.013)	0.119*** (0.012)	0.127*** (0.013)	-0.205*** (0.010)	-0.098*** (0.015)	-0.098*** (0.015)	-0.179*** (0.004)	-0.089*** (0.011)	-0.097*** (0.011)
Refugee	-0.054*** (0.009)	-0.040*** (0.012)	-0.037** (0.012)	0.001 (0.001)	0.059*** (0.015)	0.057*** (0.015)	0.054*** (0.009)	0.010 (0.011)	0.015 (0.012)
Other reason	0.061*** (0.010)	-0.001 (0.010)	0.006 (0.011)	-0.014*** (0.003)	0.038** (0.013)	0.042** (0.014)	-0.047*** (0.007)	-0.026** (0.010)	-0.038*** (0.010)
Observations	52,405	46,642	43,728	52,405	46,662	43,728	52,405	46,107	43,728
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Origin area		X			X			X	
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X			X	
Origin area			X			X			X
Recession effect*Reason for migration			X			X			X
			-0.004 (0.006)			-0.006 (0.007)			0.013* (0.006)

Panel (B)									
<10 years sample									
	High-skill			Medium-skill			Elementary-level		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Work (omitted category)									
Family	-0.020 (0.011)	-0.040*** (0.011)	-0.037** (0.012)	0.003 (0.002)	0.026 (0.015)	0.028 (0.015)	0.016 (0.009)	0.023* (0.011)	0.019 (0.012)
Study	0.342*** (0.022)	0.133*** (0.021)	0.136*** (0.022)	-0.176*** (0.016)	-0.102*** (0.025)	-0.099*** (0.026)	-0.166*** (0.008)	-0.107*** (0.017)	-0.102*** (0.018)
Refugee	-0.123*** (0.014)	-0.038 (0.025)	-0.052* (0.025)	-0.003 (0.004)	0.044 (0.029)	0.055 (0.028)	0.126*** (0.017)	0.032 (0.022)	0.037 (0.022)
Other reason	0.036 (0.020)	0.011 (0.019)	0.014 (0.020)	-0.009 (0.006)	0.018 (0.025)	0.017 (0.026)	-0.027 (0.015)	-0.020 (0.020)	-0.025 (0.020)
Observations	14,337	12,997	13,030	14,337	13,023	13,030	14,337	12,797	13,030
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Origin area		X			X			X	
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X			X	
Origin area			X			X			X
Recession effect*Reason for migration			X			X			X
			-0.000 (0.008)			0.006 (0.010)			-0.003 (0.008)

Note: The table reports the coefficients of the refugees and other migrants residing in the EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of the ordered probit regression model of the dependent variable 'occupation level' with high, medium, and low skill occupations. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. The sample comprises migrants aged between 20 and 64. The baseline estimations include destination country-survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. Controls include gender, age category, education, and language skills. In education, lower secondary education is the excluded category; in language, advanced language proficiency is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in the age category, 20-24 years is the excluded category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates are statistically different from work migrants at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels of significance. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

3.4. Heterogeneities between refugees and other migrant groups based on gender, education, and language skills

Table 14 reports the estimates from equation (2) separately for men and women in Panel A, for non-tertiary and tertiary education in Panel B, and non-advanced and advanced language proficiency in Panel C for non-economic migrant groups, and work migrants are the reference category.

Gender differences in labor market outcomes of migrants

Panel A highlights gender based disparities in labor market outcomes among migrant groups.

Employment outcomes

Refugee men are 13.3 percentage points less likely to be employed, while refugee women face an even larger employment gap of 19.9 percentage points compared to their work migrant peers. Among other migrant men, family migrants and those who migrated for other reasons are 7.4 and 7.8 percentage points less likely to be employed, while study migrant men do not significantly differ from work migrant men. In contrast, employment gaps among migrant women are evident across all groups, including those who initially entered the EU countries for study reasons. Study migrant women are 7.6 percentage points less likely to be employed, while family migrant women experience an employment gap similar to refugee women at 19.4 percentage points. Other reason migrant women are 14.2 percentage points less likely to be employed than work migrant women.

A study by [Frattini and Solmone \(2022b\)](#) found that migrant women generally have lower employment rates than migrant men, with the migrant-native employment gap being more pronounced for women in nearly all European countries, despite their higher educational attainment. The findings presented in Table 14 align with this trend, revealing **substantial employment disparities among migrant women, particularly refugee women**, who lag significantly behind their male refugee counterparts. These results are consistent with previous migration research by [Cheung and Phillimore \(2017\)](#); [Kosyakova and Kogan \(2022\)](#); [Salikutluk and Menke \(2021\)](#).

Unemployment outcomes

Refugee men are 3.6 percentage points more likely to be unemployed, whereas refugee women are 2.6 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed compared to their similar work migrant peers. Among other migrant men, study and other reason migrants do not significantly differ from work migrant men, while family migrant men are 2.5 percentage points more likely to be unemployed. Similarly, among migrant women, study and other reason migrants do not show significant differences, whereas family migrant women are 2.3 percentage points more likely to be unemployed.

High-skilled occupation outcomes

Refugee men face significant challenges in accessing high-skilled employment, being 4.3 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to hold high-skilled jobs. In contrast, refugee women are not statistically different from work migrant women in their likelihood of occupying high-skilled jobs. Among other migrant groups, study migrant men and women have a clear advantage, being 11.4 and 12.3 percentage points more likely to be employed in high-skilled occupations compared to work migrants. However, family and other reason migrants, regardless of gender, do not significantly differ from work migrants in occupying high-skilled jobs.

A study on Austria's labor market by [Ortlieb et al. \(2024\)](#) found that **although refugee women have lower**

employment rates than refugee men, they are disproportionately represented in high-skilled occupations. This trend is reflected in Table 14, where **refugee women, despite lower overall employment rates, are equally likely as work migrant women to hold high-skilled jobs.** However, **refugee men experience a significant high-skilled occupation gap compared to work-migrant men.** Therefore, policies should focus on facilitating high-skilled job placements for refugee women through targeted training and skills development rather than placing them in low-skilled jobs prematurely. A study conducted by [Jestl and Tverdostup \(2023\)](#) find that the nature of the first job significantly influences the long-term employment trajectories of migrants in the host country.

Low-skilled occupation outcomes

Refugee men and women do not significantly differ from their work-migrant counterparts in their likelihood of working in elementary occupations. Family migrant men and women exhibit similar patterns, showing no significant differences from work migrants in this regard. However, other reason migrant women are 4.8 percentage points less likely to work in elementary occupations than work migrant women, while other reason migrant men do not show a significant difference. Study migrants, particularly women, demonstrate the strongest advantage in not occupying elementary jobs. Study migrant men are 4.4 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to hold elementary jobs, while study migrant women are 16.2 percentage points less likely, making them the most advantaged group in this category.

Income distribution outcomes

Refugee men are 5 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile, while refugee women do not significantly differ from their work-migrant counterparts. Among other migrant groups, family and other reason migrant men and women do not show significant differences. However, other reason migrant men are 3.8 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) and other reason migrant women are 2.2 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to be in the top-income decile compared to work migrants.

In the bottom-income decile, migrant groups do not show significant differences from their work migrant counterparts, except for family migrant women, who are 3.4 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be in the bottom-income decile.

Discussion and policy implications

Targeted policy interventions are necessary to address the employment gap faced by migrant women, who consistently experience a large disadvantage compared to migrant men. **Particular attention is needed for refugee women, who exhibit the largest employment gap among all migrant groups.** Family migrant women also face similar challenges, highlighting the need for policies that address both refugee and family migrant integration.

Additionally, **policy measures should focus on refugee men, who not only experience high unemployment rates but also significant disadvantages in accessing high-skilled jobs.** This lack of upward mobility contributes to their underrepresentation in the top-income decile. Addressing these disparities requires a dual approach: enhancing access to skills development programs and improving job-matching mechanisms that align refugee qualifications with suitable employment opportunities.

Instead of prioritizing rapid placement into low-skilled jobs **for refugee women, policies should focus on facilitating their entry into high-skilled employment through structured training and career development initiatives.** Given that the first job in a host country can significantly impact long-term employment trajectories, ensuring that refugee women can leverage their skills in appropriate roles will be critical for their economic integration and self-sufficiency.

By addressing these structural barriers, policymakers can enhance labor market outcomes for refugees, reduce dependency on welfare systems, and promote more equitable economic integration across gender and migrant

status groups.

Education differences in labor market outcomes of migrants

Panel B presents the labor market differences among refugees and other migrant groups with and without tertiary education.

Employment outcomes

Among those without tertiary education, refugees are 17 percentage points less likely to be employed than work migrants with similar educational backgrounds. Refugees with tertiary education face a slightly smaller, but still substantial, employment gap of 14.1 percentage points compared to work migrants with tertiary education.

For other migrant groups without tertiary education, family migrants experience a 14 percentage point employment gap, other reason migrants have a 11 percentage point gap, and study migrants have a 6.2 percentage point gap compared to work migrants. Similarly, among migrants with tertiary education, family migrants are 14.8 percentage points, other reason migrants are 9.5 percentage points, and study migrants are 4.7 percentage points less likely to be employed than similar work migrants.

The findings in Table 14 indicate that even after controlling for individuals who arrived from the same origin area to the same destination country and from the same entry cohort significant employment gaps remain in refugee labor market outcomes. These gaps suggest that beyond educational qualifications, the reason for migration plays a critical role in employment outcomes in EU countries. **Refugees, in particular, face persistently weaker employment outcomes, even when they hold tertiary qualifications.** This discrepancy is likely driven by factors such as **labor market discrimination and difficulties in foreign qualification recognition due to regulatory barriers, as widely documented in refugee labor market research.**

Unemployment outcomes

Among non-tertiary educated migrants, refugees are 2.2 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed, and family migrants face a 1.5 percentage point increase in unemployment risk. In contrast, study migrants and other reason migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants in their unemployment likelihood.

Among tertiary-educated migrants, refugees are 5.5 percentage points more likely to be unemployed, and family migrants face a 3.8 percentage point higher unemployment risk. However, study and other reason migrants do not exhibit significant differences from work migrants in unemployment outcomes.

A study by [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#), analyzing the 2008 and 2014 EU-LFS data, found that **refugees are less likely to be employed and more likely to be unemployed than other migrants with similar educational characteristics.** The findings in Table 14 align with prior literature, underscoring the need for stronger policies to close employment and unemployment gaps while addressing structural barriers in EU labor markets.

High-skilled occupation outcomes

Refugees without tertiary education do not significantly differ from work migrants in high-skilled employment. However, other migrant groups show stronger high-skilled employment outcomes: study migrants are 12.4 percentage points, other reason migrants are 4.3 percentage points, and family migrants are 2.4 percentage points more likely than work migrants to hold high-skill jobs with similar educational backgrounds.

Among migrants with tertiary education, refugees face a significant disadvantage, being 15.8 percentage points less likely to hold high-skilled employment compared to work migrants. Other reason migrants and family migrants also face barriers, being 6.9 and 4.8 percentage points less likely to hold high-skilled jobs. In contrast, study migrants benefit significantly, being 12.3 percentage points more likely than work migrants to occupy high-skilled jobs.

The substantial gap in high-skilled employment among refugees in column (6) is **primarily due to challenges such as overqualification with difficulties in skills recognition and the absence of documentation for their qualifications that they bring from their home countries**. One potential solution is **simplifying the process of foreign qualification recognition** to facilitate access to skilled employment. Additionally, **investing in host-country education is crucial for refugees' long-term labor market integration**, improving their ability to access high-skilled jobs.

Active Labor Market Policies (ALMPs) can significantly enhance employment outcomes for less employable refugees by providing targeted training programs that improve job stability. However, poorly designed ALMPs may yield ineffective results, leading to wasted resources. Well-structured ALMPs tailored to refugee needs could lead to positive employment and job quality outcomes. Research suggests that **ALMPs focusing on human capital investment yield substantial benefits**, with effects becoming evident two to three years after program completion (Card et al., 2018). Successful ALMPs have been observed in Sweden, Germany, and other EU countries, where targeted interventions improved refugee integration. In Sweden, intensive counseling and training programs (Joonas and Nekby, 2012), in Germany, NGO-led job search assistance programs (Battisti et al., 2019a), and in Sweden, a combination of practical job training, language courses, and job search support (Alexander et al., 2024) have demonstrated positive impacts on refugee employment and job quality.

Low-skilled occupation outcomes

Among non-tertiary educated migrants, refugee and family migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants in their likelihood of holding low-skilled jobs. However, study migrants are 15.6 percentage points, and other reason migrants are 4.6 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to work in low-skilled jobs compared to work migrants.

Among those with tertiary education, refugee, family, and other reason migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants in low-skilled employment. However, study migrants are 4.4 percentage points less likely to be employed in low-skilled jobs compared to work migrants with similar educational backgrounds.

Income distribution outcomes

Among non-tertiary educated migrants, refugee, study, and other reason migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants in their likelihood of being in the top-income decile. However, family migrants are 1.4 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be in the top-income decile compared to work migrants.

Among tertiary-educated migrants, refugees face a significant disadvantage, being 8.2 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to be in the top-income decile. Study migrants do not show significant differences from work migrants, while family migrants are 6 percentage points and other reason migrants are 10.2 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to be in the top-income decile.

For the bottom-income decile, refugees without tertiary education are 5.8 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be in the lowest-earnings bracket, while study and other reason migrants do not differ significantly from work migrants. However, family migrants are 3.5 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to be in the bottom-income decile. Among tertiary-educated migrants, no significant differences exist between refugee and other migrant groups regarding their likelihood of being in the bottom-income decile.

The income distribution outcomes for refugees with tertiary education in column (10) indicate that while they perform relatively well compared to other reason migrants, they still face substantial barriers to reaching the top-income decile. **Despite holding tertiary qualifications, refugees exhibit significant income disparities, suggesting that their educational attainment does not fully translate into higher earnings**. One key factor contributing to this outcome is the prevalence of refugees being overqualified and skills mismatch in the jobs they occupy due to qualification recognition issues.

As highlighted by [Fasani et al. \(2022\)](#), refugees tend to earn lower wages and are less likely to secure high-skilled employment. The findings in Table 14 align with existing literature, reinforcing that **tertiary education does not provide refugees with the same financial returns as it does for other migrant groups**. Specifically, column (10) demonstrates that **refugees with tertiary education are less likely to be in the top-income decile**, while column (11) shows that **among migrants with non-tertiary education, refugees remain more likely than their counterparts to be in the bottom-income decile**.

These findings suggest that tertiary education does not serve as a sufficient mechanism for upward income mobility for refugees, while non-tertiary education further increases their likelihood of being in the lowest income bracket. This highlights a persistent disadvantage in labor market outcomes for refugees compared to other migrant groups, irrespective of educational attainment.

Discussion and policy implications

Reforms aimed at simplifying the recognition of qualifications obtained in refugees' home countries could significantly enhance their access to high-skilled employment, thereby improving their likelihood of reaching the top-income decile. Facilitating the qualification recognition process would allow refugees to better utilize their existing skills and credentials in the labor market.

Additionally, **investing in education within the host country** could help refugees effectively integrate by enabling them to acquire qualifications that are more directly aligned with local labor market demands. This, in turn, would increase their chances of securing higher-paying skilled employment.

Furthermore, the implementation of well-designed Active Labor Market Policies (ALMPs) that specifically address the unique challenges faced by refugees is essential for improving their labor market outcomes. Tailored ALMPs, such as targeted job training, skills certification, and employment support programs, can play a crucial role in reducing barriers to employment and ensuring better economic integration.

Language differences in labor market outcomes of migrants

Panel C presents the labor market differences among refugees and other migrant groups with and without advanced language proficiency of the destination country.

Employment outcomes

Among migrants with no advanced language proficiency, refugees face the highest disadvantage, being 24.3 percentage points less likely to be employed compared to work migrants. Family migrants experience a somewhat similar gap of 20.5 percentage points, followed by other reason migrants (16.2 percentage points) and study migrants (8.1 percentage points, significant at a 5% confidence level).

Employment gaps are notably smaller for migrants with advanced language proficiency. Refugees are 10 percentage points less likely to be employed, while family migrants (10.5 percentage points), other reason migrants (7.7 percentage points), and study migrants (2.6 percentage points, significant at a 10% confidence level) experience lower employment likelihood compared to work migrants.

Unemployment outcomes

Among migrants without advanced language proficiency, refugees are 5.1 percentage points more likely to be unemployed while family migrants face a 1.6 percentage point (significant at a 5% confidence level) increase in the unemployment likelihood. In contrast, study and other reason migrants do not differ significantly from work migrants in their likelihood of unemployment.

For migrants with advanced language proficiency, refugee, study, and other reason migrants are not statistically different from work migrants in unemployment outcomes. However, family migrants remain at a disadvantage, being 2.4 percentage points more likely to be unemployed than work migrants.

High-skilled occupation outcomes

Among migrants without advanced language skills, refugees are 5.4 percentage points less likely to be employed in high-skilled jobs. Family and other reason migrants do not show significant differences from work migrants, whereas study migrants are significantly advantaged, being 11.9 percentage points more likely to work in high-skilled occupations.

The high-skill occupation gaps largely disappear for migrants with advanced language skills. Refugee, family, and other reason migrants are not statistically different from work migrants in occupying high-skilled jobs. However, study migrants remain advantaged, being 13 percentage points more likely to be employed in high-skilled occupations than work migrants.

Low-skilled occupation outcomes

Refugees, regardless of their language proficiency, do not significantly differ from work migrants in their likelihood of working in low-skilled jobs. Family migrants exhibit a similar pattern.

Among other reason migrants, language proficiency makes a difference. Those without advanced language skills are not significantly different from work migrants in their likelihood of being in low-skilled jobs. However, those with advanced language skills are 2.5 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to work in low-skilled jobs compared to work migrants.

Language proficiency plays a notable role for study migrants. Those without advanced language skills are 12.8 percentage points and those with advanced language skills are 7.6 percentage points less likely to work in elementary jobs than their work migrant peers.

Income distribution outcomes

In the top-income decile, among migrants without advanced language proficiency, refugees are 4.7 percentage points less likely to be in the highest-income decile than work migrants. Other reason migrants face a similar disadvantage as that they are 4.5 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile. However, family and study migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants in this regard.

The gaps are reduced among migrants with advanced language skills. Refugee, study, and other reason migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants in their likelihood of being in the top-income decile. However, other reasons migrants remain at a disadvantage, being 2.4 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to reach the top-income decile.

Language proficiency plays a significant role in the bottom-income decile outcomes. Among migrants without advanced language proficiency, refugees are 9.9 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level), and family migrants are 4.6 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to be in the bottom-income decile. Study and other reason migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants.

Among migrants with advanced language skills, refugee, study, and other reason migrants do not significantly differ from work migrants. However, family migrants remain at a disadvantage, being 2.5 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be in the bottom-income decile.

Discussion and policy implications

Language proficiency is a critical determinant of migrants' access to employment, job quality, and income levels in the destination country. Research consistently highlights the positive relationship between language skills and migrants' socio-economic integration ([Chiswick and Miller, 2015b](#); [Dustmann and Fabbri, 2003b](#); [Dustmann and van Soest, 2001](#)). While other migrants may choose their destination country based on language familiarity or have the opportunity to invest in language acquisition before migration, refugees, however, due to the forced nature of their migration, often lack this advantage. As a result, they start with a

significant language gap, which negatively impacts their initial labor market integration. However, over time, this gap can be reduced through the years of residence and exposure in the destination country.

Although language skills are beneficial for all migrants, their impact is particularly pronounced for refugees in the EU countries. **Early access to language training is a crucial factor in refugee economic integration.** The Reception Conditions Directive (RCD) of 2024 introduced important policy changes in this regard. Unlike the 2013 RCD (Article 16), which made language and vocational training optional, the **2024 RCD (Article 18) mandates compulsory language training for asylum seekers in EU member states.** Additionally, it incorporates civic education, further emphasizing the role of language in integration (Union, 2024). The findings presented in Panel C of Table 14 reinforce this argument. Columns (1), (3), (5), and (9) show that refugees with no advanced language proficiency face substantial employment, unemployment, high-skill jobs, and income decile gaps relative to the reference group. However, Columns (2), (4), (6), and (10) demonstrate that once refugees attain the advanced language skills of the host country, these gaps significantly narrow or become statistically insignificant when compared to work migrants.

The results highlight the critical role of language proficiency in shaping migrants’ labor market trajectories. For refugees, language acquisition is not merely an advantage but a necessity for successful integration. Policies that facilitate early language training and vocational skill development are essential to closing the employment and earnings gaps observed among refugees in EU labor markets. Given the findings, policymakers should focus on: **1. mandatory and early access to language training for refugees, aligning with the updated 2024 RCD directive. 2. Integration of language learning with job training programs, allowing refugees to develop industry-specific language skills. 3. Recognition of prior skills and qualifications, complemented by language support to facilitate skills transferability.**

By addressing language barriers early, refugees can transition into employment more effectively, secure high-quality jobs, and reduce long-term dependency on welfare systems, ultimately leading to improved economic and social integration in the EU destination countries.

Table 14: Heterogeneities between refugees and other migrant groups based on gender, education, and language skills

	Employment (1) (2)		Unemployment (3) (4)		High-skilled job (5) (6)		Low-skilled job (7) (8)		Top-income decile (9) (10)		Bottom-income decile (11) (12)	
Panel A - Gender differences												
Gender:	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women
Work (omitted category)												
Family	-0.074*** (0.008)	-0.194*** (0.007)	0.025*** (0.006)	0.023*** (0.005)	-0.014 (0.009)	0.002 (0.009)	0.010 (0.008)	-0.012 (0.009)	-0.007 (0.010)	-0.003 (0.008)	0.019 (0.011)	0.034* (0.015)
Study	-0.031 (0.016)	-0.076*** (0.016)	0.009 (0.013)	0.010 (0.011)	0.114*** (0.017)	0.123*** (0.017)	-0.044** (0.014)	-0.162*** (0.015)	0.007 (0.017)	0.017 (0.016)	0.035 (0.028)	-0.021 (0.042)
Refugee	-0.133*** (0.014)	-0.199*** (0.015)	0.036*** (0.010)	0.026* (0.010)	-0.043** (0.015)	-0.031 (0.019)	-0.003 (0.013)	0.023 (0.020)	-0.050*** (0.013)	0.006 (0.017)	0.036 (0.025)	0.046 (0.039)
Other reason	-0.078*** (0.013)	-0.142*** (0.013)	0.000 (0.010)	0.016 (0.009)	-0.011 (0.014)	0.009 (0.015)	-0.013 (0.013)	-0.048** (0.015)	-0.038** (0.012)	-0.022* (0.008)	0.032 (0.026)	-0.001 (0.028)
Observations	44,139	52,798	43,338	51,332	23,561	22,933	22,738	22,485	7,968	6,803	7,985	9,546
Panel B - Education differences												
Tertiary Education:	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Work (omitted category)												
Family	-0.140*** (0.006)	-0.148*** (0.008)	0.015*** (0.005)	0.038*** (0.006)	0.024*** (0.007)	-0.048*** (0.013)	-0.010 (0.008)	0.006 (0.008)	0.014* (0.006)	-0.060* (0.026)	0.035** (0.011)	0.021 (0.019)
Study	-0.062** (0.021)	-0.047*** (0.012)	0.011 (0.014)	0.015 (0.009)	0.124*** (0.024)	0.123*** (0.015)	-0.156*** (0.019)	-0.044*** (0.007)	-0.001 (0.010)	0.031 (0.035)	0.074 (0.046)	-0.032 (0.023)
Refugee	-0.170*** (0.013)	-0.141*** (0.018)	0.022* (0.009)	0.055*** (0.013)	0.007 (0.012)	-0.158*** (0.025)	0.004 (0.016)	0.015 (0.016)	0.005 (0.009)	-0.082* (0.041)	0.058* (0.028)	0.032 (0.047)
Other reason	-0.110*** (0.012)	-0.095*** (0.013)	0.006 (0.008)	0.009 (0.009)	0.043*** (0.012)	-0.069*** (0.021)	-0.046** (0.014)	-0.010 (0.012)	-0.003 (0.005)	-0.102** (0.037)	0.008 (0.022)	-0.005 (0.028)
Observations	67,748	29,163	66,949	27,752	30,050	16,077	30,110	12,797	8,579	4,869	13,525	3,891

Advanced Proficiency:	Panel C - Language differences											
	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Work (omitted category)												
Family	-0.205*** (0.009)	-0.105*** (0.007)	0.016** (0.006)	0.024*** (0.005)	-0.018 (0.009)	0.004 (0.009)	0.016 (0.012)	-0.005 (0.007)	-0.015 (0.013)	-0.002 (0.008)	0.046** (0.018)	0.025* (0.011)
Study	-0.081** (0.025)	-0.026* (0.013)	0.030 (0.018)	0.004 (0.009)	0.119*** (0.023)	0.130*** (0.015)	-0.128*** (0.024)	-0.076*** (0.011)	-0.022 (0.014)	0.024 (0.015)	0.034 (0.075)	0.016 (0.026)
Refugee	-0.243*** (0.015)	-0.100*** (0.015)	0.051*** (0.012)	0.011 (0.009)	-0.054*** (0.014)	-0.021 (0.017)	0.004 (0.020)	0.013 (0.015)	-0.047*** (0.009)	-0.018 (0.014)	0.099* (0.045)	0.027 (0.028)
Other reason	-0.162*** (0.018)	-0.077*** (0.011)	0.007 (0.012)	0.010 (0.008)	0.005 (0.016)	0.001 (0.013)	-0.027 (0.022)	-0.025* (0.010)	-0.045*** (0.007)	-0.024** (0.009)	0.009 (0.039)	0.014 (0.021)
Observations	35,086	61,876	34,518	60,753	15,678	30,643	15,737	29,831	3,084	12,164	5,238	13,000
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Individual Controls	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Entry Cohort*Destination Country	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Entry Cohort*Origin Area	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Note: The table reports the coefficients of migrant groups residing in the EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of a probit regression model for the dependent variables employment, unemployment, occupation, and income decile. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. Panel A reports the gender differences, Panel B reports the tertiary and non-tertiary education differences, and Panel C reports the differences in not having and having advanced-level language skills. The sample comprises migrants aged between 20 and 64. All specifications include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the destination country and survey year fixed effects. The probit model includes gender, age category in five-year age groups, education, and language proficiency controls where needed. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates statistically differ from work migrants at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels of significance. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

Chapter 4

Do refugee labor market outcomes differ based on their origin areas?

Refugees migrate to EU destination countries seeking protection from threats such as persecution, war, or violence in their home countries. This chapter studies the labor market outcomes of refugees from five main origin areas, i.e., Other Europe, North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America.¹⁷

This chapter offers a novel perspective, as previous studies at the European level have not specifically analyzed labor market outcomes across different refugee groups based on their origin area. Historically, the labor market dynamics of refugees have been an underexplored topic, with most research focusing on economic migrants entering EU countries. Refugee integration studies conducted on North America, Canada, and the UK by [Bevelander and Pendakur \(2014\)](#); [Cortes \(2004\)](#); [Ruiz and Vargas-Silva \(2018\)](#), as well as of individual European countries by [Bratsberg et al. \(2014\)](#); [Sarvimäki \(2017\)](#) among others, primarily analyzed refugee integration gaps in comparison to other migrant groups. In contrast, this chapter uniquely investigates the labor market outcomes of refugees based on their origin area.

The 2015 Syrian refugee crisis and the Ukraine-Russia war highlight the importance of understanding the refugee experiences in the EU labor market based on their regional context. This chapter provides a critical analysis of the challenges faced by refugee groups from different origin areas in integrating into EU labor markets. Such an approach can inform policymakers, enabling them to adopt tailored strategies to expedite refugee integration by addressing refugee region-specific challenges and barriers in the European labor market.

The probit regression model used to analyze the labor market outcomes of refugee groups is

$$y_{idse} = \beta \text{refugee}_{idse} * \text{recession} + \gamma(D.\text{Country} * S.\text{Year})_i + \phi X_{idse} + \rho(E.\text{Cohort})_i + \epsilon_i \quad (3)$$

y_{idse} represents a dichotomous outcome of interest of an individual "i" who is a refugee residing in an EU destination country "d" and was interviewed in the survey year "s" from the entry cohort "e." The recession dummy is an indicator variable that takes the value of 1 if the EU destination country was affected by an economic downturn during the entry cohort of a refugee.¹⁸ "D.Country" and "S.Year" are a set of the destination country and survey year fixed effects that capture any economic and non-economic fluctuations in the destination countries during the survey year. X_{idse} is a vector of controls for gender, age, education, and language skills of refugees. "E.Cohort" is the entry cohort of a refugee into an EU destination country that captures all unobservable factors common to refugees from the same year of arrival.¹⁹ " ϵ_i " captures the heteroskedastic robust standard error. In equation (3), refugees from Other Europe are considered the reference category.

4.1. Employment likelihood among refugee groups

Table 15 presents the coefficients of the employment likelihood of refugee groups from North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America, compared to refugees from Other Europe (reference group). These coefficients are derived from the probit regression model based on Equation (3), which evaluates employment likelihood through a step-wise approach, incorporating various controls and fixed effects. Below are the key findings:

¹⁷The EU-LFS provides only the origin areas of refugees and not their exact country of origin.

¹⁸Recession effects of the EU destination countries is taken from the World Bank data. Recession=1 if an EU destination country has a negative GDP per capita growth rate during the entry cohort of a refugee, and recession=0 if an EU destination country has a positive GDP per capita growth rate during the entry cohort of a refugee. In the case of a five-year entry cohort band of a refugee, if an EU destination country had a negative GDP growth rate for more than 2 years, then the recession indicator is 1, else 0.

¹⁹Entry cohort or year of arrival of a refugee is represented by a single-year or a 5-year entry cohort band.

Baseline employment gaps: At baseline in column (1), **North African and Middle Eastern refugees exhibit a significant employment gap** of -12.2 percentage points compared to the reference group (Other Europe). Controlling for gender and age in column (2), this gap widens to -14.6 percentage points, and the employment gap for Other African refugees becomes -6.3 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level).

Role of education and language skills: Education and language skills are critical determinants of labor market outcomes in destination countries. Refugees, due to the fear of persecution and violence in their home countries, are less likely to return and, therefore, **have a strong incentive to invest in the destination country's human capital**. A study by Cortes (2004) highlights the permanence of refugees in destination countries increases their likelihood of investing in destination country skills. Similarly, Borjas (1982) emphasizes the long-term labor market benefits of destination country human capital, even though initial employment outcomes may remain poor due to structural disadvantages and complex refugee migration patterns. In column (3), adding education to the model reduces the employment gap for North Africa and Middle East refugees to -13.3 percentage points. Including language skills in column (4) further narrows the gap to -8.8 percentage points. **These findings demonstrate the significant positive impact of destination countries' human capital, such as education and language skills, on North African and Middle Eastern refugees**, with language proficiency having a more pronounced effect on employment likelihood.

Effect of entry cohort: Accounting for the entry cohort in column (5) eliminates the significance of the employment gap for **North African and Middle Eastern refugees, suggesting that this group is overrepresented in recent cohorts**, particularly this effect could be coming from the large influx of refugees from the 2015 crisis. Refugees from recent cohorts likely had less time to integrate into EU labor markets, which could explain the large initial employment gap that became insignificant after the entry cohort was induced into the model.

Impact of initial shocks: In column (6), inducing fixed effects for entry cohort and destination country captures the initial shocks (e.g., unemployment rates and GDP growth rate) that might affect employment outcomes of refugee groups. The results reveal that North African and Middle Eastern refugees face a -6.3 percentage point (significant at a 10% confidence level) employment gap, while there is no significant impact on the other refugee groups.

Recession effects: The recession effects on employment likelihood are analyzed for the "full sample" of refugees and refugees who entered EU destination countries in the last ten years. Åslund and Rooth (2007); Barsbai et al. (2023); Fasani et al. (2021) in their research have examined the negative impact on the employment outcomes of refugees compared to other migrants who entered destination countries during a recession period. This section adds a novel perspective to the existing body of literature by comparing the different refugee groups entering EU destination countries to the resilience of recession effects. The coefficients in the "full sample" show that **entering during a recession period reduces employment likelihood** by -4.9 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) **for all refugee groups, with North African and Middle East refugees having a significant and strongest negative effect** of -9.1 percentage points on employment likelihood. However, there is no significant recession effect on recent refugee groups in the "less than ten-year sample." Additionally, the recent cohorts do not show significant differences in employment outcomes across the refugee groups during their initial years in EU countries, irrespective of the recession and non-recession periods. Conversely, older cohorts, especially North African and Middle Eastern refugees, experience a more pronounced negative employment gap.

Discussion and policy implications:

Immediate policy interventions are needed for North African and Middle Eastern refugees as they face persistent employment challenges. Priority should be given to:

1. **Language training and educational attainment programs**, including diploma courses, which can significantly enhance their employment outcomes.

2. **Skills recognition programs** targeted at refugees from North African and Middle Eastern origin areas, as they may face difficulties in having their qualifications recognized in EU countries.

Table 15: Employment likelihood among refugee groups

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Other Europe (Omitted group)				
North Africa and Middle East	-0.122*** (0.025)	-0.146*** (0.025)	-0.133*** (0.025)	-0.088*** (0.026)
Other Africa	-0.031 (0.032)	-0.063* (0.031)	-0.021 (0.032)	-0.006 (0.031)
Asia	0.003 (0.031)	-0.027 (0.031)	0.016 (0.031)	0.052 (0.031)
Latin America	0.074 (0.054)	0.078 (0.053)	0.087 (0.054)	0.055 (0.048)
Observations	6,335	6,335	6,248	5,790
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X
Gender and Age		X	X	X
Education			X	X
Language skills				X
	(5)	(6)	(Full sample)	(<10 years sample)
Other Europe (Omitted group)				
North Africa and Middle East	-0.044 (0.027)	-0.063* (0.029)	-0.091*** (0.026)	0.000 (0.056)
Other Africa	0.031 (0.032)	0.017 (0.033)	-0.013 (0.031)	0.033 (0.058)
Asia	0.062 (0.032)	0.035 (0.034)	0.046 (0.031)	0.136* (0.061)
Latin America	0.105* (0.048)	0.075 (0.052)	0.059 (0.049)	0.163 (0.099)
Observations	5,742	5,583	5,572	2,042
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X
Gender and Age	X	X	X	X
Education	X	X	X	X
Language skills	X	X	X	X
Entry cohort	X			
Entry cohort*Destination country		X		
Recession effect			X -0.049* (0.022)	X -0.013 (0.027)

Note: The table reports the employment coefficients of North African and Middle Eastern, Other African, Asian, and Latin American refugee groups compared to Other European refugees estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. All refugees aged between 20 and 64 are included in the analysis. All specifications include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. The probit model induces gender, age category, education, language skills, and entry cohort of refugees through step-wise regression. Additionally, fixed effects are captured from the interaction dummies for the entry cohort-destination country, and recession effects of the EU destination countries are captured. In the age category, 20-24 is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in education, low education is the excluded category; in language, advanced language proficiency is the excluded category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates are statistically different from refugees from Other Europe at 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

4.2. Unemployment and income distribution likelihood among refugee groups

A key question explored in this section is whether refugees from different origin areas exhibit varying likelihoods of unemployment and income distribution outcomes. Table 16 presents the coefficients for unemployment, top, and bottom-income deciles, estimated from equation (3) of refugee groups residing in EU destination countries.

Panel A presents the unemployment likelihood of refugee groups. In the "full sample" estimates, the baseline results in column (1) indicate that **refugees from North Africa and the Middle East are significantly more likely to be unemployed**, at 6.1 percentage points. Similarly, refugees from Other Africa are 6.1 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed.

When socio-demographic characteristics are introduced in column (2), the unemployment likelihood for North African and Middle Eastern refugees decreases to 5.2 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level). For refugees from Other African region, the effect becomes statistically insignificant.

Controlling for recession effects in column (3) reveals no significant difference in unemployment likelihood among refugee groups entering during a recession and non-recession periods. In the "less than 10-year sample," no significant unemployment effects are observed for any refugee group, nor are recession effects significant. This likely reflects the time required for recent refugee cohorts to adjust to the European labor market.

Income distribution

As the data is only available for the 2014 survey wave for income distribution, the sample sizes for individual refugee groups are small. Therefore, the results of column (1) are only analyzed (for reliable analysis of top and bottom-income deciles).

Panel B reports the differences in the likelihood of being in the top-income decile among refugee groups. The baseline estimates in the "full sample" show that refugee groups are not statistically different from the reference group. However, the only exception is Other African refugees, who are somewhat significantly less likely to be in the top-income decile by 4 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level). Panel C reports the differences in the likelihood of being in the bottom-income decile among refugee groups. From the "full sample" estimates, Asian refugees are significantly less likely to be in the bottom-income decile and have strong characteristics that make them even less likely to be in the bottom-income decile (at -20 percentage points). Refugees from other regions are not statistically different from the reference group.

Discussion and policy implications:

Overall, refugees from North Africa and the Middle East, and Other Africa need special attention, given their higher association with unemployment despite their socio-demographic advantage. **Early attention on refugees entering from these regions in skills recognition and training programs could be beneficial as they are weakly associated with the EU labor market.**

Table 16: Unemployment and income distribution likelihood among refugee groups

Panel A - Unemployment						
	Full sample			<10 years sample		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Other Europe (Omitted category)						
North Africa and Middle East	0.061*** (0.015)	0.052* (0.020)	0.056** (0.017)	0.023 (0.040)	0.032 (0.040)	0.015 (0.043)
Other Africa	0.061** (0.020)	0.038 (0.022)	0.059** (0.022)	0.019 (0.043)	0.021 (0.043)	0.019 (0.047)
Asia	0.019 (0.018)	0.001 (0.021)	0.008 (0.021)	-0.050 (0.041)	-0.039 (0.043)	-0.060 (0.045)
Latin America	-0.014 (0.030)	0.020 (0.045)	-0.002 (0.035)	-0.052 (0.077)	0.046 (0.109)	-0.040 (0.084)
Observations	6,335	5,192	5,572	2,302	1,842	2,034
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X	
Recession effect*Origin area of refugee			X -0.001 (0.015)			X 0.004 (0.023)

Panel B - Top-income decile						
	Full sample			<10 years sample		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Other Europe (Omitted category)						
North Africa and Middle East	0.006 (0.042)	-0.063 (.)	0.004 (0.047)	0.000 (.)	- (-)	- (-)
Other Africa	-0.040* (0.020)	-0.143 (.)	-0.129*** (0.020)	0.000 (.)	- (-)	- (-)
Asia	0.019 (0.057)	0.269 (.)	0.039 (0.085)	0.000 (.)	- (-)	- (-)
Latin America	0.117 (0.122)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	- (-)	- (-)
Observations	391	133	228	11	-	-
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X	
Recession effect*Origin area of refugee			X 0.000 (.)			X

Panel C - Bottom-income decile						
	Full sample			<10 years sample		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Other Europe (Omitted category)						
North Africa and Middle East	0.001 (0.070)	-0.057 (0.087)	0.000 (.)	0.235 (0.151)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
Other Africa	0.010 (0.068)	0.021 (0.081)	0.029 (0.064)	0.201 (0.113)	0.000 (.)	0.282** (0.105)
Asia	-0.138** (0.045)	-0.196*** (0.037)	0.000 (.)	-0.009 (0.095)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
Latin America	0.117 (0.174)	0.496* (0.206)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
Observations	426	337	405	73	29	58
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X	
Recession effect*Origin area of refugee			X			X
			0.000 (.)			0.000 (.)

Note: The table reports the coefficients of different refugee groups residing in the EU destination countries estimated through the probit regression model of the dependent variable 'unemployment,' 'top and bottom-income decile.' Sampling weights are used in the analysis. The sample consists of refugees and other migrants aged between 20 and 64. The baseline or no control estimations include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. Controls include gender, age category, education, and language proficiency. In education, lower secondary education is the excluded category; in language, advanced language proficiency is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in the age category, 20-24 years is the excluded category. Income decile information is only available for the 2014 survey wave. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates are statistically different from refugees from Other Europe at 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

4.3. Occupation likelihood among refugee groups

Table 17 presents the occupational likelihood coefficients for refugees from five main origin regions: North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America, with Other Europe refugees serving as the reference group. Panel A provides estimates for the "full sample," while Panel B focuses on "less than ten-year" sample estimates.

High-skilled occupation

In the "full sample" estimates, at baseline, refugees from Other Africa are 12.7 percentage points less likely to be employed in high-skilled occupations, while refugees from Asia are 6.1 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to do so. In contrast, the occupational outcomes of refugees from North Africa and the Middle East and those from Latin America are not statistically different from those of Other Europe refugees. However, after controlling for individual characteristics and fixed effects, refugees from North Africa and the Middle East become 5.2 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to hold high-skilled jobs, whereas refugees from all other regions show no significant differences from the reference group.

In the "recent cohorts" sample, refugees from all four non-European regions are not statistically different from Other European refugees in their likelihood of being employed in high-skilled occupations, both at baseline and after adjusting for individual controls and fixed effects.

Medium-skilled occupation

In the "full sample" estimates, at baseline, refugees from Other Africa are 2.7 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to be employed in medium-skilled occupations,

while refugees from all other regions do not differ significantly from Other Europe refugees. However, after adjusting for individual characteristics and fixed effects, the differences across refugee groups disappear, indicating that observed characteristics explain most of the initial disparities.

A similar pattern is observed in the "recent cohorts" estimates, where refugees from Other Africa are 7.7 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to be employed in medium-skilled jobs, while all other refugee groups do not significantly differ from the reference group. After accounting for socio-demographic characteristics and fixed effects, all refugee groups become statistically similar in their likelihood of holding medium-skilled occupations, mirroring the pattern seen in the "full sample."

Elementary occupation

In the "full sample" estimates, at baseline, refugees from Other Africa are 15.3 percentage points more likely to work in elementary occupations, while refugees from Asia are 6 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to do so. However, once individual controls and fixed effects are applied, refugees from all regions are no longer statistically different from one another in their likelihood of holding elementary jobs.

In the "recent cohorts" estimates, at baseline, refugees from Other Africa are 15.4 percentage points more likely to be employed in elementary jobs, while all other refugee groups do not differ significantly from Other European refugees. However, after accounting for socio-demographic characteristics and fixed effects, refugees from all non-European regions are no longer significantly different from the reference group in elementary occupation outcomes.

Effects of recession

In the "full sample" estimates, the effects of entering the labor market during a recession are particularly evident in elementary occupations. Refugees who arrived in the EU countries during a recession period are 7.3 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to work in elementary jobs than those who arrived during non-recession periods. However, recession effects are not significant in high and medium-skilled occupations. Furthermore, the negative impact of a recession is only observed in the "full sample" estimates for elementary jobs, while it does not appear in the "recent cohorts" estimates.

Discussion and policy implications

The findings indicate that refugees from Other Africa, North Africa and the Middle East, experience poor occupational outcomes compared to refugees from other regions. Likewise, refugees from Asia tend to be less likely to hold high-skilled jobs and more likely to hold elementary jobs. While previous research has primarily focused on employment rates, further investigation into occupational outcomes provides deeper insights into the types and quality of jobs taken up by different refugee groups in EU countries. Particular policy attention is needed for refugees from African and Middle Eastern regions, as they generally face significant barriers to employment and experience prolonged periods of joblessness, as also highlighted in previous studies by [Dustmann et al. \(2017\)](#); [Lundborg \(2013\)](#). These groups not only encounter difficulties in securing employment but also face additional challenges in high-skilled job outcomes.

Refugees from these two regions tend to have lower educational qualifications, and even those with formal education often struggle with skills recognition in EU countries. Addressing these challenges requires targeted policy interventions, particularly in **improving access to education in host countries and expanding language training opportunities. Facilitating skill recognition processes**

and ensuring that refugees can effectively transfer their qualifications to the host labor market would also enhance their occupational outcomes.

By implementing more inclusive policies, EU countries can improve the occupational integration of refugees, reduce their dependency on welfare support, and mitigate the risks of long-term unemployment, social isolation, and economic marginalization.

Table 17: Occupation likelihood among refugee groups

Panel (A)									
Full sample									
	High-skill			Medium-skill			Elementary-level		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Other Europe (Omitted category)									
North Africa and the Middle East	0.006 (0.024)	0.052* (0.026)	-0.021 (0.028)	-0.001 (0.004)	-0.005 (0.004)	0.049 (0.036)	-0.005 (0.020)	-0.047 (0.024)	-0.026 (0.028)
Other Africa	-0.127*** (0.024)	-0.032 (0.027)	-0.074* (0.034)	-0.027* (0.011)	-0.004 (0.005)	0.014 (0.044)	0.153*** (0.031)	0.036 (0.031)	0.066 (0.037)
Asia	-0.061* (0.028)	0.016 (0.029)	0.009 (0.037)	0.001 (0.004)	-0.000 (0.001)	0.015 (0.045)	0.060* (0.029)	-0.016 (0.029)	-0.009 (0.034)
Latin America	0.045 (0.062)	0.012 (0.051)	0.055 (0.065)	-0.011 (0.019)	0.000 (0.001)	-0.030 (0.084)	-0.034 (0.043)	-0.012 (0.050)	0.003 (0.059)
Observations	3,062	2,742	2,618	3,062	2,742	2,631	3,062	2,742	2,626
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X			X	
Recession effect*Origin area of refugee			X			X			X
			-0.026 (0.029)			-0.037 (0.039)			0.073* (0.034)

Panel (B)									
<10 years sample									
	High-skill			Medium-skill			Elementary-level		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Other Europe (Omitted category)									
North Africa and the Middle East	0.040 (0.047)	0.043 (0.051)	-0.060 (0.083)	0.011 (0.020)	0.009 (0.019)	0.149 (0.084)	-0.051 (0.067)	-0.052 (0.068)	-0.095 (0.072)
Other Africa	-0.077 (0.046)	-0.061 (0.050)	-0.113 (0.083)	-0.077* (0.034)	-0.048 (0.032)	0.007 (0.092)	0.154* (0.076)	0.110 (0.077)	0.123 (0.085)
Asia	-0.054 (0.050)	-0.018 (0.055)	-0.001 (0.096)	-0.042 (0.035)	-0.009 (0.025)	-0.020 (0.093)	0.096 (0.082)	0.026 (0.079)	0.055 (0.084)
Latin America	0.191 (0.124)	0.077 (0.126)	-0.046 (0.138)	-0.024 (0.053)	0.007 (0.020)	0.294 (0.167)	-0.168 (0.092)	-0.084 (0.126)	-0.233* (0.096)
Observations	1,012	868	806	1,012	868	857	1,012	868	848
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gender, Age, Education, Language		X	X		X	X		X	X
Entry cohort*Destination country		X			X			X	
Recession effect*Origin area of refugee			X			X			X
			0.021 (0.039)			-0.022 (0.047)			0.008 (0.040)

Note: The table reports the coefficients of the refugee groups residing in the EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of the ordered probit regression model of the dependent variable 'occupation level' with high, medium, and low-skilled occupations. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. Other European refugees are the reference category. The sample comprises refugee groups aged between 20 and 64. The baseline estimations include only destination country-survey year interaction dummies to capture the fixed effects. Controls include gender, age category, education, and language proficiency. In education, lower secondary education is the excluded category; in language, advanced language proficiency is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in age category, 20-24 years is the excluded category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates are statistically different from refugees from Other Europe at 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

4.4. Heterogeneities among refugee groups based on gender, education, and language skills

Table 18 presents the estimates from equation (3) for gender in Panel A, education in Panel B, and language proficiency in Panel C for refugee groups from different origin regions living in EU destination countries.

Gender differences in labor market outcomes among refugee groups

Panel A highlights gender gaps in labor market outcomes among refugee groups.

Employment outcomes

Among refugee men, those from Latin America are 19.3 percentage points more likely to be employed than the reference refugee group. However, refugee men from North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, and Asia do not show statistically significant differences in employment outcomes compared to Other European refugee men.

Among refugee women, those from North Africa and the Middle East face employment disadvantage and are 8.7 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to be employed. However, refugee women from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America do not differ significantly in employment likelihood from refugee women from Other Europe.

Unemployment outcomes

Among refugee men, only those from Latin America show a lower likelihood of unemployment and are 10.5 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to be unemployed than refugee men from Other Europe. In contrast, refugee men from North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, and Asia do not exhibit statistically significant differences in unemployment likelihood compared to their Other Europe refugee counterparts.

Among refugee women, those from North Africa and the Middle East are 7.8 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed. Similarly, Other African refugee women are 6.5 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed, and Latin American refugee women face the highest unemployment likelihood and are 13.9 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed than refugee women from Other Europe. However, refugee women from Asia do not show statistically significant differences in unemployment likelihood compared to Other European refugee women.

The overall findings from above align with the literature. [Ho and Turk-Ariss \(2018\)](#) found that the economic integration of migrants from North Africa and the Middle East tends to be slower than migrants from other regions. Additionally, [Münz \(2007\)](#) reported that women migrants from North Africa and the Middle East have particularly low employment rates, while those from Latin America, Africa, and the Middle East face high unemployment rates. The results for refugee women in this study are consistent with [Münz \(2007\)](#), particularly in the observed **negative employment gaps for North African and Middle Eastern women and high unemployment gaps for women from North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, and Latin America.**

Occupational outcomes

While no significant gender gaps are observed in high-skilled occupations among refugee groups, differences emerge in low-skilled occupation outcomes. Column (8) indicates that refugee women

from North Africa and the Middle East are 22.7 percentage points less likely to be employed in low-skilled jobs, while refugee women from Asia are 28.7 percentage points less likely to hold low-skilled occupations compared to their Other European counterparts. However, refugee women from Other Africa and Latin America do not significantly differ from Other European refugee women in low-skilled employment. On the other hand, refugee men of all the four regions are not statistically different from Other European refugee men.

Earnings distribution outcomes

Due to small sample sizes, gender differences in the top-income decile could not be analyzed.

For the bottom-income decile, refugee men from North Africa and the Middle East, and Other Africa do not significantly differ from refugee men from Other Europe in their likelihood of being in the lowest earnings decile. However, significant differences are observed among refugee women: Refugee women from Asia are 30.1 percentage points significantly less likely to be in the bottom-income decile. Refugee women from North Africa and the Middle East are 18.1 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to be in the bottom-income decile. Refugee women from Other Africa are not statistically different from the reference refugee women group.

While the findings on occupation and income distribution outcomes for refugee women may seem counterintuitive, two key factors could explain these patterns:

Lower labor market participation: Refugee women from Africa and the Middle East region tend to have lower labor force participation rates compared to both refugee men from the same regions and refugee women from Other Europe. Cultural norms may further restrict workforce participation for women from these regions.

Informal and undocumented work: Many refugee women from Africa and the Middle East region may be employed in informal and undocumented sectors, such as domestic work or caregiving, leading to underrepresentation in official labor statistics. As a result, refugee women from Other Europe appear more frequently in low-skilled jobs and the bottom-income decile than those from Africa and the Middle East regions.

Discussion and policy implications

Refugee women face a "triple penalty" in the labor market: Their refugee status, gender-based disadvantages, and lower levels of labor market skills contribute to this penalty. A study by [Brücker et al. \(2020\)](#) found that refugee women often have little or no formal education and limited work experience, hindering their economic integration. Additionally, the long migration journey, often marked by trauma and stress, combined with cultural differences, presents extra challenges for refugee women from the Middle East and African regions in integrating into EU labor markets. Cultural barriers further restrict labor force participation among refugee women from these regions.

While some EU countries have adopted a gender-sensitive approach in broader migrant integration strategies, others have implemented targeted policies specifically for migrant women, including language training, access to education, and support for labor market entry. Such policies aim to facilitate the socio-economic integration of migrant women ([European Commission, 2022](#)). Additionally, policy recommendations safeguard the rights of migrant and refugee women, emphasizing reception conditions, healthcare provision, education access, and employment opportunities ([Council of Europe, 2022](#)).

In conclusion, although refugee integration itself is a relatively recent policy challenge, there is an

urgent need for more robust, gender-specific economic integration policies. Tailored interventions, particularly for refugee women from the Middle Eastern and African regions, should focus on:

1. **Targeted skill-building programs** to address education and employment gaps.
2. **Recognition of informal work experiences** to increase access to formal employment.
3. **Early language training and vocational education** to improve long-term economic prospects.

By addressing these structural barriers, policymakers can enhance labor market participation, job quality, and income security for refugee women in EU countries.

Education differences in labor market outcomes among refugee groups

Panel B presents the estimates for refugee groups distinguishing between individuals with and without tertiary education.

Employment outcomes

Among refugee groups without tertiary education, refugees from North Africa and the Middle East are 12.2 percentage points less likely to be employed than refugees from Other European region. However, refugees from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America do not exhibit statistically significant differences from the reference group.

Employment disparities diminish for refugees with tertiary education. Refugees from North Africa and the Middle East, Other Africa, and Asia are not significantly different from the Other Europe refugee group. Refugees from Latin America are 2.2 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to be employed than their Other Europe counterparts.

Unemployment outcomes

Among refugees without tertiary education, those from North Africa and the Middle East are 7.7 percentage points more likely to be unemployed, while Other African refugees have a 7.5 percentage point (significant at a 5% confidence level) higher likelihood of unemployment. In contrast, refugees from Asia and Latin America do not differ significantly from the reference group in unemployment outcomes.

For tertiary-educated refugees, the disadvantage in unemployment likelihood observed for North African and Middle Eastern, and Other African refugees disappears. This suggests that having a tertiary education eliminates the unemployment gap for these groups. Similarly, tertiary-educated refugees from Asia and Latin America do not show significant differences from the reference group.

High-skilled occupational outcomes

Among refugee groups without tertiary education, no significant differences are observed in the likelihood of high-skilled employment compared to Other European refugees.

Among refugees with tertiary education, including those from North Africa and the Middle East, Asia, and Latin America do not significantly differ from Other European refugees in high-skilled occupation likelihood. However, refugees from Other Africa are 20.9 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to occupy high-skilled jobs.

Low-skilled occupational outcomes

Among refugees without tertiary education, no significant differences are observed between groups

in their likelihood of occupying elementary jobs.

For tertiary-educated refugees, a notable difference emerges for North African and Middle Eastern refugees who are 27 percentage points less likely to be employed in low-skilled jobs than Other European refugees. However, refugees from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America do not show significant differences from the reference group.

Earnings distribution

Due to limited sample sizes, earnings differences could only be analyzed for refugees in the top-income decile.

Among the refugee groups with no tertiary education in the bottom-income decile, refugees from North Africa and the Middle East are 17.3 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) and refugees from Asia are 27.4 percentage points less likely to be in the lowest earnings decile than Other European refugees. In contrast, Other African refugees do not show statistically significant differences from the reference group.

Discussion and policy implications

The results highlight the **critical role of tertiary education in reducing labor market disadvantages for refugees from North Africa and the Middle East, and Other Africa regions.**

Refugees from North Africa and the Middle East without tertiary education have significantly lower employment rates than Other European refugees. However having tertiary education, the employment gap disappears, making them equally likely to be employed.

Refugees from North Africa and the Middle East, and Other Africa without tertiary education have significantly higher unemployment rates. However, obtaining a tertiary degree eliminates this disadvantage.

Refugees from North Africa and the Middle East with tertiary education are considerably less likely to hold low-skilled jobs, suggesting that higher education significantly improves occupational outcomes for these groups.

These findings indicate that **while refugees from Africa and the Middle East regions face initial labor market disadvantages, tertiary education serves as a strong equalizer**, significantly improving their employment outcomes, reducing unemployment risks, and reducing the likelihood of occupying low-skilled jobs.

Studies by [Bonin \(2017\)](#); [Ichou et al. \(2022\)](#) found that migrants in the EU labor market tend to be positively selected based on educational attainment. The results from Panel B in Table 18 align with their findings, showing that even refugees from weaker origin regions can overcome significant labor market barriers if they obtain tertiary education. To improve the labor market integration of refugees from disadvantaged origin regions within the EU, two key policy interventions should be prioritized:

Recognition of foreign qualifications: Many refugees face bureaucratic hurdles in having their degrees recognized, limiting their ability to secure jobs that match their qualifications. Simplifying qualification recognition processes could enhance employment outcomes for refugees with existing tertiary education.

Encouraging host country education for refugees with low education levels: Access to higher education and vocational training should be promoted for refugees with lower education levels. **In-**

vestment in scholarship programs, tuition support, and language training can encourage refugees to pursue further education, significantly boosting their long-term employment outcomes.

By facilitating qualification recognition and promoting access to higher education, policymakers can significantly enhance refugees' integration into the EU labor market, particularly for those from North Africa and the Middle East, and Other Africa, where initial labor market disadvantages are more pronounced.

Language differences in labor market outcomes of refugees

Panel C presents the estimates for refugee groups distinguishing between individuals with and without advanced language proficiency of the destination country.

Employment outcomes

Among refugees without advanced proficiency in the destination country's language, those from North Africa and the Middle East are 10.4 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to be employed compared to the reference group. However, refugees from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America do not show statistically significant differences in employment likelihood.

Among refugees with advanced language proficiency, no significant differences are observed between North African and Middle Eastern refugees and the reference group. Similarly, refugees from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America do not show statistically significant differences in employment outcomes.

Unemployment outcomes

Among refugees without advanced language skills, those from North Africa and the Middle East are 8.1 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed, however, refugees from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America do not exhibit significant differences from the reference group.

Among refugees with advanced language proficiency, unemployment gaps disappear, as North African and Middle Eastern refugees are not statistically different from the reference group a pattern that also holds for Other African, Asian, and Latin American refugees.

High-skilled occupation outcomes

Refugees regardless of their language proficiency level, do not show statistically significant differences in the likelihood of being employed in high-skilled jobs compared to Other European refugees with similar host country language characteristics.

Low-skilled occupation outcomes

Among refugees without advanced language skills, those from North Africa and the Middle East are 16.4 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to be employed in low-skilled jobs, and refugees from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America are not statistically different from the reference group.

Among refugees with advanced language proficiency, no statistically significant differences are observed in low-skilled job outcomes of North African and Middle Eastern refugees compared to Other European refugees. Likewise, refugees from Other Africa, Asia, and Latin America do not show statistically significant differences compared to the reference group.

Earnings distribution

Due to limited sample sizes, estimates for high-income decile outcomes were not attainable.

For the bottom-income decile outcomes among refugees without advanced language proficiency, those from North Africa and the Middle East and Other Africa do not exhibit statistically significant differences from the reference group. However, Asian refugees are 38 percentage points less likely to be in the bottom-income decile compared to Other Europe refugees.

Among refugees with advanced language proficiency in the bottom-income decile, no significant differences are observed between refugee groups and the reference category.

Discussion and policy implications

The findings highlight significant disadvantages for North African and Middle Eastern refugees in employment, unemployment, and low-skilled job outcomes when they lack advanced host country language proficiency. Several studies emphasize the critical role of language skills in improving labor market integration.

Greater access to language training and labor market outcomes: [Kanas and Kosyakova \(2023\)](#) found that an increased supply of local language courses significantly enhanced the likelihood of refugees completing language training which led to a positive causal effect on their labor market integration.

Language training and employment in communication-intensive jobs: [Arendt et al. \(2023\)](#) found that refugees who completed language training were more likely to secure employment in communication-intensive jobs with higher wages. Furthermore, they were more likely to pursue additional education, which further improved their labor market outcomes.

Language distance and labor market integration: [Bar-Haim and Birgier \(2024\)](#) found that greater linguistic distance between a migrant's native language and the host country's language negatively impacts migrants' labor market integration. This includes lower employment rates, reduced labor force participation, and increased difficulties in job access.

A similar pattern emerges when examining low-skilled occupation outcomes. In Column (7), North African and Middle Eastern refugees without advanced language proficiency are 16.4 percentage points less likely to be employed in low-skilled jobs compared to Other European refugees. This suggests that language barriers extend beyond employment and unemployment challenges as they also restrict access to low-skilled jobs, possibly leading to:

Reliance on informal employment (e.g., domestic work, cash-in-hand jobs). **Delayed labor market entry**, as refugees may prioritize learning the language before seeking employment. **Job market exclusion**, as employers may hesitate to hire refugees with weak language skills, even for low-skilled positions. However, once North African and Middle Eastern refugees attain advanced language proficiency, their labor market outcomes become statistically insignificant from Other European refugees.

Given these findings, future policy interventions should focus on:

1. Expanding access to structured language training programs tailored to refugees from linguistically distant regions.
2. Accelerating early language acquisition through intensive courses, particularly for those with low host-country language proficiency.

3. Integrating language training with employment opportunities, such as on-the-job language training programs.

4. Investigating informal employment patterns among North African and Middle Eastern refugees to understand barriers to formal job access.

Overall, language proficiency is a key determinant of refugee labor market integration. Addressing language gaps through targeted policies and early interventions could significantly improve economic opportunities for North African and Middle Eastern refugees in EU countries.

Table 18: Heterogeneities among refugee groups based on gender, education, and language skills

	Employment		Unemployment		High-skilled job		Low-skilled job		Top-income decile		Bottom-income decile	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Panel A - Gender differences												
Gender:	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women	men	women
Other Europe (Omitted category)												
North Africa and Middle East	-0.046 (0.039)	-0.087* (0.039)	0.044 (0.029)	0.078** (0.029)	0.034 (0.047)	0.042 (0.063)	-0.018 (0.038)	-0.227*** (0.052)	0.000 (.)	-	-0.061 (0.101)	-0.181* (0.077)
Other Africa	0.057 (0.045)	-0.027 (0.043)	0.029 (0.031)	0.065* (0.032)	-0.023 (0.054)	-0.046 (0.062)	0.090 (0.049)	-0.073 (0.066)	0.000 (.)	-	-0.019 (0.116)	-0.023 (0.116)
Asia	0.042 (0.044)	0.004 (0.050)	-0.005 (0.031)	0.030 (0.033)	0.013 (0.053)	-0.020 (0.090)	0.049 (0.044)	-0.287*** (0.063)	0.000 (.)	-	0.000 (.)	-0.301*** (0.059)
Latin America	0.193** (0.064)	-0.046 (0.074)	-0.105* (0.048)	0.139* (0.062)	0.037 (0.100)	0.174 (0.098)	-0.047 (0.086)	-0.109 (0.102)	0.000 (.)	-	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
Observations	3,107	2,263	2,803	1,947	1,504	725	1,442	793	54	-	131	133
Panel B - Education differences												
Tertiary Education:	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Other Europe (Omitted category)												
North Africa and Middle East	-0.122*** (0.033)	0.018 (0.051)	0.077*** (0.022)	-0.030 (0.050)	0.032 (0.040)	-0.032 (0.081)	-0.070 (0.040)	-0.270*** (0.077)	0.000 (.)	-	-0.173** (0.062)	-
Other Africa	-0.032 (0.037)	0.104 (0.060)	0.075** (0.024)	-0.092 (0.050)	-0.002 (0.045)	-0.209* (0.091)	0.069 (0.047)	-0.052 (0.108)	0.000 (.)	-	-0.049 (0.094)	-
Asia	-0.000 (0.039)	0.055 (0.073)	0.030 (0.023)	-0.091 (0.064)	0.039 (0.049)	-0.127 (0.094)	0.017 (0.048)	-0.078 (0.108)	0.000 (.)	-	-0.274*** (0.045)	-
Latin America	-0.089 (0.066)	0.220** (0.073)	0.111 (0.066)	-0.083 (0.077)	-0.026 (0.087)	0.173 (0.185)	0.117 (0.128)	-0.112 (0.144)	0.000 (.)	-	0.000 (.)	-
Observations	4,138	1,243	3,779	961	1,491	596	1,747	334	21	-	246	-
Panel C - Language differences												
Advanced Proficiency:	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Other Europe (Omitted category)												
North Africa and Middle East	-0.104** (0.038)	-0.064 (0.040)	0.081** (0.030)	0.044 (0.026)	0.047 (0.047)	0.038 (0.060)	-0.164** (0.055)	-0.030 (0.038)	-	0.000 (.)	-0.096 (0.137)	0.078 (0.161)
Other Africa	0.004 (0.043)	-0.037 (0.048)	0.041 (0.032)	0.064 (0.034)	0.037 (0.051)	-0.088 (0.062)	0.030 (0.061)	0.040 (0.049)	-	0.000 (.)	-0.047 (0.132)	0.111 (0.123)
Asia	0.006 (0.044)	0.006 (0.058)	-0.018 (0.028)	0.069 (0.046)	0.089 (0.054)	-0.078 (0.068)	-0.110 (0.059)	0.058 (0.061)	-	0.000 (.)	-0.380*** (0.072)	0.000 (.)
Latin America	0.018 (0.080)	0.004 (0.072)	0.114 (0.095)	0.026 (0.054)	-0.086 (0.047)	0.090 (0.105)	0.003 (0.145)	0.074 (0.115)	-	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.460 (0.237)
Observations	2,967	2,449	2,680	2,064	841	1,252	1,137	1,120	-	64	91	186
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Individual Controls	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Entry Cohort*Destination Country	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Note: The table reports the coefficients of the refugee groups residing in the EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model for the dependent variables employment, unemployment, occupation, and income distribution. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. Panel A reports the gender differences, Panel B reports the tertiary and non-tertiary education differences, and Panel C reports the differences in not having and having advanced-level language skills of the host country. The sample comprises refugee groups aged between 20 and 64. All specifications include destination country survey year interaction dummies to capture the destination country and survey year fixed effects. The probit model includes gender, age category in five-year age groups, education, and language proficiency controls where needed. Other European refugees are the reference category. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate that the estimates are statistically different from refugees from Other Europe at 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This PhD thesis makes several key contributions to the literature on refugee labor market integration. First, it addresses a critical data gap by utilizing the newly available 2021 EU-LFS data to examine the labor market outcomes of refugees in the aftermath of the 2015 refugee crisis. This provides an updated perspective on refugee employment trends in the EU destination countries. Second, it fills the methodological gap by incorporating probit regression models to estimate the average marginal effects of labor market outcomes offering an alternative to traditional linear models used in previous studies. Third, it introduces a comparative graphical analysis of EU destination countries, using data from the 2014 and 2021 survey waves to assess employment and language proficiency rates of refugees and other migrants.

In addition, this thesis expands the scope of analysis by incorporating family characteristics, such as household composition, parental education, and urbanization degree, to examine their role in refugee labor market outcomes. It also contributes a regional perspective by analyzing refugees by their origin areas, shedding light on the unique challenges faced by different refugee groups in the EU labor market. Furthermore, the thesis explores the impact of economic recessions on refugee labor market trajectories. Lastly, the appendix offers a regional comparison of refugee integration across five main EU regions—Nordic, Anglo-Saxon, Eastern European, Mediterranean, and Continental Western Europe, highlighting the differences in welfare systems. Collectively, these contributions would enhance the understanding of refugee integration and provide new empirical insights into the structural barriers they face.

The findings underscore the transformative role of tertiary education in improving employment outcomes, reducing unemployment risks, and enhancing earnings for refugees. While refugees from North Africa and the Middle East, and Other Africa face substantial initial disadvantages, obtaining a tertiary degree significantly improves their economic integration. These results suggest that effective qualification recognition mechanisms and expanded access to higher education should be central to refugee integration policies. Such measures can help bridge employment gaps, reduce dependence on social welfare, and enable refugees to contribute more effectively to their host economies.

Beyond education, language proficiency emerges as a critical determinant of employment, unemployment, and occupational outcomes. North African and Middle Eastern refugees, in particular, experience severe disadvantages due to language barriers. Strengthening language training programs can substantially reduce these disparities, enhancing refugees' ability to compete in the EU labor markets. Additionally, the language distance between a refugee's native language and the host country's language may play a crucial role in determining employment success, a future research area that could be explored.

Despite some positive findings, this research confirms that refugees in the EU labor market face persistent and significant labor market disadvantages. Even when they possess strong socio-demographic characteristics, they remain underemployed, are concentrated in low-skilled jobs, and have high unemployment rates—especially those from North Africa and the Middle East region. Gender differences further exacerbate these challenges, with refugee women encountering particularly severe employment barriers. These findings highlight the urgent need for targeted policy interventions, such as skills recognition programs, employer incentives for hiring refugees, expanded vocational training, and gender-sensitive labor market strategies. Addressing recession-induced disadvantages, improving access to advanced language training, and supporting tertiary-educated refugees could further enhance their employment outcomes and facilitate long-term economic integration.

Future research could explore additional factors influencing refugee employment outcomes. One potential avenue is examining the role of health conditions in employment likelihood. Previous studies have found that work and study migrants may have better employment outcomes partly due to superior health conditions (Giuntella et al., 2018; Kone et al., 2019). Investigating whether similar health gaps exist among refugee groups could offer valuable policy insights. Additionally, further research could assess how sectoral demand, employer perceptions of refugees, and informal labor market participation influence long-term refugee employment trajectories in EU destination countries.

In conclusion, while this thesis advances the understanding of refugee labor market integration, its findings underscore the need for continued efforts to remove structural barriers and enhance economic opportunities for refugees in the EU labor market. Future research should continue to explore innovative policy solutions that promote fairer labor market access and long-term social and economic inclusion for refugees.

Appendix

Labor market outcomes of refugees across the five main EU regions

Table 19 presents the coefficients of the probit regression model estimated from equation (1) for the likelihood of employment, unemployment, high and low-skilled occupation, and top and bottom-income decile for refugees, economic migrants, and non-economic migrants compared to natives (reference category). Migrant destination countries in Europe are categorized into five main regions: Nordic (Denmark, Finland, Norway, Sweden), Anglo-Saxon (Ireland), Eastern European (Croatia, Slovenia), Mediterranean (Cyprus, Greece, Spain, Italy, Portugal), and Continental Western European (Austria, Belgium, Switzerland, Germany, France, Luxembourg, Netherlands) regions.

1. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Nordic region

Panel A presents the labor market outcomes of refugees in the Nordic region relative to natives. At baseline, refugees are significantly disadvantaged: they are 21.7 percentage points less likely to be employed, 12.6 percentage points more likely to be unemployed, 25.2 percentage points less likely to work in high-skilled jobs, 11.1 percentage points more likely to occupy low-skilled jobs, and 29.2 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to belong to the bottom-income decile. After accounting for individual socio-demographic characteristics, these gaps narrow to a slight extent. Employment and unemployment gaps reduce to -19.6 and 11.8 percentage points, while the high-skilled occupation gap considerably shrinks to -14.2 percentage points. The low-skilled occupation gap decreases to 6.3 percentage points, but the likelihood of being in the bottom-income decile increases to 30.7 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level).

Among the three migrant groups (refugees, economic migrants, and non-economic migrants), economic migrants exhibit relatively better labor market outcomes in the Nordic region. While the non-economic migrants at the baseline start with smaller gaps compared to refugees, the latter group demonstrates stronger labor market characteristics, making them more likely to gain employment, less likely to remain unemployed, more likely to be in high-skilled jobs, and less likely to be in low-skilled jobs compared to their non-economic migrant counterparts.

A study by Heikkilä (2020) found that refugee youth in Nordic countries have weaker labor market attachment compared to their native peers. Additional challenges faced by refugees in Nordic countries include intermittent employment, periods of unemployment, and periodic reliance on training and voluntary work. In particular, refugees without upper secondary education, experience larger employment gaps in the Nordic region. Another issue is that refugees who do not have an upper secondary education are less likely to participate in host country education, employment, or training programs in Nordic countries. This may explain the significant initial employment gaps observed in Table 19 relative to other migrant groups. Refugees in the Nordic region often lack work experience, social networks, and uninterrupted education. While this is the case, many refugees report that the traineeship programs they participate in are ineffective in improving employability. On the other hand, employers cite insufficient language skills and cultural barriers as reasons for not hiring refugees. However, refugees who are employed generally receive positive feedback from their employers.

Additionally, dispersal policies, which are still implemented in countries like Denmark, Norway, and Finland, exacerbate these challenges. By dispersing refugees to areas away from ethnic enclaves and urban centers, dispersal policies reduce access to job opportunities and increase the likelihood of mismatches in employment due to the limited geographic mobility of refugees. Research by Fasani et al. (2022) demonstrates that refugees affected by dispersal policies exhibit lower labor market

participation and are less likely to secure skilled employment compared to those not subject to such policies.

Despite starting with a large significant initial labor market disadvantage, refugees possess stronger socio-demographic potential in the Nordic region that reduces the labor market gap. Targeted interventions in the Nordic region, such as mentorship programs for young refugees and early career guidance for those without secondary education, could help harness their skills and improve their integration into the Nordic labor market. Such initiatives could motivate refugees and enhance their contribution to the Nordic economies. Additionally, dispersal policies that impede refugee employment opportunities should be revised by providing accommodation close to their ethnic enclaves.

Welfare system in the Nordic region

Refugees in the Nordic region benefit from accommodation and food, healthcare, and monetary support during their asylum claim. Additionally, language and cultural training, vocational training, and employment assistance are provided to adapt to the Nordic society and integrate into the labor market ([Nordic Health and Welfare Statistics, nd](#)). Furthermore, the Nordic program on integration brings the countries in the Nordic region together in sharing their experiences and building effective strategies for socio-economic integration practices of refugees and other migrants ([Nordregio, nd](#)).

2. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Anglo-Saxon region

Panel B compares the labor market outcomes of refugees in the Anglo-Saxon region to natives. Only the data from Ireland is used for this analysis, as the United Kingdom is excluded from the study because of the data unavailability of the UK in the 2021 survey wave.

At baseline, there are no statistically significant differences between refugees and natives in employment, unemployment, and low-skilled occupation outcomes. However, refugees are 24.3 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to work in high-skilled occupations. After accounting for individual socio-demographic characteristics, the gap in high-skilled occupations also becomes statistically insignificant. Due to the data unavailability income deciles are not analyzed for this region.

Among the three migrant groups, economic migrants exhibit relatively better labor market outcomes and are even more likely to be employed than natives. Unlike the Nordic region, where non-economic migrants start with smaller initial employment gaps compared to refugees, in the Anglo-Saxon region, refugees demonstrate relatively stronger employment likelihood than non-economic migrants.

In conclusion, labor market access for individuals seeking international protection in Ireland is a relatively recent development. Refugees were granted access to the Irish labor market only from mid-2018. Before this, Ireland implemented a permanent employment ban on asylum seekers. Consequently, there is limited literature specifically addressing the economic integration of refugees in Ireland.

A study by [McGinnity et al. \(2020\)](#) conducted on migrant integration before the COVID-19 pandemic found that migrants in Ireland were more likely to be employed than Irish nationals, and no statistically significant unemployment difference was found between migrants and Irish citizens. The results in Table 19 broadly show a similar picture concerning employment and unemployment outcomes of migrants in Ireland. Additionally, research by [Privalko et al. \(2023\)](#) on Ireland found variations in labor market outcomes among refugee groups: while white and Asian refugees performed relatively well, African refugees faced significant disadvantages in the labor market. Recent research by [Po-](#)

[Iakowski and Cunniffe \(2023\)](#) indicates that by 2022, the labor market gap between African-origin refugees and Irish nationals had become statistically insignificant. The results in the table are consistent with this evolving body of literature, reinforcing the observation that refugees in the Anglo-Saxon region, particularly Ireland experience improved integration into the labor market over time.

Welfare system in the Anglo-Saxon region

Refugees in the Anglo-Saxon region (Ireland) benefit from accommodation, food, healthcare, and monetary support during their asylum claims. Additionally, individuals with recognized refugee status and temporary protection enjoy equal benefits as Irish citizens, such as job search allowance, disability allowance, single parent allowance, and child benefits ([Asylum Information Database \(AIDA\), 2024](#)). Furthermore, Ireland runs a Community-based Sponsorship Program encouraging local communities to support refugees in their socio-integration ([Global Compact on Refugees, nd](#)).

3. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Eastern European region

Panel C presents the labor market outcomes of refugees in the Eastern European region compared to natives. At baseline, refugees are 9.5 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) less likely to be employed. However, there is no significant difference in unemployment likelihood between refugees and natives. Refugees are 9 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to hold high-skilled occupations and 9.7 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level) more likely to be employed in low-skilled occupations. There are no significant differences in the top and bottom-decile earnings between refugees and natives. After accounting for individual socio-demographic characteristics, the employment likelihood of refugees is no longer significantly different from natives. Refugees, however, exhibit a 5.6 percentage point (significant at a 10% confidence level) higher likelihood of unemployment, while their representation in high-skilled and low-skilled occupations is not significantly different from natives.

While it appears that refugees in the Eastern European region exhibit relatively favorable labor market outcomes, only a small proportion of individuals receive refugee status in this region. Countries such as Croatia and Slovenia are primarily regarded as transit destinations for refugees who aim to settle in other parts of Europe, and therefore the scarcity of refugee labor market research in this region is notable. For instance, Croatia has historically hosted a limited number of foreigners, most of whom originate from Southeast Europe. This shared regional background facilitates smoother integration into the Croatian labor market. However, Croatia lacks comprehensive migrant integration policies. Despite this, societal attitudes towards immigrants in Croatia are relatively positive compared to Slovenia. Refugees in Croatia often report fewer cultural barriers to integration, as highlighted by [Gregurović and Župarić-Iljić \(2023\)](#). This general acceptance provides a foundation for fostering social networks between refugees and native populations in Croatia. Nevertheless, academic studies on refugee integration in Croatia remain limited. Given the significant influx of refugees since the 2015 European migrant crisis, there is considerable potential for future research in this area.

On the other hand, Slovenia imposes restrictive labor market access policies for asylum seekers. Individuals applying for international protection are permitted to work only after a nine-month waiting period. Furthermore, if an initial asylum decision is negative, they are barred from working during the entire application process, which can span several years. [Keuc \(2020\)](#) recommends reducing this initial waiting period to a maximum of three months to facilitate faster labor market integration and foster legal employment opportunities for refugees in Slovenia.

Eastern European countries, such as Slovenia and Croatia, are also characterized as emigration nations, with many citizens seeking employment abroad. This emigration dynamic may contribute to

relatively smaller labor market gaps between natives and refugees. However, the broader migrant and refugee policies in this region require substantial improvement. Historically, the governments of these countries have not faced significant refugee crises. However, the 2015 European migrant crisis marked a turning point, sparking discussions about refugee inflows in the Eastern European region, but the policy responses remain inadequate in this region. Targeted measures are the weakest link in this region's integration system, which has not yet adapted to the increasing refugee inflows. As global migration continues to rise due to natural disasters and humanitarian crises, Eastern European countries must develop and implement effective refugee integration strategies.

Welfare system in the Eastern European region

Refugee integration programs in the Eastern European region show some differences between Croatia and Slovenia, though both countries implement welfare programs to support refugees. In Croatia, refugees granted international protection receive benefits of accommodation, food, healthcare, housing allowance, and child benefits (including free education for children up to a certain age). Unemployment allowance is provided to refugees (who are granted international protection) similar to those of citizens. Additionally, language and vocational training programs are available to facilitate refugee integration ([Council of Europe, nd](#); [European Council on Refugees and Exiles \(ECRE\), nda](#)).

Similarly, Slovenia provides refugees with basic support, covering accommodation, food, and healthcare, while granting unrestricted access to the labor market. Refugees can also access job search and job-matching assistance, language training, and scholarships for higher education. Furthermore, free education is available for refugee children.

However, a significant challenge in the Eastern European region is the limited funding available for refugee integration compared to Western European countries. This financial constraint hinders the implementation of comprehensive welfare programs necessary for effective refugee integration ([European Council on Refugees and Exiles \(ECRE\), ndb](#)).

4. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Mediterranean region

Panel D explores the labor market outcomes of refugees in the Mediterranean region compared to natives. At baseline, refugees exhibit similar employment rates to natives however, they are 5.9 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to be unemployed, 10 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) less likely to hold high-skilled jobs, and 8 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to occupy low-skilled jobs. There is no significant difference between refugees and natives in earnings across the top and bottom-income distributions. When individual socio-demographic characteristics are considered, the refugee-native employment gap widens to 8.3 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level), and the unemployment gap widens to 7 percentage points (significant at a 5% confidence level). The high-skilled occupation gap increases to -18.1 percentage points, and the low-skilled occupation gap increases to 15 percentage points. The income gap in the bottom decile increases to 14.5 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level), although the top-income decile remains insignificant. Economic migrants in the Mediterranean region perform relatively well in employment likelihood compared to their native counterparts. Among the migrant groups, refugees generally fare better in employment and earnings distribution than non-economic migrants.

Italy has implemented relatively comprehensive refugee integration measures in the Mediterranean region, which remains in the early stages of policy development. For example, under the SPAR (Sistema di Protezione per Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati) system, asylum seekers in the second reception phase have equal rights as Italian nationals, including access to employment and training programs.

The SPAR system typically lasts six months, providing refugees with accommodation, psychological and legal support, healthcare, food, language training, vocational programs, internships, and social integration initiatives. However, Italy lacks targeted labor market integration measures for refugees. Additional challenges include differences in integration services between reception centers and Public Employment Services (PES), delays in asylum registration, and weak coordination among employment services and refugee integration institutions ([European Parliament and Policy, 2018](#)).

In Greece, the pre-requirement for asylum seekers to obtain work permits has been removed, allowing refugees to access legal employment more easily. Beneficiaries of international protection are entitled to the same employment rights and unemployment benefits as Greek nationals. However, systemic issues persist. Labor market integration measures, such as language training and credential recognition remain fragmented and underdeveloped that are often implemented by NGOs. Also, the prioritization of citizens and EU nationals in the labor market further hinders newly recognized refugees' employment opportunities, particularly given the challenging economic conditions in Greece coupled with the 2015 refugee influx. Refugees also face barriers to vocational training, which requires proof of educational qualifications that many refugees fail to provide ([European Parliament and Policy, 2018](#)).

A study conducted by [Fellini \(2018\)](#) found that in Southern European countries such as Italy and Spain, migrants face a lower risk of unemployment but are more likely to occupy low-skilled jobs. For instance, reliance on PES for job placements often results in refugees being channeled into short-term, low-paying jobs in EU countries. Another study by [Addison and Portugal \(2002\)](#) on Portugal's labor market revealed that employers often view PES as a last resort to recruit labor. Employers primarily use PES to benefit from government subsidies for hiring young and inexperienced workers, a practice that undermines the recognition of refugee human capital. This highlights the structural limitations of PES in facilitating meaningful labor market integration of refugees and underscores the need for more effective policies to leverage refugee skills and improve their employment outcomes. Cyprus, unlike many EU countries, has a well-organized procedure for recognizing refugees' qualifications. However, the procedures are often reported to be time-consuming and lengthy. In Cyprus, occupational restrictions limit refugees to seeking employment only in certain unskilled areas, and asylum seekers can only access the labor market six months after their asylum claim.

Welfare system in the Mediterranean region

Welfare programs for refugees in the Mediterranean region are managed at the national level, with each country implementing its own system of support. In Greece, the ESTIA (Emergency Support to Integration and Accommodation) program oversees accommodation and healthcare services for asylum seekers, while refugee children have access to education ([International Organization for Migration, nd](#)).

In Italy, the SPRAR/SIPROIMI system (Protection System for Refugees and Asylum Seekers) facilitates accommodation, healthcare, socio-integration, and legal assistance. It also provides access to vocational training, and internship programs to support refugees' integration into the labor market ([Italian Ministry of Health, nd](#); [Italian Ministry of the Interior, nda,n](#); [Refugee Council Italy, nd](#)).

Spain addresses accommodation and integration needs through temporary shelters and additional housing support. Refugees also receive healthcare services and benefit from free language and cultural education that also includes refugee children ([Comisión Española de Ayuda al Refugiado, nd](#)).

Portugal promotes refugee integration through community sponsorship programs, encouraging local communities to participate in accommodation and support efforts. Refugees have access to healthcare, and refugee children receive free language and cultural education ([Portuguese Council for Refugees,](#)

nd).

In Cyprus, refugees are provided with accommodation, food, and financial assistance to cover basic needs. They also receive healthcare, legal support, and free education for children up to a certain age. Additionally, vocational and language training is available to help refugees enter the labor market. However, employment opportunities remain restricted to specific sectors until their refugee status is officially recognized ([Asylum Service of Cyprus, nd](#); [Cyprus Ministry of Interior, nda,n](#)).

5. Labor market outcomes of refugees in the Continental Western European region

Panel E highlights the labor market outcomes of refugees in the Continental Western European region compared to natives. Refugees are 23.9 percentage points less likely to be employed, 5.6 percentage points more likely to be unemployed, 27 percentage points less likely to work in high-skilled occupations, and 15.6 percentage points more likely to hold low-skilled jobs. Additionally, they are 6.7 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile and 3.6 percentage points (significant at a 10% confidence level) more likely to fall in the bottom-income decile.

When individual characteristics are controlled, the labor market outcomes of refugees slightly improve, but significant gaps persist. Refugees remain 19.8 percentage points less likely to be employed and 5 percentage points more likely to be unemployed. The likelihood of working in high-skilled occupations narrows to -16.6 percentage points, while the likelihood of being employed in low-skilled occupations narrows to 11.4 percentage points. Furthermore, the income decile gaps widen, with refugees being 7 percentage points less likely to be in the top-income decile and 8 percentage points more likely to fall in the bottom-income decile. Overall, the labor market gaps of refugees relative to natives are considerably larger in the Western European region than in the Mediterranean region, highlighting the significant labor market challenges refugees face when seeking asylum in Western European countries.

Economic migrants in the Continental Western European region display employment outcomes comparable to natives. Specifically, after adjusting for individual characteristics, economic migrants show no statistically significant differences in employment and bottom-income decile outcomes. Their likelihood of reaching the top-income decile is also relatively similar to natives. On the other hand, refugees fare worse than non-economic migrants in their labor market outcomes in this region.

Refugees in Western Europe face lower employment rates compared to those in the Mediterranean region. Research by [Fellini \(2018\)](#) highlights that immigrants in the Southern European region have lower unemployment rates but are more often employed in low-skilled jobs than their immigrant counterparts in the Western European region. The results in the table align with this pattern: refugees in the Mediterranean region exhibit less likelihood of unemployment and are more likely to hold low-skilled jobs (even after accounting for individual characteristics) compared to refugees in the Western European region. Additionally, the Western European region accommodates a larger share of refugees than the Mediterranean region, which may partly explain these differences.

The labor market integration of refugees in the Continental Western European region is burdened with both complexities and structural barriers. Prolonged asylum procedures and the spatial dispersion of refugees hinder both networking with locals and access to employment opportunities for refugees. For example, in Switzerland, such challenges significantly impede effective refugee labor market integration.

Skills mismatch is another critical issue. Refugees often have qualifications and work experience that do not align with the job market demands of the host countries. For instance, in Germany, vocational

training is essential for employment, but many refugees lack access to these programs because of the qualification mismatch that they bring from their home countries. Although countries like Germany and the Netherlands face labor shortages, bureaucratic hurdles and legal restrictions often prevent refugees from filling these gaps. Consequently, native workers and other migrant groups dominate the job market, and many job vacancies are left unfilled despite the need for employees where refugee human capital could be utilized (Martín et al., 2016).

Cultural barriers and social isolation further hamper the integration of refugees in Continental Western Europe. Many refugees, especially those from non-European cultural backgrounds face difficulties adapting to Western societal norms. Challenges such as language acquisition are worsened by trauma and limited prior education of refugees. Political and public resistance to accepting refugees from certain regions, such as Africa and the Middle East, is prevalent in countries like Belgium, where such groups are less welcomed compared to European-origin refugees. This discrimination and social exclusion hinder refugees' successful integration into both Western European societies and labor markets (Kosyakova and Kogan, 2022).

Welfare system in Continental Western European region

Welfare programs in Continental Western Europe provide a range of support measures for refugees and asylum seekers. These include temporary accommodation during the asylum process, financial assistance to cover basic needs, access to healthcare, and language training. Additionally, integration initiatives offer support in securing employment, qualification recognition programs, legal assistance, and social inclusion efforts to facilitate long-term settlement (on Refugees, 2025); (of Vienna, nd); (, AIDA); (Fedasil, nd); (Belgium, nd); (, AIDA); (, AIDA); (Refugies.info, nd); (Project, nd); (, AIDA); (Netherlands, nd); (Foundation, nd); (Ministry of Family Affairs, ndb); (Ministry of Family Affairs, nda); (Luxembourg, nd); (, AIDA); (Council, nd); (, AIDA); (Commission, nd).

6. Concluding remarks

Before 2015, Europe was unprepared for the refugee crisis. In response to the crisis, EU countries have recently begun implementing welfare programs aiming to foster effective socio-economic integration of refugees. However, structural barriers and complexities continue to hinder the successful implementation of the welfare programs. Limited resources and budget constraints contribute to these challenges, even though migration has become increasingly inevitable due to war and natural disasters in refugee-origin countries, and systemic inefficiencies continue to surface in EU host countries.

Multiple factors, including economic conditions, employment opportunities, and state-led welfare programs influence the choice of the destination country for refugees. While anti-immigrant political parties often argue that refugees are primarily drawn to generous welfare systems, in reality, refugees do not receive the same level of benefits as natives of EU destination countries. A weak positive correlation exists between welfare generosity and the number of asylum applications received by EU countries. Furthermore, the rise of populist parties and restrictive labor market policies have not significantly deterred refugee inflows (Di Iasio and Wahba, 2023).

A more coordinated approach among EU countries is necessary to address inefficiencies in the current asylum framework. The fragmented nature of national welfare systems has led to high initial costs and limited long-term benefits due to slow refugee economic integration. Since EU countries do not receive equal budget allocations for refugee welfare, a more effective strategy would involve aligning refugee human capital with the needs of the aging European workforce. Accelerating economic integration would not only improve resource efficiency but also enhance the sustainability of welfare provisions.

The uncertainty surrounding asylum status often discourages refugees from investing in the host country's human capital. Granting immediate access to labor markets, alongside language and vocational training could mitigate this issue. While refugees receive financial and livelihood support from the outset of their asylum process, targeted interventions are crucial for successful labor market integration. Particular attention should be given to refugee youth, refugees with lower secondary education, and refugee women, who often face more prominent economic barriers. Additionally, qualification recognition programs should be strengthened to enable refugees to access skills training programs more effectively.

EU countries that continue to enforce dispersal policies should reconsider their approach, as such policies often restrict refugee access to urban areas where employment opportunities are abundant, including better occupation abilities. Overall, refugee economic integration in Europe remains a complex challenge. While it continues to adjust to the ongoing inflow of asylum seekers, developing effective long-term policies remains an evolving process. Overcoming the short-term focus of nationalist political parties will be essential in designing sustainable and inclusive integration strategies at the EU level.

Table 19: Labor market outcomes of refugees across the five main EU regions

Panel (A) Nordic region												
	Employment		Unemployment		High-skill		Low-skill		Top-income		Bottom-income	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Natives (Omitted category)												
Economic migrants	0.011 (0.010)	-0.010 (0.015)	0.019** (0.007)	0.019* (0.009)	-0.079*** (0.020)	-0.099*** (0.016)	0.051*** (0.011)	0.072*** (0.015)	-0.049* (0.025)	-0.012 (0.023)	0.043 (0.032)	0.052 (0.036)
Non-economic migrants	-0.085*** (0.007)	-0.091*** (0.008)	0.059*** (0.005)	0.053*** (0.006)	-0.081*** (0.012)	-0.085*** (0.010)	0.066*** (0.007)	0.071*** (0.009)	-0.052*** (0.013)	-0.022 (0.013)	0.070*** (0.019)	0.063** (0.020)
Refugees	-0.217*** (0.015)	-0.196*** (0.016)	0.126*** (0.013)	0.118*** (0.014)	-0.252*** (0.022)	-0.142*** (0.020)	0.111*** (0.016)	0.063*** (0.015)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.292* (0.127)	0.307* (0.132)
Observations	705,797	630,819	705,797	630,819	346,444	308,955	346,444	308,955	138,591	129,628	138,607	129,644

Panel (B) Anglo-Saxon region												
	Employment		Unemployment		High-skill		Low-skill		Top-income		Bottom-income	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Natives (Omitted category)												
Economic migrants	0.103*** (0.016)	0.067* (0.026)	0.015 (0.010)	0.007 (0.016)	0.054* (0.026)	-0.040 (0.024)	0.050** (0.016)	0.119*** (0.029)	-	-	-	-
Non-economic migrants	-0.040** (0.015)	-0.097*** (0.020)	0.013 (0.007)	0.024 (0.012)	0.034 (0.020)	-0.030 (0.020)	0.009 (0.011)	0.033 (0.023)	-	-	-	-
Refugees	-0.103 (0.081)	-0.192 (0.113)	0.067 (0.051)	0.108 (0.081)	-0.243* (0.095)	-0.167 (0.088)	0.082 (0.097)	0.069 (0.117)	-	-	-	-
Observations	705,797	630,819	705,797	630,819	346,444	308,955	346,444	308,955	-	-	-	-

Panel (C) Eastern European region												
	Employment		Unemployment		High-skill		Low-skill		Top-income		Bottom-income	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Natives (Omitted category)												
Economic migrants	-0.050* (0.021)	-0.012 (0.019)	-0.003 (0.012)	0.006 (0.013)	-0.157*** (0.034)	-0.083** (0.031)	0.143*** (0.029)	0.120*** (0.023)	-0.058** (0.020)	-0.062*** (0.015)	-0.013 (0.019)	0.019 (0.026)
Non-economic migrants	-0.105*** (0.015)	-0.069*** (0.014)	0.031** (0.010)	0.033** (0.010)	-0.045 (0.026)	-0.025 (0.023)	0.060*** (0.016)	0.044** (0.015)	-0.031 (0.016)	-0.022 (0.016)	0.016 (0.018)	0.003 (0.018)
Refugees	-0.095** (0.032)	-0.056 (0.030)	0.041 (0.021)	0.056* (0.022)	-0.090* (0.046)	0.012 (0.040)	0.097** (0.036)	0.041 (0.027)	-0.006 (0.044)	0.008 (0.042)	0.104 (0.070)	0.078 (0.060)
Observations	705,797	630,819	705,797	630,819	346,444	308,955	346,444	308,955	138,591	129,628	138,607	129,644

(Panel D)												
Mediterranean region												
	Employment		Unemployment		High-skill		Low-skill		Top-income		Bottom-income	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Natives (Omitted category)												
Economic migrants	0.050*** (0.005)	0.025*** (0.005)	0.052*** (0.004)	0.043*** (0.004)	-0.240*** (0.005)	-0.213*** (0.007)	0.209*** (0.007)	0.148*** (0.006)	-0.088*** (0.003)	-0.078*** (0.004)	0.124*** (0.007)	0.109*** (0.007)
Non-economic migrants	-0.109*** (0.005)	-0.108*** (0.005)	0.055*** (0.004)	0.038*** (0.003)	-0.088*** (0.007)	-0.101*** (0.007)	0.092*** (0.006)	0.076*** (0.005)	-0.040*** (0.005)	-0.024*** (0.006)	0.104*** (0.008)	0.070*** (0.007)
Refugees	-0.014 (0.029)	-0.083** (0.031)	0.059* (0.023)	0.070** (0.026)	-0.100* (0.041)	-0.181*** (0.041)	0.080* (0.031)	0.150*** (0.036)	0.021 (0.084)	0.007 (0.080)	0.104 (0.058)	0.145* (0.061)
Observations	705,797	630,819	705,797	630,819	346,444	308,955	346,444	308,955	138,591	129,628	138,607	129,644

(Panel E)												
Continental Western European region												
	Employment		Unemployment		High-skill		Low-skill		Top-income		Bottom-income	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Natives (Omitted category)												
Economic migrants	-0.002 (0.006)	-0.005 (0.008)	0.018*** (0.004)	0.024*** (0.005)	-0.112*** (0.009)	-0.098*** (0.009)	0.097*** (0.006)	0.086*** (0.008)	0.057*** (0.010)	0.019* (0.008)	-0.020*** (0.006)	0.007 (0.009)
Non-economic migrants	-0.138*** (0.004)	-0.116*** (0.005)	0.027*** (0.003)	0.035*** (0.003)	-0.087*** (0.006)	-0.072*** (0.006)	0.087*** (0.004)	0.072*** (0.005)	-0.042*** (0.005)	-0.020*** (0.006)	0.036*** (0.006)	0.052*** (0.008)
Refugees	-0.239*** (0.011)	-0.198*** (0.012)	0.056*** (0.006)	0.050*** (0.007)	-0.270*** (0.012)	-0.166*** (0.017)	0.156*** (0.012)	0.114*** (0.013)	-0.067*** (0.012)	-0.070*** (0.007)	0.036* (0.017)	0.080*** (0.023)
Observations	705,797	630,819	705,797	630,819	346,444	308,955	346,444	308,955	138,591	129,628	138,607	129,644
Destination country*Survey year	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Individual Controls		X		X		X		X		X		X

Note: The table reports the labor market outcomes of refugees, non-economic and economic migrants of the Nordic region in Panel A, the Anglo-Saxon region in Panel B, the Eastern European region in Panel C, the Mediterranean region in Panel D, and the Continental Western European region in Panel E. Natives are considered as the reference category. The analysis is conducted on individuals residing in EU destination countries estimated through the average marginal effects of the probit regression model. Sampling weights are used in the analysis. The sample includes all individuals aged between 20 and 64. All specifications include destination country and survey year interaction dummies to capture the destination country and survey year fixed effects, and individual controls include gender, age category, education, urbanization degree, household composition, and parents' education. In the age category, 20-24 is the excluded category; in gender, male is the excluded category; in education, low education is the excluded category; in urbanization degree, cities are the excluded category; in household composition, single adult with or without children is the excluded category; in parent's education, low education is the excluded category. The information on income decile is only available for the 2014 survey wave. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. *** and ** and * indicate the estimates are statistically different from natives at a 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels. Otherwise, the estimates are not statistically different.

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